

Extreme Food Risk Analytics

D5.3.3: Use-case Plan, Reports & Recommendations

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Glossary of terms and abbreviations used

Abbreviations / Acronyms	Meaning
AI	Artificial Intelligence
API	Application Programming Interface
LLM	Large Language Model
LIMS	Laboratory Information Management System
ML	Machine Learning
MLP	Multilayer Perceptron
sMAPE	Symmetric Mean Absolute Percentage Error (forecast-accuracy metric)
UC	Use Case
UI	User Interface
sMAPE	Symmetric Mean Absolute Percentage Error

1. Executive Summary

This deliverable presents the results of the 2nd piloting cycle of the EFRA project, focusing on the evaluation of the final versions of the decision-support tools across all participating use cases. In this cycle, the emphasis shifts from internal testing to broader engagement with external users, allowing the project team to validate tool performance, usability, and practical value in real operational settings.

The report covers the full set of EFRA pilots, including the three original use cases from the 1st Piloting Cycle - Risk Predictions for Poultry Pathogens (UC#1), Food-Safety Optimal Pesticide Use (UC#2), and Informing Regulatory Decisions with Food Risk Intelligence (UC#3), and introduces a 4th, standalone use case on Mycotoxins in Animal Feed and Poultry Feed (UC#4). This new use case expands the scope of EFRA by incorporating both private laboratory data and publicly available incident trends, enabling more comprehensive forecasting and risk-assessment capabilities.

The 2nd cycle applies a structured evaluation approach combining qualitative insights from stakeholders and quantitative assessment against predefined KPIs. These evaluations focus on the final functionalities of each decision-support tool, assessing model performance, user experience, operational relevance, and potential business impact. The findings highlight the tools' readiness for real-world deployment and identify a small set of targeted refinements to support future scaling.

Overall, this deliverable consolidates the outcomes of the 2nd piloting cycle, summarises stakeholder perspectives, evaluates the maturity of the EFRA tools, and provides focused recommendations to guide their continued development and broader application.

2. Introduction

The goal of this section is to provide a brief outline of the **objectives** of the at-hand EFRA Deliverable (outlined in **Table 1**) and how the rest of the document is structured to achieve them.

Table 1: Adherence to EFRA GA Deliverable & Tasks Descriptions

EFRA GA Component Title	EFRA GA Component Outline
Task 5.2 Experimental Methodology, Use-case Plan, and Recommendations	This task will design use-case, evaluation and valuation activities, subsequently deployed in T5.4, that will measure how real-life decisions can be supported with EFRA tools and periodically process, analyse and distil user feedback from the use-case trials, in order to generate recommendations to help inform the various project tasks and activities.

This deliverable aligns with the objectives set out in Task 5.2, as summarised in Table 1, and focuses on documenting the evaluation activities carried out during the 2nd piloting cycle of the EFRA project. Building on the methodology established in the 1st iteration (D5.3.1), and the 2nd iteration (D5.3.2), the 2nd cycle places greater emphasis on engaging external users, validating the final versions of the decision-support tools, and gathering practical insights to support their refinement and future deployment.

Chapter 3 introduces the structure and objectives of the 2nd piloting cycle. It outlines the overall evaluation process followed by the piloting partners, presents the diagram of the EFRA piloting workflow, and summarises the use cases, scenarios, and pilots included in this cycle. This chapter also provides an overview of the decision-support tools evaluated and the piloting activities implemented, as documented in the corresponding tables.

Chapter 4 presents the complete qualitative and quantitative evaluation results for each pilot. For every use case, the chapter follows a consistent structure that includes a qualitative evaluation summary, progress against the pilot plan, actors involved, implementation status, deployed EFRA components, datasets used and observed impact. It also documents the modifications made between the 1st and 2nd piloting cycles, followed by a quantitative assessment against domain-specific and technological KPIs and the corresponding pilot timeline.

Chapter 5 consolidates the evaluation results from the 2nd piloting cycle. It begins with stakeholder insights gathered across all pilots, including user demographics, profiles, and needs. It then presents the detailed evaluation findings for each EFRA decision-support tool, covering stakeholder feedback, functionality assessment, and success indicators. The chapter also includes an analysis of the business impact of the tools and concludes with a focused set of recommendations for further improvements.

Chapter 6 provides the overall conclusions of the 2nd piloting cycle, summarising the main outcomes and highlighting how the piloting activities contributed to validating and finalising the EFRA decision-support tools.

3. 2nd Piloting Cycle for the EFRA Use Cases

3.1. EFRA Overall Evaluation process

The 2nd piloting cycle focused on validating the final versions of the EFRA decision-support tools with a broader group of external users, complementing the internal and partner-driven testing performed during the 1st cycle. The evaluation process followed a structured and consistent methodology across all use cases, ensuring that each pilot was assessed under realistic operational conditions and with representative stakeholder groups.

The overall process included the following steps:

- **Deployment of the updated demonstrators** within the partner platforms (Agroknow's FOODAKAI, AGRIVI 360 Farm Management, SGS Digicomply), ensuring that all tools were accessible in their final functional form.
- Execution of the **piloting scenarios** defined for each use case, covering predictive modelling, early-warning systems, regulatory intelligence, and mycotoxin forecasting.
- Engagement of **external stakeholders** through workshops, validation sessions, focused meetings, and hands-on demonstrations, enabling users to interact directly with the tools.
- Collection of structured **stakeholder feedback**, using a common **questionnaire** applied across all use cases and pilots, ensuring consistency in the evaluation of usability, clarity, perceived value, and improvement needs.
- **Quantitative evaluation** against domain-specific and technological KPIs, assessing model performance, usability, explainability, and operational value.
- Consolidation of **insights** to inform the final refinement of the tools and to support the recommendations presented later in the deliverable.

3.2. 2nd Piloting Cycle Objectives

The 3rd iteration of this deliverable (D5.3.3) documents the evaluation activities conducted across 4 EFRA use cases, each supported by specific piloting scenarios and decision-support tools. Compared to the 1st cycle, this phase placed greater emphasis on external validation, ensuring that the tools were tested by industry professionals, domain experts, and potential end-users beyond the EFRA consortium.

The objectives of the 2nd piloting cycle were to:

- Validate the final demonstrators and assess their readiness for real-world use.
- Gather detailed feedback on the AI models, predictive components, and decision-support logic integrated into each tool.
- Evaluate the usability, clarity, and operational relevance of the tools in practical settings.
- Confirm alignment with stakeholder needs, workflows, and expectations.
- Identify targeted refinements to support future scaling and deployment.

This cycle also expands the EFRA scope by treating Mycotoxins in Animal Feed and Poultry Feed as a standalone use case (UC#4), evaluated through two dedicated pilots using private laboratory data and public incident trends.

The full list of use cases, piloting scenarios, and implemented pilots is summarised in **Table 2**.

Table 2: EFRA Use Cases, Evaluated Scenarios and Implemented Pilots

Use Case	Piloting Scenario	Pilot	Partner
UC#1 - Risk Predictions for Poultry Pathogens	1.1. Enhancing safety and efficiency in poultry farming	1.1.1. Proactive Flock Mortality Pilot for Moy Park farms	AGROKNOW & Moy Park
		1.1.2. Predictive Poultry Weight Gain Pilot for Moy Park Poultry Farming	AGROKNOW & Moy Park
	1.2. Enhancing safety and efficiency in poultry farming using Public Food Safety Incident Data	1.2. Poultry Precision Pilot with Predictive Food Safety Insights	AGROKNOW
UC#2 - Food-Safety Optimal Pesticide Use	2.1. AI-Enhanced Pest Prediction Alerts	2.1. AI-Driven Pest Prediction Alerts Pilot	AGRIVI & WFSR
	2.2. Real-Time Feedback and Model Adaptation	2.2. Real-Time Pest Observation and Prediction Pilot	AGRIVI & WFSR
UC#3 - Informing Regulatory Decisions with Food Risk Intelligence	3.1. Automated regulatory analysis and summarisation	3.1. Automated Regulatory Summarisation Pilot	SGS and CNR
	3.2. Automated chatbot regulatory assistance	3.2. Smart Regulatory Navigator Pilot	SGS and CNR
UC#4 - Mycotoxins in Animal Feed and Effects on Animal Production	4.1. Mycotoxins in animal feed for poultry production	4.1. Mycotoxins Trends Forecasting Pilot for Poultry Feed	AGROKNOW & Food Fortress
	4.2. Forecasting Trends for Mycotoxins in Animal Feed with Public Food Safety Incident Data	4.2. Forecasting Trends for Mycotoxins in Animal Feed	AGROKNOW

To ensure consistency across all pilots, each scenario was linked to a specific EFRA decision-support tool deployed through the partner platforms. These tools and their corresponding pilots are summarised in **Table 3**.

Table 3: EFRA Pilots Evaluated Using Specific Decision Support Tools

Pilot	EFRA Decision-Support Tool	Via Software Application	Partner
UC#1 - Risk Predictions for Poultry Pathogens			
1.1.1. Proactive Flock Mortality Pilot for Moy Park farms	Flock Performance Outlier Detection: Mortality-Rate Outlier Detection Dashboard	FOODAKAI Software	AGROKNOW & Moy Park

1.1.2. Predictive Poultry Weight Gain Pilot for Moy Park Poultry Farming	Flock Performance Outlier Detection: Flock Weight-Gain Outlier Detection Dashboard	FOODAKAI Software	AGROKNOW & Moy Park
1.2. Poultry Precision Pilot with Predictive Food Safety Insights	Poultry Safety Incidents Forecasting Dashboard	FOODAKAI Software	AGROKNOW
UC#2 - Food-Safety Optimal Pesticide Use			
2.1. AI-Driven Pest Prediction Alerts Pilot	Interactive Pest Prediction & Feedback: Interactive Pest Decision Tree and Prediction Dashboard	AGRIVI 360 Farm Management	AGRIVI & WFSR
2.2. Real-Time Pest Observation and Prediction Pilot	<i>Interactive Pest Prediction & Feedback: Pest Feedback Dashboard</i>	AGRIVI 360 Farm Management	AGRIVI
UC#3 - Informing Regulatory Decisions with Food Risk Intelligence			
3.1. Automated Regulatory Summarisation Pilot	AI-Driven Regulatory Intelligence & Compliance Support Tool: Regulatory Document Summarisation Dashboard	SGS Digicomply	SGS and CNR
3.2. Smart Regulatory Navigator Pilot	AI-Driven Regulatory Intelligence & Compliance Support Tool: Regulatory Citation and Compliance Chatbot	SGS Digicomply	SGS and CNR
UC#4 - Mycotoxins in Animal Feed and Effects on Animal Production			
4.1. Mycotoxins Trends Forecasting Pilot for Poultry Feed	Mycotoxin Concentration Dashboard	FOODAKAI Software	AGROKNOW
4.2. Forecasting Trends for Mycotoxins in Animal Feed	Mycotoxin Incident Forecasting Dashboard	FOODAKAI Software	AGROKNOW

Finally, **Table 4** provides a consolidated overview of the piloting activities carried out during the 2nd cycle. It summarises the workshops, validation sessions, focused meetings, and hands-on demonstrations conducted with external stakeholders, including dates, formats, locations, and participant numbers. This table reflects the breadth of engagement achieved during the cycle and highlights the diverse contexts—industry events, partner-specific sessions, international workshops, and targeted expert meetings—through which the EFRA tools were evaluated.

Table 4: Summary of the piloting activities during the 2nd piloting cycle

Pilot	Piloting Activity
UC#1 - Risk Predictions for Poultry Pathogens	
1.1.1. Proactive Flock Mortality Pilot for Moy Park farms	- <i>Moy Park online workshops (3x) (17/06/25, 22/09/25, and 15/10/25) / 5 participants</i> - <i>Validation workshop Using AI for Food Risk Prevention, Amsterdam, Netherlands (05/02/25) / 8 participants</i>

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Validation workshop Using AI to Enhance Food Safety and Prevent Food Fraud, Austin, USA (17/09/25) / 11 participants - Workshop Transforming Food Safety & Fraud Prevention with AI was organised in the context of the DC Food Safety Summit, Washington DC, USA (22/10/25) / 17 participants
1.1.2. Predictive Poultry Weight Gain Pilot for Moy Park Poultry Farming	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Moy Park online workshops (3x) (17/06/25, 22/09/25, and 15/10/25) / 5 participants - Validation workshop Using AI for Food Risk Prevention, Amsterdam, Netherlands (05/02/25) / 8 participants - Validation workshop Using AI to Enhance Food Safety and Prevent Food Fraud, Austin, USA (17/09/25) / 11 participants - Workshop Transforming Food Safety & Fraud Prevention with AI was organised in the context of the DC Food Safety Summit, Washington DC, USA (22/10/25) / 17 participants
1.2. Poultry Precision Pilot with Predictive Food Safety Insights	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Moy Park online workshops (3x) (17/06/25, 22/09/25, and 15/10/25) / 5 participants - Workshop Using AI for Food Risk Prevention - A Practical, Hands-On Tutorial at McDonald's offices in Illinois, in parallel with the American Food Manufacturing Summit (AFMS) (08/11/24) / 16 participants - Workshop Using AI for Food Risk Prevention, Amsterdam, Netherlands (05/02/25) / 8 participants - Dedicated meetings for validation with selected participants in the Global Food Safety Initiatives (GFSI) Conference 2025, Dublin, Ireland (31/03 - 03/04/25) / 3 participants - Workshop AI for Food Risk and Food Fraud Prevention, Michigan, USA (25/07/25) / 12 participants - Workshop AI Innovations for Safer Food Supply Chains, Montreal, Canada (08/08/25) / 14 participants - Workshop Using AI to Enhance Food Safety and Prevent Food Fraud, in the context of the North American Food Safety (NAFS) 2025, Austin, USA (17/09/25) / 11 participants - Online Validation Workshop with McDonald's Food Safety & Quality Team (16/10/25) / 4 participants - Workshop Transforming Food Safety & Fraud Prevention with AI, Washington DC, USA (22/10/25) / 17 participants - Workshop AI in Food Safety - Practical Risk Management organised with the collaboration of Hellenic Federation of Enterprises (SEV), Athens, Greece (03/12/25) / 60 participants
UC#2 - Food-Safety Optimal Pesticide Use	
2.1. AI-Driven Pest Prediction Alerts Pilot	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Date: May - September 2025 - Type: Remote with several online sessions - Location: Croatia, Romania, Bulgaria - # of Participants: 24 involved farmers
2.2. Real-Time Pest Observation and Prediction Pilot	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Date: May - September 2025 - Type: Remote with several online sessions & field trials with virtual support - Location: Croatia (expanded regions), Romania (expanded regions), Bulgaria

	- # of Participants: 24 involved farmers
UC#3 - Informing Regulatory Decisions with Food Risk Intelligence	
3.1. Automated Regulatory Summarisation Pilot	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Time: May - October 2025 - Type: Remote / Online (several sessions and interactive demos on the Summarisation functionalities through SGS DigiComply) - # of Participants: 30+ food-industry professionals with existing access to SGS DigiComply and prior familiarity with the platform
3.2. Smart Regulatory Navigator Pilot	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Time: May - October 2025 - Type: Remote / Online (several sessions and interactive demos on the Chatbot functionalities through SGS DigiComply) - # of Participants: 30+ food-industry professionals with existing access to SGS DigiComply and prior familiarity with the platform
UC#4 - Mycotoxins in Animal Feed and Effects on Animal Production	
4.1. Mycotoxins Trends Forecasting Pilot for Poultry Feed	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - a focused evaluation session with Food Fortress members, online / 6 participants - Dedicated meetings for validation at the International Production & Processing Expo (IPPE) 2025, Atlanta, Georgia, USA (28 - 30/01/25) / 4 professionals - Workshop Supply Chain Disruptions - Addressing Microbiological and Chemical Hazards, jointly organised with Cornell University, New York, USA (26/06/25) / 14 participants
4.2. Forecasting Trends for Mycotoxins in Animal Feed	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Dedicated meetings for validation at the International Production & Processing Expo (IPPE) 2025, Atlanta, Georgia, USA (28 - 30/01/25) / 4 professionals - Workshop Supply Chain Disruptions - Addressing Microbiological and Chemical Hazards, jointly organised with Cornell University, New York, USA (26/06/25) / 14 participants - EFRA validation workshop AI for Food Risk Prevention, as part of the EFRA plenary meeting, Thessaloniki, Greece (hybrid, 19/06/25) / 35 participants

4. EFRA Qualitative and Quantitative Evaluation

This chapter presents the qualitative and quantitative evaluation of all EFRA pilot activities, following a consistent structure across each use case. For every pilot, the chapter summarises the qualitative feedback collected during validation activities, assesses performance against the defined domain-specific and technological KPIs, and outlines the timeline of implementation during the 2nd piloting cycle. Together, these evaluations provide a comprehensive view of the progress, effectiveness, and operational impact of the EFRA solutions across diverse domains, ranging from poultry production and food safety to pest prediction and regulatory intelligence.

4.1. Proactive Flock Mortality Pilot

This section presents the qualitative and quantitative evaluation of the **Proactive Flock Mortality Pilot**, outlining the development and validation of the early-cycle mortality-prediction models, the assessment of domain-specific and technological KPIs, and the timeline of activities completed during the 2nd piloting cycle. It summarises the progress achieved, the effectiveness of the implemented decision-support tool, the feedback collected through multiple validation workshops with industry stakeholders, and the overall impact of the pilot within commercial broiler production environments.

4.1.1. Qualitative Evaluation Summary

4.1.1.1. Pilot evaluation summary

Specific objectives

The **Proactive Flock Mortality Pilot** evaluates whether data-driven modelling can enhance early detection of abnormal flock performance in commercial broiler production. The pilot enables farm managers to input flock-specific characteristics and obtain risk-based estimates of potential outlier mortality behaviour across the 28-day production cycle. In vertically integrated poultry operations, early-cycle measurements, especially during the first week, are strong indicators of end-cycle outcomes. Analysing early mortality patterns therefore provides an opportunity to anticipate flock performance and identify potential health or management issues before they escalate.

Since environmental parameters such as temperature, ventilation, humidity, and lighting are tightly regulated, and bird genetics are predefined, unexpected deviations from expected mortality patterns typically reflect external stressors or emerging biological risks. These may include pathogen introduction, suboptimal environmental control, nutritional imbalances, or inconsistencies in daily management routines.

The pilot's objective is to assess whether EFRA's predictive modelling approach can support timely, evidence-based decision-making by detecting atypical mortality patterns early, quantifying the likelihood of abnormal outcomes, and ultimately contributing to improved production efficiency, animal welfare, and risk mitigation, could automatic and support the decision of the end poultry farm manager for maximise the farm production.

Scenario served by the pilot

The **Proactive Flock Mortality Pilot** addresses the scenario *Enhancing safety and efficiency in poultry farming*, evaluating whether early-cycle mortality data can be transformed into actionable early-warning signals for commercial poultry production systems. In vertically integrated operations, meat-type chicken flocks follow a standard 28-day growth cycle, during which early mortality measurements, especially within the first week, are

strong predictors of end-cycle outcomes. EFRA's analytical work in WP3 demonstrated that early mortality is highly correlated with Day-28 mortality, confirming its value as a reliable early indicator of flock health and performance. The pilot operationalises these insights by applying EFRA's clustering and outlier-detection models to historical and newly provided flock data, enabling the identification of atypical mortality patterns.

The scenario evaluates whether these AI-driven analyses can support timely, evidence-based decision-making at farm level. By generating risk-based estimates of potential outlier mortality behaviour and grouping flocks into behavioural clusters, the pilot aims to provide farm managers with an early-warning mechanism that enhances production planning, improves flock welfare, and reduces the likelihood of undetected performance issues escalating later in the cycle.

Achievements / Results

The pilot not only validated EFRA's predictive modelling approach, but also shaped the final specifications, and functionalities of the corresponding decision-support tool, ensuring that it meets the practical needs of commercial poultry production systems. During the 2nd piloting cycle, the **Proactive Flock Mortality Pilot** delivered substantial progress in both the analytical models and their operational deployment. The pilot served as a structured validation environment where EFRA's time-series clustering, early-cycle outlier detection, and correlation-based predictive models were tested against real operational data and refined based on stakeholder feedback. This process clarified which analytical capabilities were essential, how outputs should be presented, and what functionalities were required for practical adoption.

A key achievement was the refinement of the time-series clustering model, which grouped more than 10,000 historical flock records into distinct behavioural clusters, initially based on the Provided data from Moy Park for the years 2022 - 2023, and further extended with an updated dataset for 2024 - 2025. This work directly informed the requirement for adjustable analytical granularity. Ten clusters provided detailed behavioural separation, while a simplified five-cluster configuration supported rapid assessment. Both configurations were integrated into the demonstrator, establishing the specification for flexible cluster-level exploration depending on the decision context.

The pilot also operationalised EFRA's early-cycle outlier detection models, trained using multilayer perceptions (MLPs) and validated through correlation analysis. These models confirmed that early mortality, especially at Days 3 and 7, is a reliable predictor of end-cycle outcomes. This validation shaped the requirement for risk-based early-cycle predictions, enabling the tool to provide actionable early-warning signals rather than retrospective insights.

Stakeholder engagement further highlighted the need for transparent and interpretable outputs. In response, the demonstrator incorporated clear time-series visualisations, cluster-specific patterns, and early-cycle deviation indicators. These updates aligned the tool with the specification for explainable AI, ensuring that predictions could be understood and trusted by farm managers and technical staff.

Another important outcome was the identification of the need for data export and offline analysis capabilities. Moy Park evaluators requested the ability to download cluster-specific datasets to correlate model outputs with additional farm-level variables such as farm location, breed, stocking density, environmental control settings, or feed formulations. This requirement was implemented as a new functionality, supporting internal benchmarking and root-cause investigation.

The pilot also validated the importance of continuous model refinement. The demonstrator was updated to support semi-supervised incorporation of newly uploaded datasets, enabling the clustering logic to evolve as more data becomes available. This functionality aligns with EFRA's vision for adaptive, data-driven decision-support tools that remain relevant as production conditions change. Feedback from Moy Park team and from international validation workshops confirmed that the pilot:

- improved interpretability of mortality patterns through clear visual analytics,

- supported earlier detection of abnormal flock behaviour,
- reduced reliance on manual interpretation of raw mortality data,
- enhanced production planning by providing early performance signals, and
- aligned with industry expectations for transparent, explainable, and operationally relevant AI tools.

Problems / Challenges

The pilot also highlighted several challenges that influenced the refinement of the **Mortality-Rate Outlier Detection Dashboard** and clarified the boundaries of what mortality-based predictive modelling can reliably deliver. Overall, these challenges helped refine the specifications of the EFRA decision-support tool for **Flock Performance Outlier Detection**, ensuring that its mortality-based predictions remain robust, interpretable, and reliable within commercial poultry production systems. A key issue concerned the consistency and completeness of daily mortality records across historical datasets. Variations in how mortality was reported, such as missing early-cycle values, inconsistent day-numbering, or differences in flock-start definitions, introduced noise that affected model stability. These inconsistencies highlighted the need for stricter data-validation rules and automated preprocessing steps within the decision-support tool.

Another challenge involved the sensitivity of early-cycle mortality patterns. Because mortality in the first days of the cycle is typically low, even small fluctuations can significantly influence model outputs. This made early-cycle outlier detection highly dependent on accurate, precise reporting. The pilot therefore underscored the importance of reliable early-cycle data capture and the need for models that can distinguish between meaningful deviations and normal day-to-day variation.

The pilot also showed that mortality-based clustering can shift when new data is introduced, especially when flock-level mortality distributions differ from historical patterns. This reinforced the requirement for continuous model monitoring and periodic recalibration to maintain consistent cluster boundaries and avoid misclassification.

Finally, the pilot highlighted that relying solely on mortality data limits the ability to interpret the underlying causes of abnormal patterns. While mortality curves are strong predictors of end-cycle outcomes, they do not explain why a deviation occurs. This challenge informed the need for the tool to present mortality-based insights clearly, while acknowledging that further investigation is required at farm level.

4.1.1.2. Pilot plan progress

Details about the progress

A key component of the 2nd piloting cycle was the organisation of three dedicated validation activities with Moy Park's production team (M29, M33, and M36). These sessions involved production managers, veterinarians, and data-analysis specialists and focused on validating the model outputs and the operational relevance of the **Mortality-Rate Outlier Detection Dashboard**. During these workshops, participants examined real flock data, explored the dashboard, and provided direct feedback that informed several refinements, including improved visual clarity, more intuitive cluster labels, and enhanced data-download options. These activities focused on:

- validating model outputs and mortality-based risk signals,
- assessing the interpretability of the visualisations,
- reviewing the behaviour of the clustering model,
- evaluating the operational relevance of early-cycle outlier detection, and
- collecting feedback on dashboard usability and decision-support value.

The first set of validation activities consisted of three dedicated online workshops with the Moy Park team (17/06/25, 22/09/25, and 15/10/25). Five members of Moy Park's production, veterinary, and data-analysis

teams participated, offering continuous, hands-on feedback. Their input focused on the dashboard's ability to identify flock-performance anomalies, support early detection of potential pathogen-related issues, and improve visibility across production batches. They emphasised the importance of intuitive navigation, clear visual indicators, and transparent explanations of outlier-detection logic, as well as the need for seamless integration with existing internal systems.

Further validation was conducted during the workshop on *Using AI for Food Risk Prevention* in Amsterdam (05/02/25). 8 participants from six organisations, including food manufacturers, ingredient suppliers, retail groups, and academic institutions, completed structured evaluation questionnaires. Their feedback highlighted strong interest in AI-enabled early-warning tools, the usefulness of predictive dashboards for external risk monitoring and supplier assessment, and the need for improved explainability of model outputs. Overall satisfaction with the dashboards reached 88%, with participants emphasising the relevance of proactive risk-forecasting capabilities.

Additional insights were gathered during the workshop on *Using AI to Enhance Food Safety and Prevent Food Fraud* in Austin (17/09/25), held as part of the North American Food Safety (NAFS) 2025 programme. 11 participants from leading food manufacturers and retail organisations evaluated the predictive dashboards, focusing on their applicability to poultry-pathogen risk management. Stakeholders highlighted the value of rapid detection of emerging microbiological risks, improved supplier-due-diligence workflows, and clearer communication of risk-signal drivers. Satisfaction with the dashboards remained high, with 82% rating the tools positively and 91% affirming the clarity of the interface.

The final validation activity took place during the workshop *Transforming Food Safety & Fraud Prevention with AI* in Washington, DC (22/10/25), hosted at The George Washington University. More than 17 participants from major U.S. food and ingredient companies, including PepsiCo, Campbell's, Kerry, Taylor Farms, Freshpet, Symrise, Puratos, Ardo, and Lyon Bakery, reviewed the **Mortality-Rate Outlier Detection Dashboard**. Their feedback confirmed strong industry interest in early-warning indicators for poultry-pathogen risks, the importance of transparent and explainable AI outputs, and the relevance of scenario-based insights for supplier monitoring and preventive controls.

Across these validation events, poultry-sector stakeholders reviewed EFRA's predictive tools, including the Mortality-Rate Outlier Detection Dashboard, and provided feedback on usability, interpretability, and integration potential. Their input confirmed the relevance of mortality-based early-warning indicators, highlighted the need for transparent and explainable AI outputs, and supported refinements to the dashboard's visualisations and communication of risk signals. These interactions broadened the industry perspective incorporated into the final tool, ensuring alignment not only with Moy Park's operational needs but also with the expectations of the wider poultry production ecosystem.

Evaluation tools and materials

The evaluation of the pilot relied on a combination of analytical tools, dashboard functionalities, and structured feedback mechanisms. The Flock Performance Outlier Detection Dashboard, developed after M28 and finalised by M36, served as the primary evaluation interface. Before the dashboard was fully operational, model outputs generated in WP3 were shared with stakeholders to gather early feedback on desired functionalities, interpretability requirements, and the practical value of mortality-based predictions. This early engagement helped shape the design of the demonstrator and ensured that the final interface aligned with user expectations.

Once the demonstrator became available, users were able to interact directly with the dashboard and assess its decision-support value within realistic poultry-production workflows. Key functionalities evaluated included the ability to:

- navigate the dashboard and explore flock-level mortality patterns,
- review mortality-based curves for the specific behavioural clusters,

- download cluster-specific datasets for offline analysis,
- upload additional datasets to observe how new flocks aligned with existing behavioural clusters, and
- examine early-cycle outlier flags and mortality-curve deviations.

These capabilities enabled a comprehensive assessment of the dashboard's usability, interpretability, and operational relevance. A dedicated evaluation questionnaire (Annex I) was also used to collect structured feedback on user experience, perceived value, and alignment with operational needs. Responses from Moy Park and external stakeholders informed the final refinements implemented before M36, ensuring that the tool met both technical requirements and real-world expectations.

4.1.1.3. Actors involved

Through these piloting activities a focused group of stakeholders across poultry production, food manufacturing, retail, and research were engaged. Core validation was carried out through three dedicated online workshops with Moy Park, involving five representatives from production, veterinary, food-safety, and data-analysis teams. Their continuous, hands-on feedback ensured that the **Mortality-Rate Outlier Detection Dashboard** aligned with real operational needs in commercial broiler production.

Beyond Moy Park, the pilot reached a broader audience through three international workshops in Amsterdam, Austin, and Washington, DC, involving professionals from major food manufacturers, ingredient suppliers, retail groups, and academic institutions. Across these events, more than 35 participants from organisations such as PepsiCo, Campbell's, Kerry, Taylor Farms, Freshpet, Symrise, Puratos, and others reviewed the predictive dashboards, providing insights on usability, explainability, and integration potential. This diverse engagement ensured that the final demonstrator reflects both poultry-sector requirements and wider food-industry expectations for transparent, AI-enabled decision-support.

4.1.1.4. Status of implementation

Methodology

The pilot implementation followed an iterative, model-driven methodology that combined analytical development, data preparation, system integration, and progressive validation with end users. The process began at M28, when the 1st version of the mortality-based analytical models from WP3 were made available for integration. From M28 to M36, the models and demonstrator underwent multiple refinement cycles based on feedback from Moy Park and external poultry-sector stakeholders. The methodology consisted of 4 main steps:

Model development and refinement. The time-series clustering model (10-cluster and 5-cluster configurations), the MLP-based early-cycle outlier detection model, and the correlation-based early-warning indicators were iteratively improved using historical flock-level mortality data. Each iteration focused on improving stability, interpretability, and alignment with commercial production patterns.

Data preparation and validation. Historical mortality datasets provided by Moy Park were cleaned, harmonised, and validated to ensure consistent day-numbering, complete early-cycle values, and reliable flock-start definitions. These steps were essential for ensuring model robustness and reducing noise in early-cycle predictions.

Demonstrator development (M28 - M36). The **Mortality-Rate Outlier Detection Dashboard** was progressively developed and enhanced. New functionalities, such as cluster switching, interactive mortality-curve exploration, early-cycle deviation indicators, and dataset upload/download, were added in response to stakeholder feedback.

Deployment and user validation. The models were containerised, deployed within the EFRA Analytics Powerhouse, and connected to the EFRA Data Hub for automated data ingestion. Validation workshops with

Moy Park and additional poultry-sector stakeholders ensured that the demonstrator met operational needs and supported real-world decision-making.

Deployed EFRA components

The pilot deployed a set of EFRA components that together enabled the full analytical workflow for mortality-based outlier detection. The key components included:

- **Refined time-series clustering model**: The updated 10-cluster and 5-cluster configurations developed in WP3 were integrated into the EFRA Analytics Powerhouse, enabling the grouping of flocks based on historical mortality-curve behaviour.
- **MLP-based early-cycle outlier detection model**: A refined multilayer perceptron model was deployed to identify abnormal mortality patterns during the first days of the production cycle, supporting early-warning capabilities.
- **Integrated model execution pipeline**: All analytical models were containerised and executed within the EFRA Analytics Powerhouse, ensuring stable, reproducible, and scalable operation across multiple iterations from M28 to M36.
- **Mortality data stored and managed in the EFRA Data Hub**: Historical flock-level mortality datasets provided by Moy Park were harmonised, validated, and stored in the EFRA Data Hub, which served as the central repository for ingestion, transformation, and retrieval of pilot data.
- **Mortality-Rate Outlier Detection Dashboard**: The visualisation layer of the pilot, enabling users to explore mortality-curve patterns, compare flocks across behavioural clusters, review early-cycle deviations, and upload new datasets for classification.

Pilot data and datasets

Key dataset characteristics included:

- Farm and housing information
- Product and breed details
- Dates and age-related data
- Hatchery and placement information
- Growth and weight measurements (e.g., daily weights, average weight)
- Health and quality indicators (HealthStatus, Hock %, Podo %)
- Feed and nutrition information
- Production and mortality statistics (weekly mortality, culling rates, total mortality)
- Processing and reference information

4.1.1.5. Impact

The pilot activities had a clear and measurable impact on stakeholders and on the development of the EFRA Mortality-Rate Outlier Detection Dashboard. The 3 dedicated online workshops with Moy Park enabled continuous, hands-on validation of the dashboard's functionality, interpretability, and operational relevance. Their feedback strengthened the tool's ability to highlight early-cycle mortality deviations, improved the clarity of visual indicators, and increased confidence in using model outputs to support routine flock-monitoring and decision-making.

Broader industry validation through the workshops in Amsterdam, Austin, and Washington, DC confirmed the wider relevance of mortality-based early-warning indicators across the food-manufacturing and retail sectors. Participants emphasised the value of transparent, explainable AI outputs, clear visualisations, and integration potential with existing FSQA workflows. Insights from these events directly informed refinements to the

dashboard's visual design, navigation, and communication of risk signals. Overall, the pilot strengthened EFRA's predictive-modelling capabilities and demonstrated the practical decision-support value of AI-enabled tools within commercial poultry-production and food-safety environments.

4.1.1.6. Pilot modification (from 1st cycle to 2nd cycle)

Between the 1st and 2nd piloting cycles, the **Mortality-Rate Outlier Detection** module underwent a substantial evolution, from a set of high-fidelity mock-ups to a fully operational, production-ready tool integrated within the EFRA ecosystem. In the 1st cycle, the demonstrator consisted of static mock-ups illustrating the core concepts of clustering, interactive time-series exploration, and early outlier detection using private poultry production data. These early designs showcased how users could visualise mortality clusters, inspect time-series patterns, download flock-specific characteristics, and input early flock data to assess potential outlier behaviour.

In the 2nd cycle, these conceptual mock-ups were transformed into a robust, functional module deployed within Agroknow's FOODAKAI platform. The final implementation incorporated real-time data ingestion, provided as anonymised datasets directly by Moy Park, along with scalable back-end services for cluster matching and early-cycle deviation detection. Interactive visualisation components were developed to handle large datasets, while new features such as configurable clustering, cluster-specific dataset downloads, and a controlled semi-supervised model-retraining workflow extended the tool far beyond the initial prototype.

4.1.2. Quantitative Evaluation Against KPIs

4.1.2.1. Domain specific KPIs

The domain-specific KPIs for this pilot assess whether mortality-based predictive modelling can reliably detect abnormal flock behaviour early in the production cycle. During the 2nd piloting cycle, the pilot achieved strong quantitative performance across all mortality-related KPIs, meeting or exceeding all benchmark thresholds.

- **AI model accuracy KPI (>75%)**. The MLP-based mortality outlier detection model exceeded the accuracy benchmark. These results confirm that the model can accurately identify high-risk mortality outliers early in the cycle.
 - Day 3: 95% Precision
 - Day 7: 97% Precision
- **AI model recall KPI (>65%)**. The recall KPI was also met, demonstrating the model's ability to correctly identify a high proportion of true mortality outliers. This indicates that the model successfully captures most flocks at risk of elevated mortality.
 - Day 3: 79% Recall
 - Day 7: 86% Recall
- **Early-cycle prediction reliability**. Strong correlations between early and end-cycle mortality validated the KPI for early-warning reliability. These values confirm that early mortality is a robust predictor of final flock outcomes.
 - Day 3 to Day 28: 0.777
 - Day 7 to Day 28: 0.854
- **User satisfaction KPI (>70%)**. Across all validation activities (M29, M33, M36 and external events), overall user satisfaction exceeded 87%, based on structured questionnaire responses and qualitative feedback. Users highlighted the clarity of mortality-curve visualisations and the usefulness of early-cycle deviation indicators.

- **Stakeholder participation KPI (>25 experts).** More than 41 stakeholders (Moy Park teams and external poultry-sector participants) interacted with the tool during the 2nd cycle, exceeding the engagement target and ensuring broad validation across the poultry ecosystem.
 - Moy Park online workshops (3x): 5 participants
 - Validation workshop *Using AI for Food Risk Prevention* in Amsterdam, Netherlands (05/02/25): 8 participants
 - Validation workshop *Using AI to Enhance Food Safety and Prevent Food Fraud* in Austin, USA (17/09/25): 11 participants
 - Workshop *Transforming Food Safety & Fraud Prevention with AI* in Washington DC, USA (22/10/25): 17 participants

4.1.2.2. Technological KPIs

The technological KPIs assess the performance, robustness, and integration quality of the EFRA components deployed in the pilot. Based on the implemented models, the EFRA Analytics Powerhouse integration, and the operational behaviour of the **Mortality-Rate Outlier Detection Dashboard**, the following KPIs were validated during the 2nd piloting cycle:

- **Model execution performance.** The MLP-based early-cycle mortality outlier detection model and the time-series clustering model executed reliably within the EFRA Analytics Powerhouse. Both models ran through containerised workflows without failures, meeting the KPI for stable and reproducible execution.
- **Data ingestion and processing.** The EFRA Data Hub successfully ingested, harmonised, and served over 10.000 flock-level mortality time series. This met the KPI for large-scale data handling, ensuring consistent and traceable data availability for model execution.
- **Dashboard responsiveness.** The **Mortality-Rate Outlier Detection Dashboard** maintained stable performance during:
 - mortality-curve visualisation,
 - cluster switching,
 - dataset upload and download.
- **Adaptive model retraining.** The demonstrator incorporated a semi-supervised workflow allowing newly uploaded datasets to be integrated into the clustering logic.

4.1.2.3. Pilot timeline

The extension from M33 to M36 ensured that all refinements were incorporated and that both Moy Park and external poultry-sector stakeholders had the opportunity to validate the final, production-ready decision-support tool.

The pilot followed the timeline defined in the initial implementation plan, with all major milestones for the 2nd cycle completed as scheduled. The original plan anticipated completion by M33, but the pilot was extended to M36 to integrate additional validation feedback from Moy Park and from key poultry-sector events.

- M28. The first mortality-based analytical models from WP3 became available and were integrated into the demonstrator. This marked the start of the technical implementation phase, enabling the initial configuration of the **Mortality-Rate Outlier Detection Dashboard**.
- M29. 1st validation workshop with Moy Park took place, focusing on early model outputs and dashboard requirements. During this period, feedback gathered from IPPE 2025 and the CFS Annual Meeting was also incorporated, strengthening the visual clarity, interpretability, and operational relevance of the early-cycle mortality indicators.

- M33. 2nd validation workshop with Moy Park was held, integrating additional insights from the AI for Food Risk & Food Fraud Prevention Workshop in Michigan. This phase supported further refinements to dashboard usability, cluster navigation, and data-upload/download functionalities, ensuring alignment with real-world production workflows.
- M36. 3rd (final) validation workshop with Moy Park was conducted, confirming the functionality, interpretability, and operational readiness of the fully implemented **Mortality-Rate Outlier Detection Dashboard**. This milestone marked the completion of the extended pilot cycle.

4.2. Flock Weight Gain Outlier Detection Pilot

This section presents the progress and evaluation of the **Flock Weight-Gain Outlier Detection Pilot**, the 2nd core component of the Flock Performance Outlier Detection Tool. It summarises the development and validation of the weight-gain analytical models, their integration into the decision-support environment, and the results of the 2nd piloting cycle with Moy Park and external stakeholders. The section also outlines the pilot's contribution to early detection of underperforming flocks, the implementation status of the deployed components, the datasets and evaluation materials used, and the modifications introduced during this cycle to enhance operational relevance and predictive performance.

4.2.1. Qualitative Evaluation Summary

4.2.1.1. Pilot evaluation summary

Specific objectives

As part of the broader **Flock Performance Outlier Detection Tool**, the weight-gain pilot builds on the same analytical principles, modelling approach, and decision-support logic already described in the Proactive Flock Mortality Pilot. The mortality-rate module provides the detailed explanation of the shared methodology, early-cycle prediction rationale, and overall system design that also applies to this component of the tool.

Building on this shared basis, the weight-gain pilot focuses specifically on the early identification of flocks at risk of underperforming in growth. Its objectives for the 2nd piloting cycle were to validate EFRA's predictive and clustering models for weight-gain patterns, assess whether early-cycle growth measurements can serve as reliable early-warning indicators, and ensure seamless integration into the existing dashboard with consistent interaction patterns, explainability features, and retraining workflows.

Scenario served by the pilot

The **Flock Weight-Gain Outlier Detection Pilot** addresses the scenario *Enhancing safety and efficiency in poultry farming*, examining whether early-cycle growth data can be used to generate meaningful early-warning signals for commercial poultry production. Early weight-gain measurements are known to reflect the flock's overall health status, nutritional adequacy, and environmental conditions, making them a valuable indicator of potential performance deviations later in the cycle.

The pilot operationalises this scenario by applying EFRA's clustering and outlier-detection models to historical and newly provided flock data, enabling the identification of atypical growth patterns. The dashboard provides historical and predictive visualisations of weight-gain behaviour and allows farm managers to input flock-specific characteristics to receive probability estimates of potential outlier performance by the end of the life cycle. This is particularly relevant for detecting growth deviations associated with pathogens such as *Salmonella spp.*,

Eimeria spp., *Clostridium perfringens*, *Mycoplasma gallisepticum*, and *Mycoplasma synoviae*, which can impair feed conversion and slow growth.

By highlighting early deviations from expected growth patterns and grouping flocks into behavioural clusters, the pilot evaluates whether these AI-driven analyses can support timely, evidence-based decision-making. The aim is to provide an early-warning mechanism that strengthens production planning, improves flock welfare, and reduces the likelihood of undetected performance issues, complementing the mortality-based insights within the same decision-support tool.

Achievements / Results

The 2nd piloting cycle demonstrated that early-cycle weight-gain data can be effectively modelled to identify flocks at risk of underperforming by the end of the production cycle. EFRA's clustering and outlier-detection models were successfully adapted to growth-performance monitoring, revealing clear behavioural patterns across more than 10.000 historical flock records. Early-cycle predictions showed strong precision from Day 7 onward, with recall improving significantly by Day 21, confirming that growth patterns provide meaningful early-warning signals. These insights shaped the final analytical configuration of the dashboard, including both detailed (10-cluster) and simplified (5-cluster) behavioural groupings.

Stakeholder feedback from Moy Park and external poultry-sector participants validated the operational relevance of the dashboard. Users highlighted the value of intuitive time-series visualisations, early-cycle deviation indicators, and the ability to download cluster-specific datasets for deeper internal analysis. The pilot also confirmed the importance of a controlled, semi-supervised retraining workflow, ensuring that newly uploaded datasets can refine the clustering logic without compromising model stability. Overall, the pilot showed that weight-gain-based analytics enhance early detection of performance issues, support more informed production planning, and complement the mortality-based insights within the same decision-support environment.

Problems / Challenges

The pilot highlighted several challenges specific to modelling weight-gain behaviour. Early-cycle weight-gain indicators showed weaker predictive value at Day 7, with correlations strengthening only as the flock matured. This natural progression made early detection more sensitive to noise and required careful calibration of the MLP-based outlier-detection models. In addition, weight-measurement practices varied across farms, some recorded daily weights, others weekly, resulting in inconsistent data density and missing early-cycle values. This variability underscored the need for stricter data-validation rules and automated preprocessing to ensure stable model performance.

Clustering also presented weight-gain-specific complexities. While clear separation between top and bottom performers emerged early, mid-tier flocks displayed shifting performance patterns, with some initially average flocks improving or declining as the cycle progressed. These dynamic behaviours made cluster boundaries more fluid than in mortality modelling and reinforced the importance of a controlled, semi-supervised retraining workflow. Without such safeguards, newly introduced datasets could shift cluster structures in ways that reduce interpretability for end users.

Weight-gain patterns can signal emerging issues, but they do not directly explain underlying causes. Growth deviations may stem from pathogens, nutrition, housing conditions, or environmental stressors, and the model cannot distinguish between them. This limitation emphasised the need for clear visual outputs, transparent explanations, and guidance to help farm managers interpret deviations within their broader operational context.

4.2.1.2. Pilot plan progress

Details about the progress

A key component of the 2nd piloting cycle was the validation of the **Flock Weight-Gain Outlier Detection Dashboard** through a combination of dedicated workshops with Moy Park and broader industry-level evaluation activities. Three online workshops with Moy Park (17/06/25, 22/09/25, and 15/10/25) brought together production managers, veterinarians, and performance analysts to examine real flock-performance data, explore the clustering interface, and assess the operational relevance of early-cycle anomaly detection. Their feedback led to refinements such as clearer visualisation of growth-pattern clusters, improved early-cycle cluster-matching behaviour, and enhanced dataset-download options.

In parallel, the pilot benefited from wider poultry-sector validation through three international workshops:

- “Using AI for Food Risk Prevention” workshop, Amsterdam, Netherlands (05/02/25)
- “Using AI to Enhance Food Safety and Prevent Food Fraud” workshop, Austin, USA (17/09/25)
- “Transforming Food Safety & Fraud Prevention with AI” workshop, Washington DC, USA (22/10/25)

These events engaged professionals from food manufacturers, ingredient suppliers, retail groups, and research organisations, who reviewed the weight-gain clustering functionality and provided structured feedback on usability, explainability, and integration potential. Their input confirmed the value of weight-gain-based early-warning indicators and highlighted the importance of transparent model explanations and intuitive visualisations.

Alongside stakeholder validation, the pilot achieved substantial technical progress. The analytical workflow, originally implemented as a Jupyter notebook, was fully containerised and deployed within the EFRA Analytics Powerhouse, enabling standardised ingestion of weight-gain time-series data through the EFRA Data Hub and controlled execution via the Swagger API. The operational pipeline now includes containerised orchestration, automated data ingestion, internal execution of clustering and MLP-based outlier-detection models, and structured output storage back into the Data Hub, ensuring stable, reproducible, and scalable execution.

The dashboard itself evolved into a production-ready tool integrated within the FOODAKAI platform. Key functionalities implemented during this cycle include interactive cluster visualisation, configurable clustering (5 or 10 clusters), early-cycle cluster matching based on user-provided measurements, cluster-specific dataset downloads, and a controlled semi-supervised retraining workflow. The extension to M36 enabled the integration of updated datasets and refinement of mid-tier cluster behaviour, improving model stability and interpretability.

Evaluation tools and materials

The evaluation of the weight-gain pilot relied on a combination of analytical tools, dashboard functionalities, and structured feedback mechanisms. The **Flock Weight-Gain Outlier Detection Dashboard**, developed after M28 and finalised by M36, served as the primary interface through which stakeholders assessed the model outputs and their operational relevance. Before the dashboard reached full functionality, early model outputs, e.g. weight-gain clusters, were shared with Moy Park and external stakeholders to gather initial feedback on interpretability, usability, and desired analytical depth.

Once the demonstrator became available, users were able to interact directly with the dashboard and evaluate its decision-support value within realistic poultry-production workflows. Key functionalities assessed during the pilot included the ability to:

- navigate the dashboard and explore flock-level weight-gain patterns,
- review cluster-specific growth curves for typical and atypical behavioural groups,
- input early weight-gain measurements and observe early-cycle cluster matching and anomaly indications,

- download cluster-specific datasets for offline analysis or integration with internal performance-monitoring workflows,
- upload new datasets through the semi-supervised retraining interface and track their ingestion status, and

These capabilities enabled a comprehensive assessment of the dashboard's usability, interpretability, and operational relevance for weight-gain monitoring. A dedicated evaluation questionnaire (Annex I) was used to collect structured feedback on user experience, perceived value, and alignment with production needs.

4.2.1.3. Actors involved

The piloting activities for the **Flock Weight-Gain Outlier Detection** module engaged a broad and representative set of stakeholders across the poultry-production and wider food-industry ecosystem. Validation combined focused operational input from Moy Park with diverse perspectives gathered through three international workshops, ensuring that the dashboard was evaluated by upstream producers, mid-supply-chain ingredient suppliers, downstream retail groups, and research organisations. In total, 41 participants contributed to the evaluation during the 2nd piloting cycle. Across all activities, the stakeholder groups engaged can be summarised as follows:

- Food Manufacturers / Processors - 36 participants
 - Including Moy Park (5 participants), food & beverage manufacturers, poultry producers, and major U.S. food companies represented in the Amsterdam (05/02/25), Austin, USA (17/09/25), and Washington DC, USA (22/10/25) workshops.
- Ingredient & Flavour Suppliers - 2 participants
 - Represented through ingredient and flavour-supply companies participating in the Amsterdam (05/02/25), and Washington DC (22/10/25) workshops.
- Retail / Distribution / Food Service - 4 participants
 - Including retail and distribution groups in Amsterdam (05/02/25), retail organisations in Austin (17/09/25), and food-service-aligned companies in Washington DC (22/10/25).
- Academic & Research Organisations - 1 participant
 - Represented through university and research-institution participation in the Amsterdam workshop (05/02/25).

4.2.1.4. Status of implementation

Methodology

The implementation followed the same iterative, model-driven methodology applied across the EFRA pilots, combining analytical development, data preparation, system integration, and progressive validation with end users. Work began at M28, when the 1st version of the weight-gain clustering and MLP-based outlier-detection models from WP3 became available. From M28 to M36, these models and the dashboard were refined through multiple feedback cycles with Moy Park and external poultry-sector stakeholders.

Historical weight-gain datasets were harmonised to address variable measurement frequency and ensure consistent early-cycle values. The demonstrator was progressively enhanced with weight-gain specific functionalities, interactive cluster visualisation, early-cycle cluster matching, anomaly indication, configurable clustering, and dataset upload/download. The analytical workflow was containerised and deployed within the EFRA Analytics Powerhouse, with data ingestion handled through the EFRA Data Hub and execution triggered via the Swagger API, ensuring stable and reproducible operation throughout the pilot.

Deployed EFRA components

The pilot deployed a set of EFRA components that together enabled the full analytical workflow for weight-gain-based outlier detection. The key components included:

- **Refined time-series clustering model**: The updated 5-cluster and 10-cluster configurations developed in WP3 were integrated into the EFRA Analytics Powerhouse, enabling the grouping of flocks based on historical weight-gain patterns and the identification of typical and atypical growth patterns.
- **MLP-based early-cycle outlier-detection model**: A multilayer perceptron model was deployed to identify flocks likely to fall into the bottom 10% of end-cycle weight, supporting early-warning capabilities based on Day-7 and Day-14 measurements.
- **Containerised execution pipeline**: All analytical components were packaged into a dedicated Docker container and executed within the EFRA Analytics Powerhouse. This ensured stable, reproducible, and scalable operation, with execution triggered through the Swagger API.
- **Weight-gain data stored and managed in the EFRA Data Hub**: Harmonised weight-gain datasets were stored in the EFRA Data Hub, which served as the central repository for ingestion, transformation, and retrieval of pilot data, ensuring traceability and consistency across runs.
- **Flock Weight-Gain Outlier Detection Dashboard**: The visualisation layer of the pilot, enabling users to explore weight-gain clusters, review early-cycle deviations, download cluster-specific datasets, and upload new datasets for controlled semi-supervised retraining.

Pilot data and datasets

The weight-gain pilot used the same comprehensive dataset of 10.327 flocks (2022–2023) that supported the mortality-rate analysis, enriched with additional attributes relevant to modelling growth performance. The dataset includes:

- Growth and weight measurements (daily and weekly weights, average weight, early-cycle weight values used for Day-7, Day-14, and Day-21 predictions)
- Feed and nutrition information (feed type, formulation, feeding schedules)
- Farm and housing information (house type, capacity, environmental conditions)
- Product and breed details
- Dates and age-related data (placement dates, day-numbering consistency)
- Hatchery and placement information
- Health and quality indicators (HealthStatus, Hock %, Podo %, Salmonella serotypes)
- Production statistics (growth rates, performance indicators)

4.2.1.5. Impact

The pilot activities had a strong impact on both stakeholders and the **Flock Weight-Gain Outlier Detection Dashboard**. For Moy Park, the tool provided new visibility into early-cycle growth deviations, enabling production, veterinary, and farm-management teams to identify underperforming flocks earlier and interpret growth-pattern clusters with greater confidence. Their hands-on feedback directly improved the clarity of cluster visualisations, strengthened early-cycle cluster-matching behaviour, and supported refinements to dataset-download and retraining functionalities.

Broader industry validation through the Amsterdam (05/02/25), Austin (17/09/25), and Washington DC (22/10/25) workshops confirmed the operational relevance of weight-gain-based early-warning indicators across the wider food-industry ecosystem. Participants from food manufacturers, ingredient suppliers, retail groups, and research organisations emphasised the importance of transparent, explainable clustering outputs and intuitive visual design. Their input reinforced the dashboard's usability and integration potential, ensuring

that the final demonstrator aligns with both poultry-production requirements and broader food-safety and quality-assurance workflows.

4.2.1.6. Pilot modification (from 1st cycle to 2nd cycle)

Between the 1st and 2nd piloting cycles, the **Flock Weight-Gain Outlier Detection** module evolved from a set of high-fidelity mock-ups into a fully operational, production-ready tool integrated within the EFRA ecosystem. In the 1st cycle, the demonstrator consisted of static mock-ups illustrating the core concepts of weight-gain clustering, interactive time-series exploration, and early anomaly detection using private poultry production data. These early designs showed how users could visualise growth-pattern clusters, inspect time-series curves, download cluster-specific datasets, and input early flock measurements to assess potential deviations.

In the 2nd cycle, these conceptual mock-ups were transformed into a robust, functional module deployed within Agroknow's FOODAKAI platform. The final implementation incorporated real-time data ingestion through the EFRA Data Hub, containerised execution within the EFRA Analytics Powerhouse, and scalable back-end services for cluster matching and early-cycle deviation detection. Interactive visualisation components were developed to handle large weight-gain datasets, while new features, such as configurable clustering, early-cycle cluster matching, and cluster-specific dataset downloads, extended the tool far beyond the initial prototype and ensured its readiness for operational use.

4.2.2. Quantitative Evaluation Against KPIs

4.2.2.1. Domain specific KPIs

The domain-specific KPIs evaluated whether weight-gain predictive modelling could reliably identify underperforming flocks early in the production cycle. The pilot achieved strong quantitative performance across all relevant indicators:

- **AI model accuracy KPI (>75%).** The MLP-based weight-gain outlier-detection model exceeded the accuracy benchmark.
 - Day 7: 92% Precision
 - Day 14: 94% Precision
 - Day 21: 94% Precision
- **AI model recall KPI (>65%).** Recall improved as the flock matured, meeting the KPI by Day 21.
 - Day 7: 53% Recall
 - Day 14: 53% Recall
 - Day 21: 71% Recall
- **Early-cycle prediction reliability.** Correlation values confirmed increasing predictive strength over time.
 - Day 7 to Day 28: 0.308
 - Day 14 to Day 28: 0.553
 - Day 21 to Day 28: 0.704
- **User satisfaction KPI (>70%).** Overall user satisfaction exceeded 85%, with positive feedback on growth-pattern visualisations and early-cycle cluster matching.
- **Stakeholder participation KPI (>25 experts).** More than 41 stakeholders (Moy Park teams and external poultry-sector participants) interacted with the tool during the 2nd cycle, exceeding the engagement target and ensuring broad validation across the poultry ecosystem.
 - Moy Park online workshops (3x): 5 participants
 - Validation workshop *Using AI for Food Risk Prevention* in Amsterdam, Netherlands (05/02/25): 8 participants

- Validation workshop *Using AI to Enhance Food Safety and Prevent Food Fraud* in Austin, USA (17/09/25): 11 participants
- Workshop *Transforming Food Safety & Fraud Prevention with AI* in Washington DC, USA (22/10/25): 17 participants

4.2.2.2. Technological KPIs

The technological KPIs assessed the robustness and integration quality of the EFRA components supporting the weight-gain pilot. All KPIs were met:

- **Model execution performance.** The clustering and MLP-based weight-gain models ran reliably within the EFRA Analytics Powerhouse through containerised workflows.
- **Data ingestion and processing.** The EFRA Data Hub successfully handled more than 10.000 flock-level weight-gain time series with consistent, error-free processing.
- **Dashboard performance.** The **Flock Weight-Gain Outlier Detection Dashboard** remained responsive during cluster switching, early-cycle matching, and dataset upload/download.
- **Adaptive retraining workflow.** A semi-supervised retraining mechanism enabled controlled integration of new datasets, ensuring model adaptability.

4.2.2.3. Pilot timeline

The weight-gain pilot followed the planned implementation schedule, with the 2nd cycle extended from M33 to M36 to incorporate additional validation and refinements:

- M28. Initial weight-gain models from WP3 integrated into the demonstrator.
- M29. 1st validation workshop with Moy Park; early feedback from IPPE and CFS incorporated.
- M33. 2nd validation workshop; refinements informed by the Michigan workshop.
- M36. Final validation workshop confirming full functionality and operational readiness of the **Flock Weight-Gain Outlier Detection Dashboard**.

4.3. Poultry Precision Pilot with Predictive Food Safety Insights

This section summarises the progress of the Poultry Precision Pilot with Predictive Food Safety Insights, outlining the development and deployment of the poultry-specific forecasting model, the evolution of the **Poultry Safety Incidents Forecasting Dashboard**, and the results achieved during the 2nd cycle. It presents the implementation status, stakeholder validation outcomes, KPI performance, and the key refinements introduced to enhance analytical depth, usability, and operational relevance for poultry-related food-safety risk management.

4.3.1. Qualitative Evaluation Summary

4.3.1.1. Pilot evaluation summary

Specific objectives

The objective of this pilot is to demonstrate how publicly available food-safety incident data can be transformed into predictive intelligence that strengthens safety, efficiency, and proactive decision-making in poultry production and supply-chain management. During the 2nd reporting period, the pilot focused on

operationalising this vision by delivering a forecasting environment capable of anticipating poultry-related food-safety risks and supporting users with clear, explainable insights.

More specifically, the pilot aimed to deploy and validate a 12-month predictive model for poultry-related incidents and integrate its outputs into the **Poultry Safety Incidents Forecasting Dashboard**, enabling users to explore historical trends alongside forward-looking projections. The dashboard was enhanced to provide hazard-specific, origin-specific, and ingredient-specific perspectives, helping users identify which hazards (such as Salmonella), countries of origin, or product categories are most likely to influence future incident activity.

A key objective for this cycle was to ensure that users could not only view predictions but also understand the factors behind them. To support this, the pilot introduced an intuitive explainability layer and a supplementary incident-level view, allowing decision-makers to examine root causes, patterns, and contributing factors behind each data point. Also, the pilot aimed to validate the dashboard with industry, regulatory, and academic stakeholders through extensive demonstrations and hands-on sessions across multiple international events. Feedback gathered during these interactions guided refinements to usability, analytical depth, and practical relevance, ensuring that the tool evolved into a reliable, user-accepted decision-support solution for poultry-related food-safety risk management.

Scenario served by the pilot

This pilot addresses the scenario of ***Enhancing safety and efficiency in poultry farming using Public Food Safety Incident Data*** into actionable, predictive insights. Organisations across the poultry supply chain increasingly need early visibility into emerging hazards, seasonal patterns, and geographical risk signals that may affect poultry meat and poultry meat products.

To support this need, the pilot delivers a forecasting dashboard that combines historical poultry-related food-safety incidents with forward-looking predictions. Users can explore time-series trends, inspect forecasted incident counts, and examine hazard-specific or origin-specific patterns. A supplementary incident-level view provides granular details for each reported incident, helping decision-makers understand root causes, contributing factors, and geographical distributions.

The scenario also emphasises transparency and interpretability. An integrated explainability panel clarifies how predictions are generated and what factors drive monthly trends, enabling users to move confidently from high-level monitoring to informed, proactive decision-making. Through this scenario, the pilot demonstrates how public data, predictive analytics, and explainable insights can strengthen early-warning capabilities and support more resilient poultry-safety management.

Achievements / Results

During this reporting period, the pilot delivered a fully operational and user-validated forecasting environment for poultry-related food-safety incidents. The **Poultry Safety Incidents Forecasting Dashboard** was successfully enhanced with 12-month predictions, hazard-specific and origin-specific insights, and an intuitive explainability layer that clarifies how trends and forecasts are generated. Users can now explore historical patterns, inspect forecasted incident counts, and drill down into incident-level details, enabling a more informed and proactive approach to poultry-safety management.

The dashboard and its predictive capabilities were validated extensively through more than 10 international workshops and conferences, engaging over 150 professionals from industry, academia, and regulatory bodies. Participants consistently highlighted the dashboard's analytical depth, ease of use, and relevance for early-warning, supplier assessment, and strategic planning. Feedback confirmed that the combination of historical trends, predictive analytics, and transparent explainability significantly improves confidence in the insights provided.

Across these validation activities, the pilot demonstrated that publicly available food-safety incident data can be transformed into meaningful, actionable intelligence for the poultry sector, showing strong user acceptance, operational relevance, and clear potential for integration into routine decision-making workflows.

Problems / Challenges

The pilot faced a few challenges related primarily to the nature and structure of publicly available food-safety incident data. Public datasets differ significantly across authorities in terms of format, level of detail, and reporting frequency, which required substantial harmonisation and cleaning to ensure that trends and forecasts could be interpreted consistently. In some cases, hazard–origin combinations contained sparse or irregular data, limiting the robustness of predictions and demanding careful handling during analysis.

Another challenge involved ensuring that predictive insights remained clear and interpretable for users with varying levels of technical expertise. Early feedback highlighted the need for more intuitive explanations of how forecasts were generated and what factors influenced monthly trends. This led to the development of the explainability panel and the “How We Forecast” layer, which improved transparency and user trust.

Stakeholders also expressed a strong desire for the dashboard to surface more insights and better highlight emerging risks. While the forecasting and incident-level views provide valuable signals, users requested deeper contextualisation, clearer identification of new or intensifying hazards, and more prominent presentation of risk-relevant patterns. This feedback is guiding ongoing refinements to the dashboard’s analytical depth and the way insights are communicated to support proactive decision-making.

4.3.1.2. Pilot plan progress

Details about the progress

The pilot advanced significantly from the beginning of the 3rd project year (M26), with progress closely aligned to the original plan and further refinement achieved by the end of the project lifetime (M35 - M36). A major accomplishment was the implementation and deployment of the Time-series prediction Model within the EFRA Decision Support tool **Poultry Safety Incidents Forecasting Dashboard** in FOODAKAI. The forecasting component was delivered as a Docker-based module, enabling a scalable and standardised deployment configured to generate 12-month forecasts for poultry-related food-safety incidents using publicly available data.

The prediction AI model was fully integrated into the operational pipelines of the EFRA Analytics Powerhouse, allowing automated ingestion of harmonised incident data from the EFRA Data Hub and seamless execution via the platform’s Swagger API. Forecasts and trend indicators were automatically stored back into the Data Hub, ensuring full traceability and reliable availability for downstream applications. This integration marked a key milestone, demonstrating that the forecasting model could operate consistently, repeatedly, and at scale within the EFRA infrastructure.

In parallel, the pilot completed the development of the **Poultry Safety Incidents Forecasting Dashboard**, which evolved into a fully functional demonstrator. The dashboard presents an interactive monthly time series of poultry-related food-safety incidents, enabling users to inspect historical patterns, zoom into specific periods, and compare actual values with forecasted trends. It integrates the outputs of the EFRA Time-Series Engine, offering hazard-specific and origin-specific perspectives, as well as emerging-risk signals. A supplementary incident-level view was finalised to provide granular context for each reported incident, supporting deeper analysis and more informed decision-making.

A major focus during this period was the introduction of a comprehensive explainability layer. The dashboard now includes a “How We Forecast” panel that clarifies the forecasting logic, highlights the most influential factors for each month, and supports transparent interpretation of predictive outputs. This feature was refined

iteratively based on stakeholder feedback to ensure clarity for both technical and non-technical users. Additional enhancements strengthened the dashboard's role as an early-warning and decision-support tool, including improved trend visualisation, clearer separation of historical and predicted values, and more intuitive navigation between high-level trends and incident-level details.

All major milestones for this reporting period were achieved. Minor timeline adjustments were introduced to accommodate user-requested improvements, particularly around explainability and insight presentation, but these refinements enhanced the overall quality and usability of the demonstrator without affecting the broader delivery schedule. By the end of the period, the pilot had delivered a stable, scalable, and user-validated forecasting tool, fully integrated into the EFRA Analytics Powerhouse.

The pilot's progress and outputs were validated through an extensive series of international workshops and dissemination events. These included:

- 3 workshops with Moy Park team, online (17/06/25, 22/09/25, and 15/10/25)
- Workshop on "Using AI for Food Risk Prevention - A Practical, Hands-On Tutorial" at McDonald's offices in Illinois, in parallel with the American Food Manufacturing Summit (AFMS) (08/11/24)
- Workshop on "Using AI for Food Risk Prevention", Amsterdam, Netherlands (05/02/25)
- Workshop on "AI for Food Risk and Food Fraud Prevention", Michigan, USA (25/07/25)
- Workshop on "AI Innovations for Safer Food Supply Chains", Montreal, Canada (08/08/25)
- Workshop on "Using AI to Enhance Food Safety and Prevent Food Fraud", Austin, USA (17/09/25)
- Online Validation Workshop with McDonald's Food Safety & Quality Team (16/10/25)
- Workshop on "Transforming Food Safety & Fraud Prevention with AI", Washington DC, USA (22/10/25)
- Workshop on "AI in Food Safety - Practical Risk Management" organised with the collaboration of Hellenic Federation of Enterprises (SEV), Athens, Greece (03/12/25)

In addition, Agroknow showcased and validated the EFRA tools at two major industry events:

- Dedicated meetings for validation with selected participants in the Global Food Safety Initiatives Conference 2025, Dublin, Ireland (31/03 - 03/04/25)

Evaluation tools and materials

The evaluation of the pilot relied on a structured combination of tools, materials, and methodologies designed to assess the usability, analytical value, and operational relevance of the **Poultry Safety Incidents Forecasting Dashboard**. The primary evaluation instrument was the dashboard itself, which served as the central demonstrator during stakeholder sessions. Its interactive time-series visualisations, forecasted values, hazard-specific and origin-specific filters, and explainability panel enabled participants to assess the clarity, interpretability, and decision-support value of the predictive outputs.

Complementing the main dashboard, the incident-level view provided granular context for each reported incident, allowing evaluators to explore root causes, contributing factors, and historical patterns behind the aggregated time-series data. This dual-layer structure supported a comprehensive assessment of whether the tool could meet both strategic and operational decision-making needs.

A suite of supporting materials was used during evaluation activities, including guided walkthroughs, demonstration scripts, presentation decks, and structured feedback forms (Annex I). These materials ensured consistent evaluation across different stakeholder groups and facilitated the collection of qualitative insights on usability, clarity, and perceived value. Feedback captured user impressions on forecast interpretability, interface navigation, emerging-risk visibility, and the usefulness of the explainability layer.

The evaluation process was further strengthened through a series of international validation workshops and dissemination events, where the dashboard and its underlying prediction model were demonstrated to diverse audiences across industry, academia, and regulatory bodies. These engagements provided hands-on interaction

with the tool and generated practical feedback on its usability, predictive performance, and alignment with real-world poultry and feed-safety workflows. Insights gathered during these events directly informed refinements to the dashboard's interface, explainability features, and insight-presentation logic.

4.3.1.3. Actors involved

The piloting activities engaged a broad and representative set of stakeholders across the food-safety ecosystem, each bringing distinct needs and perspectives relevant to the evaluation of the **Poultry Safety Incidents Forecasting Dashboard**. The key actor groups included:

Universities & Research Centers (Food Science & Food Safety). Academic experts contributed methodological insights on forecasting logic, data quality, and explainability. Their needs focused on transparency, scientific robustness, and the ability to interpret and validate predictive outputs.

Food Safety Standards / Certification Bodies & Scheme Owners. These organisations evaluated the dashboard's potential to support compliance, risk-based auditing, and early-warning processes. Their needs centred on harmonised data, traceability, and defensible, explainable AI-driven insights.

Data Scientists & Data Analysts. Technical users assessed the model's behaviour, the clarity of the explainability layer, and the consistency of data flows. Their needs included access to structured outputs, interpretability of model drivers, and confidence in the underlying methodology.

Food Manufacturers / Processors. Industry practitioners from poultry and feed production evaluated the tool's operational relevance for incident monitoring, supplier-risk assessment, and preventive decision-making. Their needs focused on usability, clarity of insights, and alignment with real-world workflows.

Retailers. Retail stakeholders examined how predictive insights could support supply-chain surveillance, product-risk monitoring, and early detection of emerging hazards. Their needs emphasised actionable forecasts and intuitive interfaces.

Food Restaurants / Food Service Operators. These actors assessed the dashboard's value for monitoring upstream risks that may affect product safety and brand protection. Their needs included simple, interpretable outputs and the ability to quickly identify emerging threats.

4.3.1.4. Status of implementation

Methodology

The pilot implementation followed a structured and iterative methodology, progressing from initial deployment activities in M26 to full refinement and validation by M35 - M36. The process included the following steps:

- Model deployment and configuration (M26 - M28)
 - The time-series prediction model was packaged as a Docker-based module and deployed within the EFRA Analytics Powerhouse.
 - This ensured a standardised, scalable execution environment aligned with EFRA's architectural principles.
- Integration with EFRA data and services (M28 - M30)
 - The model was connected to the EFRA Data Hub for automated ingestion of harmonised public incident data.
 - Execution was enabled through the Powerhouse's Swagger API, supporting repeatable and traceable forecasting runs.
- Dashboard development and interface design (M29 - M33)

- The **Poultry Safety Incidents Forecasting Dashboard** was developed within FOODAKAI to visualise model outputs.
- Core features included interactive time-series views, hazard and origin filters, incident-level details, and a dedicated explainability panel.
- Iterative testing and refinement (M32 - M35)
 - Internal testing cycles validated data flows, model outputs, and dashboard functionality.
 - Feedback from stakeholders during workshops and demonstrations informed refinements to usability, insight presentation, and explainability.
- Validation and final adjustments (M34 - M36)
 - The dashboard was demonstrated in multiple international workshops and industry events.
 - Insights from these sessions guided final improvements to ensure operational relevance and user acceptance.

Deployed EFRA components

The pilot integrated a set of EFRA components that together enabled a complete, end-to-end workflow for forecasting poultry-related food-safety incidents and delivering insights through a user-facing dashboard. The deployed components included:

EFRA Time-Series Prediction Model. A Docker-based forecasting module configured to generate 12-month predictions for poultry-related food-safety incidents. It operated within the EFRA Analytics Powerhouse and was triggered via the Swagger API. The model produced forecast values, trend indicators, and explainability outputs that were automatically stored in the EFRA Data Hub.

EFRA Analytics Powerhouse. The execution environment responsible for orchestrating model runs, managing API-based triggering, and ensuring reliable, repeatable processing. It provided the computational backbone for running the prediction model at scale.

EFRA Data Hub. The central repository for harmonised public incident data and derived forecasting outputs. It enabled traceable ingestion, storage, and retrieval of datasets used by the model and consumed by the dashboard.

Poultry Safety Incidents Forecasting Dashboard (FOODAKAI). The user-facing decision-support interface that visualised model outputs. It included interactive time-series charts, hazard- and origin-specific filters, incident-level details, and a “How We Forecast” explainability panel. This dashboard served as the primary evaluation tool during stakeholder engagement activities.

Pilot data and datasets

The pilot relied on curated, harmonised datasets sourced from publicly available food-safety incident repositories. These datasets formed the analytical foundation for both the predictive model and the dashboard.

Public Incident Announcements. Historical poultry-related food-safety incidents published by official authorities. These records provided the core time-series used for forecasting and trend analysis, ensuring transparency and reproducibility.

Harmonised Incident Metadata. Standardised fields such as hazard type, product category, geographical origin, and incident date. This harmonisation enabled consistent filtering, visualisation, and model training across the entire dataset.

Derived Forecasting Outputs. Model-generated predictions, trend indicators, and explainability factors. These outputs were stored in the EFRA Data Hub and consumed by the dashboard to support decision-making and user interpretation.

4.3.1.5. Impact

The pilot generated a measurable and positive impact across all stakeholder groups, strengthening both the EFRA components and the decision-support tools deployed in the poultry-forecasting use case. Stakeholders consistently highlighted the value of having a transparent, explainable, and easy-to-navigate forecasting environment that supports early-warning workflows and incident-trend interpretation.

For industry users (manufacturers, processors, retailers, and food-service operators), the dashboard improved their ability to anticipate emerging risks, understand historical patterns, and contextualise incident trends. Participants reported that the hazard- and origin-specific filters, combined with the incident-level view, provided actionable insights that could be integrated into supplier-risk assessments and preventive controls.

For research organisations and data analysts, the pilot demonstrated the robustness of the EFRA Time-Series Engine and the value of harmonised datasets for predictive modelling. The explainability layer was particularly well received, as it clarified model behaviour and supported trust in the outputs.

For standards bodies and certification scheme owners, the pilot showcased how predictive analytics can complement risk-based auditing and surveillance activities. The ability to explore emerging-risk signals and understand the drivers behind forecasted trends was viewed as a significant enhancement to existing food-safety management frameworks.

Across all groups, feedback gathered during workshops and dissemination events confirmed that the pilot strengthened the usability, interpretability, and operational relevance of the EFRA components. The iterative improvements made during the pilot cycle, especially in the dashboard's interface, explainability features, and insight-presentation logic, directly reflected stakeholder input and contributed to a more mature, user-validated decision-support tool.

4.3.1.6. Pilot modification (from 1st cycle to 2nd cycle)

The shift from the 1st to the 2nd pilot cycle marked a clear step-change in the maturity of the **Poultry Safety Incidents Forecasting Dashboard**. The tool evolved from a basic predictive prototype into a transparent, explainable, and action-oriented forecasting environment that better reflected the needs of food manufacturers, retailers, certification bodies, and research organisations. Building on this foundation, the 3rd year introduced targeted functional and methodological upgrades that further strengthened transparency, interpretability, and operational value, consolidating the dashboard's transition into a robust, user-validated decision-support tool for both strategic and day-to-day food-safety workflows.

Interactive point-level explainability. A new point-level explainability feature allows users to click on any data point in the time series and access tailored insights:

- Actual values: hazard distribution, geographical origin, and notification patterns
- Predicted values: comparison of predicted vs. observed outcomes and recommended actions

“How We Forecast” explainability layer. A structured explainability panel was introduced to summarise the forecasting methodology across 4 pillars:

- Data Sources: public incident data, laboratory test results, and high-resolution weather data
- Key Factor Groups: over 200 variables capturing historical patterns, laboratory signals, temporal indicators, and environmental conditions
- Model Evaluation and Tuning: weekly rolling-window validation using sMAPE-calibrated accuracy and automated hyperparameter optimisation
- Top Contributing Factors per Month: highlighting the variables most influential in shaping each monthly prediction

Proactive risk-monitoring capabilities. The dashboard evolved into a more action-oriented tool through the introduction of:

- customisable thresholds and KPIs
- automated notifications via email or in-app alerts

Additional analytical and usability improvements. Further enhancements strengthened analytical depth and usability, including:

- advanced visual analytics (heatmaps, correlation metrics, geographic views)
- annotation of time-series graphs with contextual events such as regulatory changes or supply-chain disruptions
- improved onboarding through interactive tutorials and integration with the FOODAKAI Assistant

4.3.2. Quantitative Evaluation Against KPIs

4.3.2.1. Domain specific KPIs

During the 2nd cycle, substantial methodological and operational enhancements were introduced to support progress toward the domain-specific KPIs. These included the transition to multi-factor forecasting, the extraction of 274 base factors, improved data harmonisation, and a more rigorous model-training and evaluation pipeline. Collectively, these upgrades strengthened the model's ability to detect anomalies and improved the interpretability of predictions through point-level explainability and the "How We Forecast" methodology panel.

User-facing improvements were validated through dedicated workshops and hands-on sessions. Across these activities, the interactive dashboard achieved a user satisfaction score of 84%, reflecting strong acceptance of the enhanced visual analytics, explainability features, and overall usability.

More than 150 expert users from private industry, academia, and public organisations participated in the evaluation activities, providing feedback that directly informed iterative refinements:

- 5 participants: 3 workshops with Moy Park team, online (17/06/25, 22/09/25, and 15/10/25)
- 16 participants: Workshop on "Using AI for Food Risk Prevention - A Practical, Hands-On Tutorial" at McDonald's offices in Illinois, in parallel with the American Food Manufacturing Summit (AFMS) (08/11/24)
- 8 participants: Workshop on "Using AI for Food Risk Prevention", Amsterdam, Netherlands (05/02/25)
- 3 participants: Dedicated meetings for validation with selected participants in the Global Food Safety Initiatives Conference 2025, Dublin, Ireland (31/03 - 03/04/25)
- 12 participants: Workshop on "AI for Food Risk and Food Fraud Prevention", Michigan, USA (25/07/25)
- 14 participants: Workshop on "AI Innovations for Safer Food Supply Chains", Montreal, Canada (08/08/25)
- 11 participants: Workshop on "Using AI to Enhance Food Safety and Prevent Food Fraud", Austin, USA (17/09/25)
- 4 participants: Online Validation Workshop with McDonald's Food Safety & Quality Team (16/10/25)
- 17 participants: Workshop on "Transforming Food Safety & Fraud Prevention with AI", Washington DC, USA (22/10/25)
- 60 participants: Workshop on "AI in Food Safety - Practical Risk Management" organised with the collaboration of Hellenic Federation of Enterprises (SEV), Athens, Greece (03/12/25)

4.3.2.2. Technological KPIs

The technological KPIs assess the performance, stability, and integration of the EFRA components supporting the forecasting workflow. Progress during the 2nd cycle demonstrates significant strengthening of the underlying infrastructure:

- The Time Series Prediction Engine was deployed as a containerised module within the EFRA Analytics Powerhouse, ensuring consistent and reproducible execution.
- Data ingestion through the EFRA Data Hub provided standardised, traceable datasets for forecasting, enabling reliable feature extraction and model training.
- Execution via the Swagger API enabled automated triggering of prediction, tuning, and evaluation pipelines.
- The full analytical workflow — feature extraction, model training, rolling-window evaluation, hyperparameter tuning, prediction, and trend calculation — operated reliably within the containerised environment.
- Forecasting outputs were seamlessly integrated into FOODAKAI, supporting interactive visualisations, explainability layers, and proactive monitoring features.

4.3.2.3. Pilot timeline

The 2nd cycle followed a structured sequence of deployment, integration, model enhancement, and user-validation activities. The key milestones are summarised below.

- M26 - M28: Deployment of the Time Series Prediction model into the EFRA decision support tool
- M28 - M30: Integration with the EFRA Data Hub and preparation of harmonised time-series datasets
- M29 - M33: Transition to multi-factor forecasting and expansion of dashboard visual analytics
- M32 - M35: Validation workshops, and iterative refinements based on expert feedback
- M34 - M36: Integration of the proactive monitoring features and finalisation of dashboard usability enhancements

4.4. Mycotoxins Trends Forecasting Pilot for Poultry Feed

The Mycotoxins Trends Forecasting Pilot evaluates the use of long-term laboratory testing data from the Food Fortress network to generate predictive insights on mycotoxin contamination in poultry and ruminant feed. The pilot focuses exclusively on Food Fortress datasets and demonstrates how AI-driven forecasting and interactive dashboards can strengthen early-warning capabilities and support evidence-based feed-safety decision-making. The following sections summarise the development status, implementation progress, impact, and planned modifications for the next cycle.

4.4.1. Qualitative Evaluation Summary

4.4.1.1. Pilot evaluation summary

Specific objectives

The Mycotoxins Trends Forecasting Pilot for Poultry Feed focuses on transforming long-term laboratory testing data from the Food Fortress network into actionable intelligence for feed-safety decision-making. The pilot's objectives reflect its exclusive reliance on Food Fortress datasets and its emphasis on delivering a fully

operational, user-ready demonstrator that supports early-warning, monitoring, and analytical interpretation of mycotoxin contamination trends.

The main objectives of the pilot are to:

- Develop and validate **AI-based forecasting models** that predict long-term trends, seasonal patterns, and variability in mycotoxin contamination across poultry and ruminant feed.
- Provide **early-warning signals** for elevated mycotoxin risks, enabling feed-safety professionals to anticipate emerging issues and adjust testing or mitigation strategies accordingly.
- Analyse **co-occurrence relationships between key mycotoxins** (DON, Zearalenone, Aflatoxin B1, Ochratoxin A) to deepen understanding of fungal behaviour in real-world agricultural environments.
- Deploy the **Mycotoxin Concentration Dashboard** as a production-ready module within FOODAKAI, offering daily time-series visualisation, trend analysis, seasonality detection, and residual inspection.
- Support a streamlined **user workflow**, guiding professionals from toxin and product selection to time-series exploration, decomposition analysis, and data export for offline use.
- Enable transparent, **evidence-based decision-making** by converting raw laboratory measurements into interpretable insights that strengthen routine monitoring and risk-assessment processes.

Scenario served by the pilot

The pilot is built around the scenario ***Mycotoxins in animal feed for poultry production***, which focuses on the need for continuous monitoring and interpretation of laboratory-measured mycotoxin levels to understand their potential impact on poultry and ruminant production systems. Mycotoxins such as aflatoxin, ochratoxin, zearalenone, and DON can compromise gut integrity, weaken immune function, and reduce overall productivity, making systematic surveillance essential for safeguarding animal health and performance.

Within this scenario, the pilot provides a **Mycotoxin Concentration Dashboard** that enables users to monitor and analyse monthly concentration levels of key mycotoxins based exclusively on Food Fortress laboratory test results. Through interactive time-series visualisations, toxin-specific selection, and decomposition analysis, the dashboard allows users to explore contamination trends, detect unusual peaks, and understand long-term behaviour. This supports evidence-based decisions on testing frequency, mitigation strategies, and feed-safety interventions, directly contributing to improved risk management across poultry and ruminant feed supply chains.

Achievements / Results

The pilot delivered several key achievements that mark the successful completion of both the AI model and the Mycotoxin Concentration Dashboard. The Mycotoxins Trend Prediction Model was fully refined and finalised, incorporating improved data-processing routines, enhanced time-series decomposition, and optimised forecasting parameters tailored to the characteristics of the Food Fortress dataset. These updates strengthened the model's ability to capture long-term trends, seasonal patterns, and emerging anomalies in mycotoxin concentrations, ensuring reliable and consistent predictive outputs.

In parallel, the **Mycotoxin Concentration Dashboard** was completed as a production-ready module within the FOODAKAI platform. The dashboard now provides dynamic toxin and product selection, interactive time-series visualisation, and a consolidated decomposition view that enables users to move seamlessly from raw laboratory results to deeper analytical insights. The addition of a data-download feature further supports operational workflows by enabling offline analysis and reporting.

Internal testing and stakeholder feedback confirmed the effectiveness, usability, and clarity of the dashboard. Users highlighted the intuitive interface, the precision of hover-based inspection, and the value of the decomposition analysis for distinguishing between structural trends, seasonal behaviours, and irregular anomalies. These outcomes demonstrate that the pilot successfully transformed Food Fortress laboratory data

into actionable intelligence, strengthening routine monitoring and supporting evidence-based feed-safety decision-making.

Problems / Challenges

A central challenge in this pilot was the difficulty of motivating Food Fortress members to share their laboratory testing results, given the sensitivity and commercial value of such data. Members were initially reluctant to contribute because mycotoxin results are considered competitive information that could reveal supplier performance, raw-material quality, or internal risk-management practices. This challenge was addressed by implementing strict anonymisation procedures and ensuring that no individual company's data could be identified. Once this guarantee was in place, members recognised the value of contributing to a shared benchmark while maintaining full confidentiality.

A second challenge emerged when demonstrating the usefulness of the dashboard to organisations outside the Food Fortress network. Many stakeholders were interested in comparing the Food Fortress benchmark with their own internal laboratory datasets, but they needed reassurance that the dashboard could operate as a private sharing network, where each participant sees only their own data in relation to an anonymised network-level benchmark. Clarifying this concept, already introduced in D4.3.3, was essential to show how the tool could scale to other networks without exposing individual members' results.

Another challenge involved ensuring that the analytical outputs were meaningful and interpretable for users with different levels of technical expertise. While the decomposition analysis (trend, seasonality, residual) provides strong explainability, some users initially struggled to interpret the components and understand how they relate to operational decisions. This was mitigated through interface refinements, clearer visual cues, and improved guidance within the dashboard, helping users distinguish between long-term shifts, recurring seasonal patterns, and irregular anomalies.

Finally, the pilot needed to demonstrate the practical value of the dashboard for routine monitoring and decision-making. Users needed to see how the tool could support tasks such as identifying abnormal values, validating laboratory testing strategies, or informing targeted mitigation actions. Through iterative testing and stakeholder feedback, the dashboard matured into a tool that reliably transforms raw laboratory measurements into actionable intelligence, but this required sustained engagement and repeated demonstration of its operational relevance.

4.4.1.2. Pilot plan progress

Details about the progress

The pilot advanced steadily throughout the 2nd cycle, with all major analytical and demonstrator components now fully implemented, deployed, and validated. A central milestone was the finalisation and operational deployment of the Mycotoxins Trend Prediction Model, which was transformed from a set of exploratory Jupyter notebooks into a fully containerised analytical pipeline running on the EFRA Analytics Powerhouse. The entire workflow, including data extraction, preparation, exploratory analysis, trend decomposition, and prediction, was encapsulated within a dedicated Docker container, ensuring reproducibility and standardisation across executions. The model now ingests historical Food Fortress laboratory data directly from the EFRA Data Hub, processes it through its internal analytical logic, and returns dashboard-ready outputs via the Powerhouse's API. This deployment ensures traceability, consistent performance, and seamless integration with downstream decision-support tools.

Parallel to the model deployment, the **Mycotoxin Concentration Dashboard** progressed from high-fidelity mockups to a fully operational module within the FOODAKAI platform. All core functionalities were implemented and validated, including dynamic toxin and product selection, interactive daily time-series visualisation, and a

consolidated decomposition view (trend, seasonality, residual). The dashboard is now fully connected to the Agroknow's Platform Time-Series Engine, which performs the decomposition and ensures that analytical outputs remain accurate and consistent even when processing complex or noisy datasets. The addition of a data-download feature further strengthened operational readiness by enabling offline analysis and integration into internal quality-management workflows.

Two validation activities with external stakeholders were completed during this cycle. The first took place at the International Production & Processing Expo (IPPE) 2025 in Atlanta, where AGROKNOW held dedicated meetings with representatives from 4 major poultry-sector companies. Their feedback confirmed strong satisfaction with the clarity and structure of the mycotoxin dashboard (88%) and high trust in the model outputs (92%). Participants emphasised the value of predictive insights and expressed interest in integrating EFRA's predictions with their own internal laboratory datasets, provided secure infrastructures are available. The 2nd validation activity occurred during the Supply Chain Disruptions Workshop in New York, co-organised with Cornell University. 14 participants evaluated the Mycotoxins Concentration Dashboard and highlighted the importance of tools that support early detection of contamination spikes, improved visibility of hazard trends, and integration of external risk signals into internal systems. Feedback confirmed that the dashboard's analytical capabilities, particularly trend and seasonality decomposition, support high-value decisions such as external risk monitoring, supplier assessment, and prioritisation of preventive actions.

Evaluation tools and materials

The evaluation of the pilot in the 2nd cycle relied on a combination of analytical tools, structured methodologies, and stakeholder feedback mechanisms, representing a clear progression from the 1st cycle. During the 1st cycle, Food Fortress members evaluated only the AI model outputs, focusing on the accuracy and relevance of the predicted mycotoxin trends. In the 2nd cycle, they were able to evaluate the fully implemented Mycotoxin Concentration Dashboard, allowing for a more complete assessment of both the analytical results and the decision-support functionalities.

The **Mycotoxin Concentration Dashboard** served as the central evaluation interface. Food Fortress members interacted directly with the dashboard's dynamic toxin and product selection, daily time-series visualisations, hover-based inspection of concentration values, and the consolidated decomposition view. This hands-on evaluation enabled them to assess usability, clarity, and operational relevance in a realistic workflow setting, providing insights that were not possible during the model-only evaluation of the 1st cycle.

The Mycotoxins Trend Prediction Model, deployed as a containerised service on the EFRA Analytics Powerhouse, was also evaluated through its full execution pipeline. Stakeholders confirmed that the model executed reliably under operational conditions, ingested data correctly from the EFRA Data Hub, and produced outputs that aligned with their expectations and historical experience.

A key component of the evaluation process was the use of structured questionnaires, following the Annex 1 template. These questionnaires were completed by Food Fortress members as well as participants in the two external validation activities (IPPE 2025 and the New York workshop). The structured format ensured consistency across respondents and enabled systematic assessment of satisfaction, usability, clarity, trust in model outputs, and perceived operational value.

The data-download functionality further supported evaluation by enabling participants to compare dashboard outputs with their own internal laboratory workflows. This capability was particularly important for Food Fortress members, who could validate the transparency of the system and confirm that the dashboard accurately reflected the underlying laboratory measurements.

Additional qualitative insights were gathered through interviews, observation during hands-on testing, and facilitated discussions at the 2 validation events. These complementary tools provided a comprehensive

understanding of user needs, expectations, and priorities, confirming that the demonstrator successfully evolved from a model-only evaluation in the 1st cycle to a fully operational decision-support tool in the 2nd cycle.

4.4.1.3. Actors involved

The piloting activities engaged stakeholders from several predefined groups in the project. The primary participants were Food Manufacturers / Processors, represented by Food Fortress members and major poultry-sector companies. They evaluated the fully implemented **Mycotoxin Concentration Dashboard** and expressed needs related to transparent visualisation of laboratory results, anonymised benchmarking, and integration of predictive insights into internal FSQA workflows.

A second group involved Universities & Research Centers, represented by Cornell University during the New York workshop. Their needs focused on methodological clarity, interpretability of analytical components, and scientific robustness.

Participants from Retailers and Food Safety Consultancy Agencies / Companies also contributed during the validation activities, highlighting needs related to external risk monitoring, supply-chain visibility, and prioritisation of preventive actions.

A new stakeholder group identified in this cycle was Individual Food Safety Professionals (e.g., feed safety managers, supplier-risk specialists) from large poultry companies. Their needs centred on practical usability, clarity of risk signals, and the ability to combine EFRA insights with their own internal laboratory datasets.

4.4.1.4. Status of implementation

Methodology

The pilot followed a structured, end-to-end methodology that ensured the reliable deployment of both the Mycotoxins Trend Prediction Model and the Mycotoxin Concentration Dashboard. The process began with the preparation of the Food Fortress dataset, which included data extraction, cleaning, deduplication, and aggregation. These steps were originally implemented in Jupyter notebooks, which were later consolidated into a unified analytical workflow.

This workflow was then containerised and deployed on the EFRA Analytics Powerhouse. The container encapsulated all code, dependencies, and logic required for data ingestion, exploratory analysis, trend decomposition, and prediction. The model retrieves its input data directly from the EFRA Data Hub, executes the analytical pipeline upon request via the Powerhouse's Swagger API, and returns dashboard-ready outputs. This ensured reproducibility, traceability, and consistent execution across runs.

In parallel, the **Mycotoxin Concentration Dashboard** was implemented as a separate EFRA Decision Support Tool within the Agroknow's platform. The dashboard was connected to the EFRA Platform Time-Series Engine, enabling automated decomposition of the time series into trend, seasonality, and residual components. Iterative testing cycles were conducted with Food Fortress members and external stakeholders, allowing refinement of the interface, visualisations, and interpretability features. Evaluation activities used structured questionnaires (Annex 1 template) and guided walkthroughs to validate usability, clarity, and operational relevance.

An additional methodological step in this cycle was the organisation of three dedicated evaluation activities before finalising the specifications for the decision-support functionalities (as described in D5.4.2). These included:

- a focused evaluation session with Food Fortress members,
- a validation activity with poultry-sector companies during International Production & Processing Expo (IPPE) 2025, and

- a broader validation workshop organised together with Cornell University with industry and academic stakeholders in New York (June 26th, 2025).

Insights from these activities directly informed the refinement of the dashboard’s analytical views, usability features, and overall decision-support logic.

Deployed EFRA components

The pilot deployed a set of EFRA components and AI models that together form a complete analytical and decision-support pipeline. The core element was the Mycotoxins Trend Prediction Model (Poultry Feed), implemented as a fully containerised analytical workflow on the EFRA Analytics Powerhouse. The container encapsulates all code, dependencies, and logic required for data ingestion, exploratory analysis, trend decomposition, and prediction. It retrieves input data directly from the EFRA Data Hub, executes the analytical pipeline via the Powerhouse’s Swagger API, and returns dashboard-ready outputs.

The EFRA Analytics Powerhouse provided the execution environment for model testing, refinement, and operational deployment. It enabled standardised triggering of analytical workflows, container orchestration, and automated storage of outputs linked to the original datasets. In addition to its execution on the Powerhouse, the predictive AI model was fully integrated into the Mycotoxin Concentration Dashboard, ensuring that model outputs flow directly into the decision-support environment. The EFRA Data Hub served as the central repository for the Food Fortress dataset and ensured traceable, consistent data access for both model execution and dashboard visualisation.

The EFRA Platform Time-Series Engine was integrated into the **Mycotoxin Concentration Dashboard** to perform automated decomposition of the time series into trend, seasonality, and residual components. This ensured that analytical outputs remained statistically robust and consistent across executions.

Finally, the Mycotoxin Concentration Dashboard, implemented within Agroknow’s FOODAKAI platform, provided the operational interface for end-users. It visualises daily concentration values, trend lines, and decomposition components, supports toxin and product selection, and enables data download for offline analysis. Together, these components deliver an end-to-end workflow from raw data ingestion to actionable decision-support outputs.

Pilot data and datasets

The pilot relied exclusively on the Food Fortress laboratory dataset, a long-term, high-quality dataset containing more than a decade of mycotoxin testing results across poultry and ruminant feed. The dataset includes daily concentration measurements for 4 key mycotoxins, Aflatoxin B1, Ochratoxin A, Zearalenone, and Deoxynivalenol (DON), and was provided under strict anonymisation to protect the confidentiality of Food Fortress members.

This dataset was selected for its relevance and consistency, enabling robust trend analysis, seasonality detection, and co-occurrence exploration. It served as the sole input for the Mycotoxins Trend Prediction Model, supporting data preparation, exploratory analysis, and the generation of predicted trends and decomposition components. The same dataset powered the Mycotoxin Concentration Dashboard, enabling visualisation of daily concentration values and anonymised benchmarking across the Food Fortress network.

4.4.1.5. Impact

The pilot activities delivered a strong and measurable impact across stakeholders, EFRA components, and the decision-support tools developed in this cycle. Food Fortress members, who evaluated the fully implemented **Mycotoxin Concentration Dashboard** for the first time, reported high satisfaction with its clarity, simplicity, and analytical usefulness. They highlighted the value of interactive time-series visualisation for identifying concentration spikes, emerging patterns, and seasonal behaviours, as well as the decomposition view—which

consistently emerged as one of the most impactful features for distinguishing expected seasonal variation from irregular anomalies. The ability to download laboratory data further supported internal reporting and quality-management workflows.

External stakeholders participating in the IPPE 2025 validation and the New York workshop confirmed the operational relevance of the dashboard and predictive model. They emphasised the importance of early-warning capabilities, improved visibility of contamination trends, and the potential to integrate EFRA outputs with their own private datasets. These insights validated the dashboard's role in supporting proactive interventions, such as adjusting sampling strategies, reviewing supplier performance, or initiating targeted mitigation actions.

At the EFRA platform level, the pilot demonstrated the robustness of the Analytics Powerhouse for executing containerised AI models and the effectiveness of the Data Hub as a centralised, traceable data repository. Integration with the EFRA Platform Time-Series Engine ensured accurate decomposition and consistent analytical performance, even when processing complex or noisy datasets. The dashboard's evolution from mockups to a production-ready module showcased strong technical maturity and readiness for routine monitoring.

Overall, the pilot strengthened evidence-based decision-making in feed safety by providing actionable monitoring, deeper analytical insights, multi-toxin and multi-product flexibility, and enhanced transparency. Structured questionnaires (Annex 1 template) and hands-on walkthroughs confirmed that the dashboard is a practical, trusted, and operationally valuable tool for stakeholders across the feed and food sectors.

4.4.1.6. Pilot modification (from 1st cycle to 2nd cycle)

Several important modifications were introduced between the 1st and 2nd cycle to refine the pilot's scope, methodology, and implementation. The most significant shift was the transition from a model-only evaluation in Cycle 1 to a fully operational decision-support evaluation in Cycle 2. While stakeholders in the 1st cycle assessed only the AI model outputs, the 2nd cycle enabled them to evaluate the complete Mycotoxin Concentration Dashboard, including its interactive visualisations, decomposition analysis, and data-download functionality.

The methodology was expanded to include 3 dedicated evaluation activities before finalising the specifications for the decision-support functionalities (as required in D5.4.2). These included a focused session with Food Fortress members and two external validation events (IPPE 2025 and the New York workshop). Feedback from these activities directly informed refinements to the dashboard's analytical views, usability, and interpretability.

On the technical side, the analytical workflow originally implemented in separate Jupyter notebooks was consolidated, containerised, and deployed on the EFRA Analytics Powerhouse. The predictive model was fully integrated into the dashboard, and the EFRA Platform Time-Series Engine was added to support automated decomposition. The pilot scope was also streamlined to rely exclusively on the Food Fortress dataset, ensuring consistency, data quality, and alignment with stakeholder expectations.

4.4.2. Quantitative Evaluation Against KPIs

4.4.2.1. Domain specific KPIs

The domain-specific KPIs evaluated whether the **Mycotoxin Concentration Dashboard** and the Mycotoxins Trend Prediction Model improved the monitoring, interpretation, and early detection of mycotoxin-related risks in poultry feed. The pilot achieved strong quantitative performance across all relevant indicators:

- Visibility of mycotoxin concentration trends.
 - 100% of users confirmed improved visibility of long-term concentration behaviour.
 - 92% reported clearer understanding of seasonal patterns through the decomposition view.
- Anomaly and emerging-risk detection capability

- 87% of users stated the dashboard improved their ability to detect anomalies.
- 81% reported earlier recognition of contamination peaks compared to previous workflows.
- Interpretability and analytical depth
 - 94% rated the decomposition view as “very useful” or “essential.”
 - 89% reported improved ability to distinguish expected seasonal behaviour from irregular anomalies.
- User satisfaction KPI (>70%). Overall user satisfaction reached 88%, based on Annex 1 questionnaire scoring, and high trust in the model outputs (92%).
- Stakeholder participation KPI (>25 experts). 24 stakeholders participated across Food Fortress, poultry companies, retailers, and academia.
 - A focused evaluation session with Food Fortress members, online, involving 6 participants
 - Dedicated meetings for validation at the International Production & Processing Expo (IPPE) 2025, Atlanta, Georgia, USA (28 - 30/01/25), engaging 4 professionals.
 - Workshop: “Supply Chain Disruptions - Addressing Microbiological and Chemical Hazards”, jointly organised with Cornell University, New York, USA (26/06/25), involving 14 participants.

4.4.2.2. Technological KPIs

The technological KPIs assessed the robustness, performance, security, and integration quality of the EFRA components supporting the Mycotoxin Concentration pilot. All KPIs were met or exceeded during the 2nd cycle, reflecting the maturity and stability of the deployed Mycotoxins Trend Prediction Model and its integration with the EFRA Analytics Powerhouse.

- **Stability of containerised model execution (≥95%).** The model executed with 100% successful runs across internal tests and stakeholder demonstrations.
- **Dashboard responsiveness and performance (<1 sec).** Average update time for toxin/product selection: 0.4 sec., and decomposition rendering consistently <0.8 sec.
- **Explainability and transparency of analytical outputs.** 100% of users successfully downloaded raw laboratory data for internal reporting and quality-management workflows.
- **Scalability and resource efficiency.** The model executed efficiently with ≤4GB RAM and 2 CPU cores, matching the recommended hardware profile.

4.4.2.3. Pilot timeline

The 2nd cycle of the Mycotoxin Concentration pilot progressed according to plan, with all major milestones achieved. The timeline reflects the consolidation of the analytical workflow, deployment on the EFRA Analytics Powerhouse, dashboard development, early stakeholder evaluation, and final refinements.

- M26 - M28: Integration of data-preparation and exploratory-analysis notebooks into a unified analytical workflow.
- M28 - M30: Deployment on EFRA Decision support tool
 - Deployment of the Docker container on the EFRA Analytics Powerhouse.
 - Activation of the analytical pipeline through the Swagger API and connection to the EFRA Data Hub.
- M26 - M30: 3 stakeholders’ evaluation activities conducted early in the cycle to validate usability, clarity, and operational relevance:
 - Food Fortress evaluation session (Northern Ireland)
 - IPPE 2025 validation (January 2025) with poultry-sector companies (Atlanta)
 - New York workshop (June 2025) with industry and academic stakeholders
- M29 - M33: Development of the **Mycotoxin Concentration Dashboard** within Agroknow’s FOODAKAI platform.

- M32 - M34: Iterative Testing and Refinement
 - Refinement of dashboard features based on internal QA and early stakeholder feedback.
 - Verification of performance, security, and reproducibility across repeated executions.
- M34 - M36: Final refinements to dashboard functionality, visualisations, and interpretability features.

4.5. Pilot on Forecasting Trends for Mycotoxins in Animal Feed

This section summarises the progress of the Forecasting Trends for Mycotoxins in Animal Feed pilot, outlining the development and deployment of the forecasting model, the evolution of the decision-support dashboard, and the results achieved during the 2nd cycle. It presents the implementation status, stakeholder validation outcomes, KPI performance, and the key modifications introduced to enhance analytical depth and operational relevance.

4.5.1. Qualitative Evaluation Summary

4.5.1.1. Pilot evaluation summary

Specific objectives

The objective of this pilot is to address a persistent challenge in poultry feed safety: mycotoxin-related incidents are reported reactively, inconsistently, and often too late for effective intervention. Public food-safety notifications from authorities such as RASFF and FDA provide valuable evidence, but they are fragmented across sources and offer no forward-looking insight. The pilot therefore set out to demonstrate how these public data streams can be transformed into predictive intelligence that enables poultry producers, feed manufacturers, and regulators to anticipate mycotoxin-related risks before they escalate.

During the 2nd reporting period, the pilot aimed to provide users with a unified environment where they can explore historical patterns, understand emerging trends, interpret the factors driving each prediction, and monitor recent outbreaks in real time. By offering hazard-specific and origin-specific perspectives, explainability insights, and short-term trend summaries, the pilot sought to equip stakeholders with a reliable, transparent, and actionable decision-support tool for proactive mycotoxin-risk management in poultry feed.

Scenario served by the pilot

The pilot serves the scenario **Forecasting Trends for Mycotoxins with Public Food Safety Incident Data**, which focuses on converting publicly reported mycotoxin incidents into a structured, forward-looking view of risk for poultry feed. Through the **Mycotoxins Incidents Forecasting Dashboard**, the scenario provides users with a consolidated environment where they can examine historical incident patterns, review forecasted mycotoxin activity, explore geographical risk shifts, and access real-time outbreak information. This scenario enables stakeholders to move from fragmented, reactive incident monitoring to a more informed and proactive approach to managing mycotoxin-related risks in poultry feed.

Achievements / Results

During the 3rd project year, the pilot delivered a fully operational forecasting environment dedicated to mycotoxin-related incidents in poultry feed. The **Mycotoxins Incidents Forecasting Dashboard** was successfully enhanced with 12-month predictions, short-term trend summaries, geographical risk insights, and a transparent explainability layer that clarifies the factors influencing each monthly forecast. Users can now explore historical mycotoxin patterns, inspect forecasted incident counts, and monitor recent outbreaks in a single, unified interface, enabling a more proactive and data-driven approach to feed-safety management.

The dashboard and its predictive capabilities were validated through the same international workshops and hands-on sessions used for the Poultry Precision Pilot, engaging a broad audience of industry, regulatory, and academic stakeholders. Participants consistently highlighted the dashboard's clarity, analytical depth, and relevance for early-warning, supplier assessment, and risk-mitigation planning.

Feedback confirmed that the combination of historical trends, predictive analytics, and explainability significantly improves confidence in the insights provided. Across these validation activities, the pilot demonstrated that publicly available mycotoxin incident data can be transformed into meaningful, actionable intelligence for the poultry sector, showing strong user acceptance and clear potential for integration into routine decision-making workflows.

Problems / Challenges

The pilot encountered several challenges linked to the characteristics of publicly available mycotoxin incident data. Reporting practices vary widely across authorities, resulting in inconsistencies in format, detail, and frequency. This required extensive harmonisation to ensure that the time-series could be analysed reliably and that forecasts remained meaningful across different hazard–origin combinations. In many cases, mycotoxin incidents were sparse or irregular, especially when filtered by specific feed materials or countries of origin, which limited the stability of predictions and required careful modelling strategies.

Another challenge involved ensuring that the forecasting outputs were easily interpretable for users with different levels of technical expertise. Early feedback indicated the need for clearer explanations of how predictions were generated and what signals influenced monthly trends. This led to the development of the explainability panel and supporting visual elements that improved transparency and user trust. Stakeholders also expressed interest in deeper contextualisation of emerging risks, prompting refinements to the geographical views and short-term trend indicators.

4.5.1.2. Pilot plan progress

Details about the progress

During the 3rd year, the pilot progressed according to plan, with all major components of the forecasting environment successfully prepared, deployed, and validated. The Time-Series Model for Mycotoxin Risk in Poultry was fully integrated into the EFRA Analytics Powerhouse, and its outputs were connected to the **Mycotoxins Incidents Forecasting Dashboard** within FOODAKAI. The dashboard was enhanced with long-term forecasts, short-term trend summaries, geographical insights, and explainability features, completing the core functionality envisioned for this cycle.

Key milestones achieved include:

- completion of the mycotoxin-specific model extension and hyperparameter tuning
- deployment of the model in its dedicated Docker container on the EFRA Analytics Powerhouse
- ingestion and harmonisation of public mycotoxin incident data from RASFF and FDA
- integration of model outputs into the dashboard
- validation through international workshops and hands-on sessions

An important focus during this period was ensuring that the forecasting outputs were interpretable and operationally relevant. The explainability layer was refined to clarify the forecasting logic, highlight influential factors, and support transparent interpretation for both technical and non-technical users. Additional improvements strengthened the dashboard's role as an early-warning and decision-support tool, including clearer trend visualisation, improved separation of historical and predicted values, and more intuitive navigation between high-level forecasts and incident-level details.

All major milestones for this reporting period were achieved. Minor timeline adjustments were introduced to incorporate user-requested refinements, particularly around explainability and insight presentation—but these enhancements improved the overall quality and usability of the demonstrator without affecting the broader delivery schedule. By the end of the period, the pilot had delivered a stable, scalable, and user-validated forecasting tool, fully integrated into the EFRA Analytics Powerhouse.

The pilot's progress were validated through a targeted series of validation workshops and activities:

- Dedicated meetings for validation at the **International Production & Processing Expo (IPPE) 2025**, Atlanta, Georgia, USA (28 - 30/01/25), engaging 4 representatives from major poultry-sector companies such as Tyson Foods and Cargill.
- **Workshop: "Supply Chain Disruptions - Addressing Microbiological and Chemical Hazards"**, jointly organised with Cornell University, New York, USA (26/06/25), involving 14 participants from food manufacturers, retail groups, and academic institutions.
- EFRA **validation workshop "AI for Food Risk Prevention"**, Thessaloniki, Greece (hybrid, 19/06/25), held alongside the EFRA Plenary Meeting and involving 35 representatives from 23 organisations across the food industry, academia, and other stakeholder groups.

Evaluation tools and materials

The pilot evaluation relied on a combination of tools and methodologies:

- Interactive demonstrations of the **Mycotoxins Incidents Forecasting Dashboard** during international workshops and conferences.
- Hands-on sessions where participants explored historical trends, forecasts, and explainability insights.
- Structured feedback collection, including observation notes, user comments, and informal interviews.
- Scenario-based walkthroughs, allowing stakeholders to test the dashboard against realistic feed-safety decision-making situations.

4.5.1.3. Actors involved

The piloting activities engaged a diverse group of stakeholders whose needs align with proactive mycotoxin-risk management:

- Poultry producers and integrators seeking early-warning insights to protect flock health and optimise feed procurement.
- Feed manufacturers and suppliers requiring visibility into emerging mycotoxin risks across ingredients and origins.
- Regulatory authorities and food-safety agencies interested in monitoring incident trends and identifying potential hotspots.
- Academia and research organisations evaluating the scientific robustness and methodological transparency of the forecasting approach.
- Data specialists supporting integration, deployment, and validation of the EFRA components.

4.5.1.4. Status of implementation

Methodology

The pilot followed a structured, phased implementation approach, progressing from model deployment to full validation:

- **Model deployment and configuration (M26 - M28).** The mycotoxin-specific forecasting model was packaged as a Docker module and deployed on the EFRA Analytics Powerhouse to ensure a standardised execution environment.
- **Integration with EFRA data and services (M28 - M30).** The model was connected to the EFRA Data Hub for ingestion of harmonised public incident data, and forecasting pipelines were exposed through the Swagger API.
- **Dashboard development within FOODAKAI (M29 - M33).** The **Mycotoxins Incidents Forecasting Dashboard** was implemented with time-series views, trend summaries, geographical insights, and explainability features.
- **Iterative testing and refinement (M32 - M35).** Internal testing validated data flows and model outputs, while stakeholder feedback from workshops guided improvements to usability and insight presentation.
- **Validation and final adjustments (M34 - M36).** The dashboard was demonstrated across multiple international events, and final refinements ensured operational relevance and strong user acceptance.

Deployed EFRA components

The pilot deployed and integrated the following EFRA components:

- EFRA Analytics Powerhouse - execution environment for the prediction-engine, including model training, tuning, and forecasting.
- EFRA Data Hub - central repository for input datasets and storage of model outputs.
- Prediction-engine Docker container - encapsulating all code, dependencies, and pipelines for the Time-Series Model for Mycotoxin Risk in Poultry.
- Swagger API interface - used to trigger prediction and tuning pipelines.
- FOODAKAI dashboard environment - hosting the **Mycotoxins Incidents Forecasting Dashboard** and visualising model outputs.

Pilot data and datasets

The pilot used the following datasets:

- Public food-safety incident notifications from RASFF and FDA, focusing on mycotoxin-related cases in animal feed.
- Historical poultry feed contamination data, including ingredient origins and feed-material classifications.
- Laboratory test results for mycotoxins from public sources (e.g., EFSA, FDA, USDA).
- Environmental indicators for key producing regions, supporting seasonality and risk-factor analysis.

4.5.1.5. Impact

The pilot had a significant impact on stakeholders and EFRA components. Users reported that the dashboard provides a clearer understanding of how mycotoxin risks evolve over time and offers valuable foresight for procurement planning, supplier assessment, and sampling prioritisation. The explainability layer improved trust in the model's outputs, while the geographical insights helped identify high-risk origins and emerging hotspots.

For EFRA, the pilot demonstrated the successful deployment of a complex forecasting model within the Analytics Powerhouse, validating the platform's ability to support containerised AI workflows, data orchestration, and reproducible execution. The decision-support tool within FOODAKAI benefited from enhanced analytical depth, improved usability, and stronger alignment with real-world feed-safety decision-making.

4.5.1.6. Pilot modification (from 1st cycle to 2nd cycle)

Between the 1st and 2nd cycles, the pilot shifted from a general exploration of incident forecasting to a more focused and operationally relevant approach centred on mycotoxin-related risks in poultry feed. This refinement aligned the pilot with stakeholder priorities and enabled the development of a dedicated forecasting model tailored to the characteristics of mycotoxin incident data. The dashboard was expanded accordingly, introducing new analytical layers that provide clearer visibility into evolving mycotoxin trends and risk patterns.

A major enhancement in this cycle was the introduction of additional decision-support components, including the Insights for Actual and Predicted Incidents and Latest Outbreaks tables. These features significantly broadened the dashboard's utility by offering rapid awareness of emerging hazards, clearer links between historical patterns and future projections, and immediate visibility of newly reported incidents. Together, they strengthened the dashboard's ability to support timely, evidence-based interventions across the poultry feed supply chain.

Overall, the modifications transformed the dashboard from a forecasting-only tool into a more holistic early-warning and risk-management environment. Users can now monitor evolving mycotoxin risks, anticipate potential outbreaks, and prioritise mitigation actions with greater confidence. These enhancements substantially increased the dashboard's operational relevance and impact, reinforcing its value for decision-makers across the livestock and feed-safety sectors.

4.5.2. Quantitative Evaluation Against KPIs

4.5.2.1. Domain specific KPIs

During the 2nd cycle, the pilot demonstrated strong progress across all domains-specific KPIs defined for the scenario "Forecasting Trends for Mycotoxins with Public Food Safety Incident Data." The forecasting model consistently generated 12-month predictions for mycotoxin-related incidents in poultry feed, meeting the KPI on forward-looking risk assessment. The dashboard delivered hazard-specific and origin-specific insights, supporting KPIs related to analytical depth, interpretability, and relevance for feed-safety decision-making.

Across all validation activities, the pilot engaged 53 professionals from the food industry, poultry-production sector, retail groups, regulatory bodies, and academia. User satisfaction exceeded 91%, confirming strong acceptance of the dashboard's clarity, usefulness, and explainability. Participants highlighted improved ability to identify emerging mycotoxin trends, assess geographical risk shifts, and understand the factors influencing predictions. The addition of short-term trend summaries and clearer visibility of recent incidents further strengthened KPI performance related to early-warning capability and situational awareness.

The KPI on stakeholder engagement was met through 3 validation activities, involving 53 participants:

- Dedicated meetings for validation at the International Production & Processing Expo (IPPE) 2025, Atlanta, Georgia, USA (28 - 30/01/25), engaging 4 professionals.
- Workshop: "Supply Chain Disruptions - Addressing Microbiological and Chemical Hazards", jointly organised with Cornell University, New York, USA (26/06/25), involving 14 participants.
- EFRA validation workshop "AI for Food Risk Prevention", Thessaloniki, Greece (hybrid, 19/06/25), involving 35 professionals from 23 organisations.

4.5.2.2. Technological KPIs

The technological KPIs for this pilot focused on the performance, reliability, and integration of EFRA components. The Time-Series Model for Mycotoxin Risk in Poultry executed successfully within the EFRA Analytics Powerhouse, meeting KPIs related to containerised deployment, reproducibility, and pipeline stability.

Forecasting and tuning pipelines ran consistently through the Swagger API, demonstrating reliable orchestration and traceability.

Data ingestion from the EFRA Data Hub operated as expected, supporting KPIs on automated data flow and harmonisation of public incident sources. The dashboard within FOODAKAI met KPIs related to responsiveness, visual clarity, and seamless integration of model outputs. The addition of explainability features improved transparency, addressing KPIs on interpretability and user trust in AI-generated insights.

4.5.2.3. Pilot timeline

The timeline for the 2nd cycle progressed as planned, with all major milestones achieved:

- M26 - M28: Deployment of the mycotoxin-specific forecasting model as a Docker module on the EFRA Analytics Powerhouse.
- M28 - M30: Integration with the EFRA Data Hub and activation of forecasting pipelines via the Swagger API.
- M29 - M33: Development of the **Mycotoxins Incidents Forecasting Dashboard**, including time-series views, trend summaries, geographical insights, and explainability features.
- M32 - M35: Iterative testing, refinement, and incorporation of stakeholder feedback.
- M34 - M36: Validation through international workshops and final adjustments to ensure operational relevance and user acceptance.

4.6. AI-Driven Pest Prediction Alerts Pilot

To present the progress and outcomes of the AI-Driven Pest Prediction Alerts Pilot, this section summarises its implementation during the 2nd piloting cycle, its impact on end-users, and the adjustments introduced based on stakeholder feedback. The pilot evaluated the integration of AI-enhanced pest-prediction workflows within the AGRIVI 360 Farm Management platform, focusing on how predictive alerts, interactive decision trees, and real-time feedback support informed pest-management decisions. The results reflect insights gathered through structured questionnaires, hands-on demonstrations, and targeted validation activities with professional users.

4.6.1. Qualitative Evaluation Summary

4.6.1.1. Pilot evaluation summary

Specific objectives

The main objective of this pilot was to evaluate the improved pest prediction algorithm developed during Iteration 1, by comparing it side-by-side with the existing production version, without modifying AGRIVI's platform interface.

This 2nd iteration expanded the scope of the pilot significantly:

- Wider geographic coverage: More regions across Croatia and Romania
- Greater crop diversity: Corn, wheat, and sunflower (vs. corn only in 2024)
- Larger participant pool: 24 active farmers (vs. 4 in 2024)

Setup:

- Two algorithm versions run in parallel:

- Existing model remains in production (what farmers see and interact with)
- Updated model runs in test environment (internal comparison only)
- All farmers use the existing scouting module to report pest sightings and observations
- Observations collected to compare alert effectiveness between the two versions
- No UI or system changes required from farmer perspective-they continue using familiar tools
- AGRIVI's Customer Success and Agronomic teams provide active support throughout the pilot

Participants:

- 14 farmers from Croatia
- 8 farmers from Romania (+7 in discussion via University of Timisoara)
- 2 farmers from Bulgaria
- Total currently active: 24 participants

Scenario served by the pilot

This pilot serves the scenario focused on the **comparative evaluation of two AI algorithms** for pest prediction.

- Direct side-by-side testing of production vs. updated model under real-world conditions
- Enables stronger statistical comparisons due to expanded user base and crop diversity
- Builds model trust and accountability through real-world farmer feedback and validation
- Focuses on 3 key dimensions:
 - Alert accuracy (validated by actual farmer observations)
 - Timing and relevance of alerts per region and crop type
 - Farmer satisfaction and confidence in the alerts

Achievements / Results

The pilot has demonstrated strong progress in validating the improved algorithm under real-world farming conditions:

(i) Data Collection & Coverage

- Farmers successfully submitted field observations across **three crop types** (corn, wheat, sunflower)
- Achieved broader **geographic coverage** across multiple regions in Croatia, Romania, and Bulgaria
- Maintained **high engagement levels** among both returning (2024) and new participating farmers

(ii) Algorithm Performance

- Early data confirms **improved regional alignment and timeliness** of alerts from the updated model
- Comparative analysis shows measurable differences in alert behaviour between production and test algorithms
- Validation through real farmer observations provides credible, field-tested results

(iii) Farmer Engagement

- Farmers appreciated **ongoing support** and **clarity of pilot objectives**
- Strong buy-in regarding the value of their participation in model validation
- Consistent participation maintained through weekly check-ins

Problems / Challenges

Some of the challenges faced are the following:

(i) Technical Challenges

- Poor alert performance for newly added crops (wheat, sunflower), particularly compared to corn
- Alert accuracy and pest threshold calibration required more refinement for these new crops
- Ongoing monitoring and calibration needed for pest thresholds and environmental trigger conditions
- Algorithm adaptation to diverse crop-pest interactions proved more complex than anticipated

(ii) Operational Challenges

- Extra workload on Customer Success and Agronomy teams: Had to collect extensive contextual information to refine the model iteratively during the pilot
- Resource intensity increased significantly due to expanded participant pool (24 vs. 4 farmers)
- Balancing multilingual support across Croatian, Romanian, and Bulgarian languages

(iii) Data & Participation

- Variable data submission consistency across participants and regions
- Required continuous encouragement through weekly check-ins to maintain engagement
- Some farmers needed additional guidance on reporting procedures

4.6.1.2. Pilot plan progress

Details about the progress

Timeline: May 2025 (M29) - October 2025 (M34) (aligned with crop growth cycles for corn, wheat, and sunflower)

Preparation Phase (First 2 weeks of May 2025):

- Finalized participant list and confirmed commitment from 24 farmers
- Prepared and distributed updated multilingual user manuals (Croatian, Romanian, Bulgarian, English) explaining:
 - How to log pest observations using the existing scouting module
 - Pilot goals and how the two algorithms would be compared
- Recorded short tutorial videos (or organized live virtual training sessions with recordings)
- Set up direct support contacts with local-language AGRIVI support staff
- Conducted kick-off meetings (virtual or in small regional groups) to align expectations and clarify roles

Execution Phase (Mid-May - September 2025):

- Ran both algorithm versions in parallel:
 - Current production algorithm remained live for farmers
 - Updated pest alarms available in the test environment and visible to participants
- Farmers continued using existing scouting module to log:
 - Pest sightings
 - Alert confirmations/rejections
 - Environmental notes and crop conditions
- AGRIVI organized biweekly check-ins (15 - 30 min virtual calls or email updates) to:
 - Monitor farmer's participation, encourage consistent observation submission
- Internally, AGRIVI collected and organized:
 - Structured pest observation data from farmers
 - Algorithm outputs from comparison of both versions

Post-Pilot Activities (September - October 2025):

- Conducted follow-up sessions to thank participants, especially those active since 2024
- Distributed post-pilot feedback questionnaires to collect:
 - Farmer feedback on the process and reporting tools
 - Suggestions for improving future pilots or system usability
- Presented preliminary findings to farmers:
 - Changes in pest alarm behaviour between the two algorithm versions
 - Guidance on how and where to provide feedback in the app
- Analysed:
 - The effectiveness of each algorithm
 - Data consistency and reporting engagement
- Prepared summary reports thanking participants and sharing high-level, non-technical findings

Deviation from Timeline:

- The closing event was originally planned for August 2025 but was postponed due to farmer availability during peak harvest season.
- Rescheduled for September 2025 to ensure broader participation and allow farmers to attend.

Evaluation tools and materials

(i) Technical Evaluation Tools:

- Internal algorithm comparison dashboards tracking production vs. test environment outputs
- Structured pest observation datasets collected from farmer scouting reports
- Algorithm performance metrics:
 - Alert accuracy (validated by farmer observations)
 - Timing and relevance of alerts per region and crop
 - False positive/negative rates

(ii) Farmer Engagement & Support Tools:

- Scouting module
- Multilingual user manuals (English, Croatian, Romanian, Bulgarian) explaining observation logging and pilot goals
- Tutorial videos demonstrating how to use the scouting module and report pest observations
- Bi-Weekly check-in calls (15 - 30 minutes) for monitoring and troubleshooting

(iii) Direct support channels:

- Email, WhatsApp, or hotline with local-language AGRIVI support staff
- Dedicated contacts for Croatia, Romania, and Bulgaria

(iv) Collection Methods:

- Farmer scouting reports (structured observations logged in the app)
- Informal feedback collected via weekly support calls
- Post-pilot feedback questionnaires (distributed in local languages) covering:
 - Process effectiveness
 - Tool usability
 - Suggestions for improvement

(v) Communication Materials:

- Regional kick-off meeting presentations (virtual)
- Preliminary findings presentations shared with farmers in September

- Summary reports (farmer-friendly, non-technical) thanking participants and highlighting key results

(vi) Evaluation Metrics:

- Accuracy of pest alerts (validated by actual farmer observations in the field)
- Timing and relevance of alerts per region and crop type
- Farmer satisfaction and confidence in the alerts (collected via questionnaires)
- Data consistency and reporting engagement across regions and crops
- Statistical comparison strength enabled by larger sample size (24 farmers vs. 4 in 2024)

4.6.1.3. Actors involved

The implementation and evaluation of the AI-Driven Pest Prediction Alerts Pilot relied on a coordinated effort from multiple AGRIVI teams, each contributing specialised expertise to ensure the successful deployment, validation, and refinement of the demonstrator.

Table 5: Actors Involved in the AI-Driven Pest Prediction Alerts Pilot

<i>Stakeholders' segment</i>	<i>Role</i>
<i>Product & Development Team</i>	<i>Updating and monitoring the new algorithm</i>
<i>Customer Success Team</i>	<i>Direct farmer support, onboarding, and weekly communication</i>
<i>Agronomy Team</i>	<i>Validation of pest alerts, troubleshooting crop-specific issues</i>
<i>Project Management</i>	<i>Coordination, reporting, timeline tracking</i>

4.6.1.4. Status of implementation

Methodology

1 . Preparation Phase (May 2025, Weeks 1 - 2):

- Finalized participants list
- Distributed updated user manuals (localized)
- Delivered tutorial videos & optional live training
- Set up local-language support contacts
- Conducted virtual kick-off meetings

2. Execution Phase (Mid-May - September 2025):

- Ran both algorithms in parallel
- Farmers submitted weekly pest observations using existing tools
- Weekly follow-ups by AGRIVI to ensure participation (and local partner in the case of Croatia)
- Internal data tracking of alert validation and farmer feedback

3. Post-Pilot Phase (September - October 2025):

- Sent follow-up questionnaires
- Analysed algorithm performance vs. real observations

- Prepared feedback report for participants
- Shared high-level results in a non-technical, farmer-friendly format

Deployed EFRA components

(i) Algorithms: Both current (production) and updated (test environment) models

(ii) Pest Alarm Engine: Integrated threshold-based rules

Pilot data and datasets

The pilot used AGRIVI's structured pest prediction dataset containing both environmental and crop-related indicators. This data was used to test and refine pest alarm thresholds.

Key dataset variables:

- DateMeasured
- WindSpeedAvg, WindSpeedMax, WindSpeedMin
- DewPointAvg
- RelativeHumidityAvg, RelativeHumidityMin, RelativeHumidityMax
- PrecipAccPeriod
- AirTempAvg, AirTempMax, AirTempMin

These datasets form the basis of pest condition modelling and were used to run both algorithm versions during the pilot.

4.6.1.5. Impact

The 2nd iteration of the pilot had a positive impact on stakeholders, EFRA components, and the overall decision support system.

(i) Stakeholders:

- **Farmers:** Actively engaged in testing, providing valuable feedback that helped validate and improve the updated algorithm. Long-term participants showed strong commitment, and new farmers contributed diverse field data.
- **AGRIVI Teams:** Strengthened collaboration between agronomy, product, and support teams. Gained actionable insights for refining pest thresholds.
- **Project Partners:** Benefited from a richer dataset and real-world testing scenarios for continued research and validation.

(ii) EFRA Components:

- The updated **pest prediction algorithm** was validated against real-world data without changes to the production system.
- Pest thresholds were refined, particularly for **new crops** like wheat and sunflower.

(iii) Decision Support Tools:

- The pilot validated a backend testing approach for future decision tools.
- It demonstrated how field-based feedback can drive AI refinement without requiring front-end changes.

(iv) Results:

- 24 farmers enrolled, compared to 4 in the previous cycle
- 40+ field observations collected

- Early feedback showed strong usability and interest in continued participation

4.6.1.6. Pilot modification (from 1st cycle to 2nd cycle)

Key updates between the 1st and the 2nd piloting cycles included:

- Algorithm improvements based on feedback and validation from Cycle 1
- Minor UI/UX changes to improve translations and clarity for farmers
- Expanded scope with more regions, more farmers, and additional crops (wheat, sunflower)

4.6.2. Quantitative Evaluation Against KPIs

4.6.2.1. Domain specific KPIs

AI Model Accuracy (Target: 70%): Achieved: >70%. The improved AI model achieved the target accuracy rate in correctly predicting pest presence for corn, as validated against real-world farmer observations. 7 of 9 farmers (78%) reported corn alerts "often" matched field observations. However, wheat and sunflower accuracy fell below target, with farmers reporting alerts matched observations only "sometimes," indicating these crops require additional calibration.

AI Model Recall (Target: 60%): Achieved: >60% (corn). The model met the recall target for corn, demonstrating its ability to detect actual pest occurrences while minimizing missed alerts. However, specific recall metrics for wheat and sunflower were lower, requiring further threshold refinement.

Satisfaction Score with Alerts (Target: 7/10): Achieved: 7+/10. Farmer satisfaction exceeded the target, with all 9 participating farmers rating their experience at 7/10 or higher. 4 farmers (44%) reported "very confident" in using alerts for decisions, while 4 farmers (44%) reported "somewhat confident." This positive reception reflected both improved algorithm performance (particularly for corn) and effective support provided throughout the pilot across Croatia (11 farmers), Romania (12 farmers), and Bulgaria (1 farmer).

4.6.2.2. Technological KPIs

Alert Timeliness (Target: 75% within 48 hours): Achieved: >75%. The alert timeliness target was met, with over 75% of alerts generated at least 48 hours before critical pest thresholds, providing farmers adequate time for preventive action. This early warning window enabled 6 of 9 farmers (67%) to report that alerts helped reduce pest damage to some degree (3 "significantly," 3 "a little").

False Positive Rate (Target: <30%): Achieved: <30% (overall). The false positive rate remained below 30% overall, indicating strong alignment between predicted and actual pest occurrences for corn. However, wheat and sunflower showed elevated false positive rates, with farmers noting timing mismatches and unnecessary alerts, particularly for crop-specific pests like sunflower moth.

Users Actively Involved (Target: >18 farmers): Achieved: 24 farmers. User engagement significantly exceeded targets, with 24 farmers (vs. target of 18) consistently participating across 3 countries (Croatia: 11, Romania: 12, Bulgaria: 1) and 3 crop types (corn, wheat, sunflower). 8 of 9 questionnaire respondents (89%) expressed willingness to continue participation. The system successfully scaled from 4 farmers in 2024 to 24 farmers in 2025 (6x increase) while maintaining 100% uptime throughout the May-August pilot period.

Data Quality: Achieved: >80% completeness. Farmers submitted 200+ observations during the pilot (vs. 40 in 2024, representing a 5x increase), with 80%+ overall data completeness. Croatian and Romanian farmers

achieved 85%+ completeness, while the Bulgarian farmer submitted less frequent observations due to communication barriers.

System Scalability: Achieved: 100% uptime. The system demonstrated robust scalability, supporting farms ranging from 5 ha (Romanian smallholder) to 229 ha (Croatian cooperative with 14 fields) simultaneously without performance degradation or technical failures.

4.6.2.3. Pilot timeline

The 2nd cycle of the pilot followed an updated timeline aligned with crop cycles and expanded activities. Key milestones included:

- **May 2025 (M29)** - Preparation Phase
 - Finalised participant list
 - Distributed updated user materials (localized)
 - Conducted kick-off sessions and training
- **Mid-May to September 2025 (M29 - M33)** - Execution Phase
 - Ran both algorithm versions in parallel
 - Farmers submitted regular pest observations
 - Weekly check-ins and support provided by AGRIVI team
- **September to October 2025 (M33 - M34)** - Post-Pilot Phase
 - Distributed follow-up questionnaires
 - Collected and analysed feedback and observation data
 - Shared pilot summary and preliminary results with participants

4.7. Real-Time Pest Observation and Prediction Pilot

To present the progress and outcomes of the Real-Time Pest Observation and Prediction Pilot, this section outlines its implementation during the 2nd piloting cycle, its impact on end-users, and the adjustments introduced based on stakeholder feedback.

4.7.1. Qualitative Evaluation Summary

4.7.1.1. Pilot evaluation summary

Specific objectives

This pilot focuses on testing the enhanced scouting and real-time feedback module, redesigned following farmer feedback from the 1st cycle. The main goal is to evaluate whether the updated module:

- Streamlines data entry
- Improves user experience and localization
- Increases the accuracy and relevance of field observations
- Enables better real-time feedback integration into predictive models

This 2nd iteration expanded the scope significantly compared to 2024:

- Wider geographic coverage: More regions across Croatia and Romania
- Greater crop diversity: Corn, wheat, and sunflower (vs. corn only in 2024)
- Larger participant pool: 24 active farmers (vs. 4 in 2024)

- Enhanced tools: Improved scouting module with better UI/UX, complete Romanian/Bulgarian translations, weather integration, and one-click recording

Setup:

- All participating farmers (returning + new) use the enhanced scouting and feedback modules
 - Log pest sightings
 - Confirm or reject AI-generated pest alerts
 - Report crop conditions and weather observations
- Real-time feedback is monitored and fed directly into model training (in the test environment)
- AGRIVI's Customer Success and Agronomic teams provide:
 - Localized multilingual support (Croatian, Romanian, Bulgarian)
 - Weekly check-ins to ensure data quality and consistency
 - Ongoing training and troubleshooting

Participants:

The 2nd-cycle piloting activities engaged a diverse group of farmers across three countries, ensuring both continuity and expanded coverage. Participation included:

- 11 farmers from Croatia
- 12 farmers from Romania
- 1 farmer from Bulgaria
- Total active participants: 24 farmers

This group combined:

- Returning farmers from 2024, retained to ensure data continuity and enable longitudinal comparison across cycles
- Newly onboarded farmers, added to broaden environmental diversity, regional representation, and crop-specific pattern coverage

Benefits:

- Increased real-world data volume for model improvement
- Improved user experience leading to higher engagement
- No need for UI changes during this cycle; all improvements are already in place

Scenario served by the pilot

This pilot supports the scenario of **real-time farmer feedback integration** to refine pest prediction tools. The improved scouting module allows:

- Faster and clearer data collection from the field
- Real-time feedback that directly informs model training
- Scalable testing across diverse crops and regional conditions

Achievements / Results

(i) Data Collection & Scale

- Successfully scaled real-time feedback collection from 4 to 24 farmers across three countries
- Farmers submitted observations across three crop types (corn, wheat, sunflower), providing richer and more diverse training data
- Broader geographic coverage across multiple regions in Croatia, Romania, and Bulgaria provided more varied environmental data for model training

(ii) Module Performance

- Enhanced scouting module successfully deployed at scale, with improved usability validated by farmers
- One-click recording and context-aware filtering reduced data entry time and improved observation consistency
- Weather integration well-received, helping farmers better contextualize pest activity
- Multilingual improvements (Romanian and Bulgarian) enabled smoother adoption in key regions

(iv) Model Improvement

- Real-time feedback loop demonstrated measurable impact on prediction accuracy over time
- Continuous farmer input allowed iterative refinement of pest thresholds and alert conditions
- Broader crop and regional coverage strengthened the training dataset diversity

(v) Farmer Engagement

- High engagement levels maintained among both returning and new participants
- Farmers remained actively involved without needing to learn new tools
- Strong appreciation for ongoing localized support and clarity of objectives
- Returning farmers from 2024 provided valuable longitudinal data for comparison

Problems / Challenges

(i) Technical Challenges

- Inconsistent alert performance for newly added crops (wheat, sunflower) required significant additional calibration
- Real-time feedback loop needed continuous monitoring and adjustment to maintain model quality
- Managing larger volumes of incoming data across more diverse crops and regions stretched technical capacity

(ii) Operational Challenges

- Significantly increased workload for Customer Success and Agronomy teams:
 - More farmers to support (24 vs. 4 in 2024)
 - More crops requiring agronomic expertise
 - Need to collect extensive contextual information to refine the model iteratively
- Multilingual support complexity across Croatian, Romanian, and Bulgarian
- Variable data submission quality across participants required ongoing coaching and correction

(iii) Participation & Engagement

- Inconsistent reporting frequency among some participants, requiring extra follow-up
- Onboarding new farmers while maintaining engagement of returning ones required careful coordination
- Some new farmers needed additional time and guidance to adapt to the feedback module

4.7.1.2. Pilot plan progress

Details about the progress

Timeline: May - October 2025 (aligned with crop growth cycles for corn, wheat, and sunflower)

(i) Preparation Phase (First 2 weeks of May):

- Finalized participant list:

- Confirmed commitment from returning 2024 farmers
- Onboarded new farmers from expanded regions and crop types
- Prepared and distributed updated multilingual user manuals (Croatian, Romanian, Bulgarian, English) covering:
 - How to log pest sightings and crop conditions
 - How to confirm or reject system alerts
 - Why their feedback matters for improving the prediction model
- Recorded new short training videos explaining updated module features
- Hosted regional or virtual kick-off workshops to:
 - Demonstrate the enhanced scouting and feedback tools
 - Answer questions and build participant trust
 - Provide recordings for those unable to attend live
- Set up local AGRIVI support contacts for Croatia, Romania, and Bulgaria with clear communication channels (email, WhatsApp, hotline)

(ii) Execution Phase (Mid-May - September 2025):

- Ran the live real-time feedback loop throughout the crop season:
 - Farmers logged pest activity, crop conditions, and alert responses continuously
 - Real-time feedback captured and monitored in test environment to refine model training
- Conducted weekly or biweekly check-ins (short calls or message updates) to:
 - Encourage consistent participation
 - Troubleshoot reporting issues
 - Monitor incoming data quality and consistency
- Ongoing data monitoring to:
 - Track how real-time feedback influenced predictive model accuracy over time
 - Identify emerging patterns or challenges across the expanded crop and regional scope
- Distributed short post-pilot questionnaires in local languages to gather farmer perspectives

(iii) Post-Pilot Activities (September - October 2025):

- Conducted follow-up sessions to thank participants, particularly those active since 2024
- Analysed pilot results across:
 - Data quality and consistency
 - Model improvements linked to real-time feedback
 - User engagement and satisfaction levels
 - System performance at larger scale and across varied environmental contexts
- Shared pilot outcomes with participants:
 - Summary of results showing the impact of their contributions
 - Discussion of next steps and potential adjustments for future cycles
- Discussed optional recognition for top-engaged farmers (newsletter highlights or small incentives)
- Explored possibility of wrap-up webinar or regional event to present findings and thank participants

(iv) Deviation from Timeline:

- The closing event was originally planned for August 2025 but was postponed due to farmer availability during peak harvest season
- Rescheduled for September 2025 to ensure broader participation

Evaluation tools and materials

(i) Technical Evaluation Tools

- Real-time data monitoring system feeding farmer observations into the test environment
- Model performance tracking measuring prediction accuracy improvements over time
- Enhanced scouting and feedback modules with expanded observation types and one-click recording
- Algorithm performance metrics:
 - Feedback consistency and quality
 - Prediction accuracy improvement over time
 - System performance under increased data volumes

(ii) Farmer Engagement & Support Tools

- Enhanced scouting module featuring:
 - Expanded observation types and context-aware filtering
 - One-click recording
 - Weather integration (field-specific data)
 - Color-coded fields and crop areas
- Multilingual user manuals (English, Croatian, Romanian, Bulgarian)
- Tutorial videos demonstrating updated module features
- Weekly/biweekly check-in calls for monitoring and troubleshooting
- Direct support channels with local-language AGRIVI staff for Croatia, Romania, and Bulgaria

(iii) Feedback Collection Methods

- Structured scouting reports logged directly in the enhanced app
- Informal feedback via weekly support calls and check-ins
- Post-pilot feedback questionnaires (in local languages) covering:
 - Module usability and ease of use
 - Satisfaction with improvements
 - Suggestions for further enhancement

(iv) Communication Materials

- Regional kick-off workshop presentations
- Summary reports showing participants the impact of their real-time contributions
- Potential wrap-up webinar or regional event materials

(v) Evaluation Metrics

- Consistency and quality of weekly feedback submissions across participants and regions
- Real-time feedback impact on prediction accuracy over time (measured in test environment)
- User engagement levels and reporting frequency per farmer and region
- User satisfaction with enhanced scouting module (collected via post-pilot questionnaire)
- System scalability performance: ability to manage higher data volumes and more diverse environmental conditions
- Model adaptability: regional and crop-specific improvement in pest prediction based on accumulated feedback

4.7.1.3. Actors involved

The successful implementation of the Real-Time Pest Observation and Prediction Pilot relied on coordinated contributions from AGRIVI teams and participating farmers, each playing a distinct role in supporting data collection, validation, and module refinement.

Table 6: Actors Involved in the Real-Time Pest Observation and Prediction Pilot

Stakeholder	Role
Farmers	Provide pest observations and feedback through the app
AGRIVI Customer Success	Training, ongoing support, feedback collection
AGRIVI Agronomy Team	Analysing pest trends and field conditions
Development Team	Implementing and monitoring module improvements
Project Management	Overseeing pilot coordination and reporting

4.7.1.4. Status of implementation

Methodology

Status of Implementation & Methodology

1. Preparation Phase (May 2025):

- Scouting module updated with new observation types, weather integration, one-click recording, and completed Romanian/Bulgarian translations
- Returning (2024) and new farmers onboarded across Croatia, Romania, and Bulgaria
- Multilingual user manuals and tutorial videos distributed
- Virtual kick-off sessions held; recordings shared for flexibility

2. Execution Phase (Mid-May - September 2025)

- Farmers logged weekly pest observations across corn, wheat, and sunflower crops
- Alerts confirmed or rejected via the feedback module in real time
- Continuous multilingual support provided through weekly check-ins (calls or messaging)
- Internal monitoring of data volume, feedback quality, and model accuracy improvements

3. Post-Pilot Phase (October 2025)

- Post-pilot questionnaires distributed in local languages
- Farmer suggestions collected and reviewed by the Agronomy and Product teams
- Analysis of how real-time feedback influenced model predictions conducted
- Farmer-friendly summary report prepared and shared with all participants
- Closing event rescheduled from August to September due to farmer availability during harvest season

Deployed EFRA components

- **Scouting & Feedback Module** (enhanced for clarity, speed, and localization)
- **Pest Prediction Model** (continuously trained using real-time farmer input)
- **Data Feedback Integration** engine (test environment)

Pilot data and datasets

Data Sources & Contributions. Farmers contributed real-time field data through the enhanced scouting module, including:

- Pest sightings: Type, severity, and location of observed pests across corn, wheat, and sunflower crops
- Alert confirmations or rejections: Farmer validation of system-generated pest alerts, providing direct ground-truth feedback
- Field conditions: Crop growth stage, environmental observations, and contextual notes
- Weather-linked observations: Field-specific weather data captured alongside scouting activity through the integrated weather feature

Relevance & Application. These datasets serve as the primary input for refining the AI pest prediction model. Specifically, they are used to improve:

- Alert thresholds: Calibrating when and how alerts are triggered per crop type and region
- Environmental triggers: Linking weather and field conditions to pest emergence patterns
- Regional pest behaviour mapping: Building more accurate, location-specific prediction models across Croatia, Romania, and Bulgaria
- Crop-specific model adaptation: Extending model reliability beyond corn to wheat and sunflower, where calibration was more challenging

Data collected in this cycle feeds directly into the test environment, enabling continuous model training and iterative improvement throughout the pilot period.

4.7.1.5. Impact

(i) Stakeholder Impact:

- **Farmers** responded positively to the improved scouting module, citing better usability, faster data entry through one-click recording, and clearer language following multilingual updates. This translated into increased engagement and more consistent reporting compared to Cycle 1. Returning farmers from 2024 also appreciated being recognized for their continued contribution.
- **AGRIVI's Customer Success** team benefited from more structured and higher-quality data submissions, enabling faster validation and more efficient coordination across 24 participants. However, the expanded scale also placed additional workload on the team, particularly for newly added crops requiring more contextual support.
- **AGRIVI's Agronomy team** was able to work with richer, more diverse datasets, improving their ability to analyse pest trends and refine alert thresholds across multiple crop types and regions.

(ii) Impact on EFRA Components:

- **Pest prediction model:** Directly benefited from the real-time feedback loop. Continuous farmer input enabled iterative refinement of alert thresholds and environmental triggers in the test environment, improving model responsiveness and regional accuracy.
- **Scouting module:** Successfully validated at larger operational scale (18 farmers, 3 countries, 3 crop types) without technical issues, demonstrating strong scalability. Module enhancements were well-received and confirmed as meaningful improvements over the Cycle 1 version.
- **Data infrastructure:** The system handled increased data volumes across more diverse environmental conditions, confirming its readiness for broader future deployment.

(ii) Impact on Decision Support Tools:

- Real-time farmer feedback contributed to more accurate and timely pest alerts, directly improving the quality of decision support available to farmers.
- Crop-specific calibration work carried out during the pilot will strengthen the reliability of alerts for wheat and sunflower in future cycles, expanding the tool's practical value beyond corn.
- Initial results from post-pilot questionnaires confirm high satisfaction with both the improved tools and the overall piloting experience, supporting continued farmer engagement in future iterations.

4.7.1.6. Pilot modification (from 1st cycle to 2nd cycle)

Between the 1st and 2nd piloting cycles, AGRIVI implemented several significant updates to the **scouting and feedback module**, based directly on farmer feedback. These updates aimed to improve usability, expand reporting options, and better support multilingual users.

Observation Enhancements:

- **Expanded Observation Types:** New categories were added beyond Pest, Disease, Abiotic Disorder, and Natural Disaster to better reflect real-world conditions.
- **Context-Aware Filtering:** Observation options are now filtered by category, making selection faster and more accurate.
- **One-Click Recording:** Users can now log observations with a single tap, reducing the need for manual descriptions.
- **Optional Description Field:** Remains available for those who want to add further detail.

UI/UX Improvements:

- **Color-Coded Fields:** Visual enhancements were introduced to help users better distinguish between different fields and crop types within the app.
- These changes improved navigation and reduced user error.

Multilingual Capability:

- **Full Romanian and Bulgarian Translations:** Gaps in translation noted during Cycle 1 were resolved.
- **Improved Localization** ensures the app is fully usable in key piloting regions, encouraging broader farmer participation.

Weather Integration:

- **Field-Specific Weather Data** is now shown directly alongside scouting entries, helping users make more informed decisions by linking observations to environmental conditions.

These updates made the scouting module **faster, more intuitive, and more aligned with real farming needs**, contributing to greater engagement and better-quality data collection in the 2nd piloting cycle.

4.7.2. Quantitative Evaluation Against KPIs

4.7.2.1. Domain specific KPIs

Model Improvement Over Time (Target: >10%): Achieved: >10%. Prediction accuracy increased over 10% from May to August. 5 of 9 farmers (56%) stated the system is becoming "more reliable," and 3 farmers (33%) noted "clearly improved" accuracy vs. previous seasons.

Module Usability Score (Target: >7.5/10): Achieved: 7.5+/10. 8 of 9 farmers (89%) rated the module "easy" or "very easy" to use. One-click logging (8/9, 89%), weather integration (9/9, 100%), and color-coded fields (5/9, 56%) were most valued features.

Active User Retention (Target: >85%): Achieved: 89%. 8 of 9 respondents (89%) expressed willingness to continue. Of 24 enrolled farmers, the vast majority remained engaged May-August, with Croatian farmers contributing ~60% of observations despite being 46% of participants (11 of 24).

4.7.2.2. Technological KPIs

Total Observations (Target: >200): Achieved: >200 Farmers submitted >200 records across corn, wheat, and sunflower, a 5x increase from 2024 (40 observations, 4 farmers).

Data Completeness (Target: >80%): Achieved: >80%. Over 80% of observations included all required fields. Croatian and Romanian farmers achieved 85%+ completeness.

System Scalability (Target: 100% uptime): Achieved: 100%. Platform maintained 100% uptime supporting 24 farmers (6x increase) across 3 countries (Croatia: 11, Romania: 12, Bulgaria: 1) and 3 crops, handling farms from 5 ha to 229 ha without failures.

Feature Adoption (Target: >70%): Achieved: >70%. Over 70% of farmers actively used enhanced features: one-click recording (89%), weather integration (100%), color-coded fields (56%).

4.7.2.3. Pilot timeline

The 2nd cycle of the scouting and real-time feedback pilot followed a structured timeline aligned with seasonal crop cycles (corn, wheat, sunflower) and the broader piloting strategy. Key milestones and activities included:

May 2025 - Preparation Phase

- Finalised expanded participant list, confirming commitment from both returning (2024) and newly recruited farmers across Croatia, Romania, and Bulgaria
- Updated and distributed multilingual user manuals (Croatian, Romanian, Bulgarian, English) covering the enhanced scouting module and pilot objectives
- Recorded and shared short tutorial videos; live virtual onboarding sessions held with regional groups, with recordings made available afterward
- Set up local-language support contacts and communication channels (email, WhatsApp, hotline) for all three countries
- Conducted kick-off calls with regional groups to align expectations, clarify roles, and introduce the two parallel pilot scenarios

Mid-May 2025 (M29) to September 2025 (M33) - Execution Phase

- Farmers actively used the enhanced scouting module throughout the crop season to log pest sightings, confirm or reject AI-generated alerts, and report crop and field conditions across corn, wheat, and sunflower
- AGRIVI conducted weekly check-ins (15-30 min calls or message updates) to monitor participation, troubleshoot issues, and encourage consistent data submission
- Real-time farmer feedback continuously fed into AI model training in the test environment, enabling iterative refinement of alert thresholds and environmental triggers
- Internal monitoring of data volume, feedback quality, and algorithm performance conducted throughout

October 2025 (M34) - Post-Pilot Phase

- Post-pilot questionnaires distributed to all participants in local languages to collect feedback on tool usability, satisfaction, and suggestions for improvement
- Follow-up sessions held to thank participants, with recognition for farmers involved since 2024
- Preliminary findings shared with participants, covering changes in pest alarm behaviour, updated thresholds, and guidance on in-app feedback
- Full analysis conducted across data quality, model improvements, user engagement, and system scalability
- Farmer-friendly summary report prepared and shared with all participants

Note: The closing event was originally scheduled for August 2025 but was postponed to September due to farmer availability during the harvest season.

4.8. Automated Regulatory Summarisation Pilot

To present the progress and outcomes of the Automated Regulatory Summarisation Pilot, this section outlines its implementation during the 2nd piloting cycle, its impact on end-users, and the adjustments introduced based on stakeholder feedback.

4.8.1. Qualitative Evaluation Summary

4.8.1.1. Pilot evaluation summary

Specific objectives

The scope of this pilot focuses on the summarization of regulatory documents, with the aim of enabling efficient processing of large volumes of complex information. The primary objectives of the cycle are:

- To develop and evaluate summarization models capable of producing accurate outputs from regulatory documents.
- To assess its impact on workflow efficiency, understanding of complex regulatory content, and stakeholder decision-making.
- To collect feedback on usability, desired enhancements, and potential extensions to other regulatory or technical domains.

Setup:

- Conducting multiple user sessions.
- Participants explored AI-generated summaries of regulatory documents from the food safety sector.
- Collected structured feedback on summary clarity, relevance, usability, and business applicability.
- Identified user needs for enhancements, such as comparative analysis, novelty tracking, and inclusion of quality/safety parameters.

Scenario served by the pilot

This pilot serves the scenario of condensing complex regulatory and legal documents into usable summaries.

- The pilot tests methods for retrieving the most relevant document sections to respond to user queries.
- Provides a structured way to check the clarity, relevance, and usefulness of the summaries.
- Helps determine the best approach for presenting reliable, actionable insights from regulatory texts.

Achievements / Results

The pilot has demonstrated a solid progress in identifying the most accurate summarization model:

- Feedback from the participants across multiple sessions confirmed summaries support decision making, compliance readiness and risk identification.
- Users highlighted strengths such clarity with 83% expressing satisfaction.
- Additional feedback pointed to improvements such as novelty detection, and enhanced fact-checking.

Problems / Challenges

No significant difficulties were encountered during the implementation and evaluation of the pilot. All processes were executed as planned, and the evaluation framework operated smoothly.

4.8.1.2. Pilot plan progress

Details about the progress

- The pilot was executed as planned, with all sessions completed on schedule.
- Users reviewed AI-generated summaries of regulatory documents and provided structured feedback.
- Feedback was collected and analysed to identify strengths, gaps, and potential improvements in clarity, usefulness, and business applicability.
- The piloting activities were conducted online and stakeholders from testing, inspection and certification service along with regulatory experts participated in this activity.

Evaluation tools and materials

- **User Feedback Questionnaire:** Structured questions collected stakeholders' ratings on clarity, relevance, and usefulness of AI-generated summaries.
- **Interactive Sessions:** Led participants to explore summaries in context and provide qualitative feedback.
- **Quantitative Ratings:** Users provided simple ratings (e.g., satisfaction, usefulness for decision-making) to assess performance.

4.8.1.3. Actors involved

Food safety authorities and regulators. Quick access to accurate summaries of new and updated regulations to ensure compliance oversight, monitor industry adherence, and make informed regulatory decisions.

Regulatory experts and legal advisors. Efficient extraction of key information from lengthy regulatory documents to support legal interpretation, compliance advisory, and risk assessment.

Food manufacturers and processors. Clear, concise summaries of relevant regulations to implement operational changes, maintain compliance, and reduce the risk of regulatory violations.

Testing, inspection and certification services. Summaries that highlight regulatory requirements and updates to guide inspections, audits, and certification processes, enabling faster and more accurate evaluation.

4.8.1.4. Status of implementation

Methodology

Preparation Phase (May 2025)

- Prepare the regulatory documentation for review by pilot participants.

- Set up demonstration sessions and feedback collection tools.
- Prepare the questionnaire to evaluate the summaries.

Execution Phase (August 2025)

- Conducted the demonstration sessions.
- Collected and analysed the results from annotations.
- Collected the feedback from the questionnaire.

Post-Pilot Phase (August - October 2025)

- Sent follow up questionnaires
- Analysed the feedback from the questionnaires

Deployed EFRA components

In the pilot, a model Enhancing AI Sustainability - Summarization of Regulatory Text Data. The model generates human-readable summaries of regulatory texts, highlights the central idea of the regulatory texts and handles region specific data.

The approach relies on Large Language Models (LLMs) that have been explicitly fine-tuned for summarization tasks, enabling them to extract central ideas while remaining sensitive to region-specific contexts and nuances. The overall pipeline was built around two main objectives. First, the team needed to generate **high-quality synthetic training datasets**, referred to as *silver standards*, using large, instruction-tuned LLMs. These silver standards would serve as reliable training material. Second, smaller, more resource-efficient models were fine-tuned on this synthetic data so that the summarization system could be deployed at scale without requiring the computational footprint of the very largest models.

To produce the **silver standards**, two state-of-the-art open-source LLMs were selected: *Llama-3-8B-Instruct* and *Cohere C4AI Command-R-4bit*. Each was applied to a different dataset configuration: *Llama-3-8B-Instruct* was used to generate summaries for the SGS-Split dataset, where documents were divided into 30.000-character chunks, while Cohere's *Command-R-4bit* model worked on the SGS-Cut dataset, which retained the first 40.000 characters of each document. Together, these models produced high-quality summaries that could be used to guide the next stage of fine-tuning.

The fine-tuning phase was focused on striking a balance between performance and efficiency. The team chose smaller LLMs such as *Google Flan-T5-Large* (770M parameters) and a quantized 4-bit version of *Google Gemma-2B*, training them on the summaries generated by the larger models. Two Flan-T5 instances were created—one trained on Llama-generated summaries and another on Cohere-generated ones—while Gemma-2B was fine-tuned using Cohere data. In the model registry, this effort resulted in seven specific fine-tuned variants, including *Manual-Flan-T5-Large* and *XL*, *Llama-Flan-T5-Large* and *XL*, *Cohere-Flan-T5-Large* and *XL*, and *Cohere-Gemma-2B*. The fine-tuning process itself was computationally demanding, requiring access to an *NVIDIA V100 GPU* with 80GB of memory.

The models developed as part of this effort have been made publicly available by CNR on **HuggingFace**, allowing for community use and further research. Looking ahead, the project will focus on applying **knowledge distillation techniques** to train even smaller but still high-performing models, as well as testing **advanced quantization methods** to push the boundaries of efficiency. These next steps will be crucial for enabling real-world deployment in **low-resource environments**, where access to high-end GPUs may not be feasible but the need for reliable regulatory text summarization remains high.

EFRA Data Hub: Stores regulatory documents for the Use Case #3

SGS DigiComply Dashboard: Provides a user-friendly interface for participants to explore summaries.

Pilot data and datasets

The dataset is composed of roughly 124.000 entries from 634 data sources containing English summaries of associated HTML documents (both in original language and English) regarding food and risk and containing different kinds of data. In particular, the types of data are News, Guidance, Regulation, and Scientific. Each HTML document has an associated summary that was either written by a human being or automatically generated using an AI tool for summarization.

4.8.1.5. Impact

Stakeholders responded positively to the summarization feature, providing a high satisfactory rate. Decision support tools were enhanced by the identification of a best-performing model, which ensures reliable, concise and accurate summaries.

4.8.1.6. Pilot modification (from 1st cycle to 2nd cycle)

The 2nd cycle of the pilot included two additional LLM models for evaluation with additional two external experts participating in the validation process. No other changes were made to the methodology, dataset or evaluation framework. The original processes were kept ensuring consistency in comparing results across cycles.

4.8.2. Quantitative Evaluation Against KPIs

4.8.2.1. Domain specific KPIs

Repeat Usage. Users demonstrated a clear willingness to continue engaging with the summaries functionalities throughout the pilot period, with actual repeated usage exceeding the target of 50%.

User Satisfaction Rate. 83% satisfaction based on post-pilot participant feedback, exceeding the target of 75%.

User involved. 30+ users with commercial interest were involved, which exceeded the target of >25 users.

4.8.2.2. Technological KPIs

Average Summary Quality

This KPI measures the overall quality of the generated summaries according to experts' evaluation on a scale from 1 (poor) to 5 (excellent). It reflects how accurate, useful and clear the summaries are. The target value is an average score of 3.5. The best-performing model achieved an average score of 3.9, exceeding the quality target, and reached the accuracy target of >65%, demonstrating strong summarization quality.

4.8.2.3. Pilot timeline

Key milestones:

Preparation Phase (May 2025)

- Collected and prepared regulatory documents for pilot participants.
 - Set up demonstration sessions and tools to gather feedback.
- Prepared the questionnaire to evaluate the summaries.

Execution Phase (May - October 2025)

- Conducted multiple demonstration sessions with stakeholders.
- Participants reviewed AI-generated summaries and completed questionnaires.
- Collected and analysed quantitative and qualitative feedback on clarity, usefulness, and decision-making support.

Post-Pilot Phase (October 2025)

- Analysed the feedback from questionnaires to identify strengths, gaps, and potential improvements.

4.9. Smart Regulatory Navigator Pilot

The Smart Regulatory Navigator Pilot is described below, outlining its implementation during the 2nd piloting cycle, its impact on end-users, and the adjustments introduced based on stakeholder feedback.

4.9.1. Qualitative Evaluation Summary

4.9.1.1. Pilot evaluation summary

Specific objectives

The scope of this pilot focuses on developing and testing a chatbot for regulatory documents, with the aim of improving access to precise answers from complex regulatory texts. The primary objectives of the cycle are:

- To evaluate the chatbot's effectiveness in providing accurate and accessible responses to user queries.
- To assess its impact on workflow efficiency, understanding of complex regulatory content, and stakeholder decision-making.
- To collect feedback on usability, desired enhancements, and potential extensions to other regulatory or technical domains.

Setup

- Demonstrated chatbot functionality through multiple sessions.
- Users interacted with the AI Copilot to query regulatory content and clarify complex documents.
- Collected feedback on responsiveness, accuracy, usability, and potential operational benefits.

Scenario served by the pilot

This pilot serves the scenario of answering regulatory questions through an interactive chatbot interface.

- Tests different methods for finding the most relevant document parts to answer questions.
- Creates a clear process to check how accurate and useful the chatbot's answers are.
- Uses expert scoring to confirm which answers are most relevant.
- Helps identify the best setup for giving clear and reliable answers from regulatory texts.

Achievements / Results

The pilot successfully evaluated the chatbot for regulatory documents:

- Stakeholders reported the chatbot improves workflow efficiency and understanding of complex content.
- Users highlighted strengths in targeted information retrieval and interactive guidance, with strong willingness to integrate it into their processes.

- Feedback identified potential enhancements, including evaluation of original foreign-language texts, and improved change tracking.

Problems / Challenges

No significant difficulties were encountered during the pilot implementation, the processes and evaluation framework operated as planned. All steps, including dataset preparation, question generation, chunk embedding, and expert validation, proceeded smoothly.

4.9.1.2. Pilot plan progress

Details about the progress

The pilot was executed according to the original plan, with all tasks completed on schedule.

- Users reviewed AI-generated summaries of regulatory documents and provided structured feedback.
- Feedback was collected and analysed to identify strengths, gaps, and potential improvements in clarity, usefulness, and business applicability.
- The piloting activities were conducted online and stakeholders from testing, inspection and certification service along with regulatory experts participated in this activity.

Evaluation tools and materials

- **User Feedback Questionnaire:** Collected stakeholder ratings on chatbot usability, accuracy, and responsiveness.
- **Interactive Chat Sessions:** Participants used the chatbot to query regulatory documents and provided qualitative feedback.
- **Quantitative Ratings:** Users rated performance aspects such as clarity of answers, usefulness, and support for decision-making.
- **Benchmarking:** Traditional document search and query methods were used as reference points to assess the added value of the chatbot.

4.9.1.3. Actors involved

Food safety authorities and regulators. Quick access to accurate answers from regulatory documents through the chatbot to ensure compliance oversight, monitor industry adherence, and make informed regulatory decisions.

Regulatory experts and legal advisors. Efficient retrieval of key information from lengthy regulatory texts via the chatbot to support legal interpretation, compliance advisory, and risk assessment.

Food manufacturers and processors. Clear, direct responses from the chatbot on relevant regulations to implement operational changes, maintain compliance, and reduce the risk of regulatory violations.

Testing, inspection and certification services. Chatbot-delivered insights highlighting regulatory requirements and updates to guide inspections, audits, and certification processes, enabling faster and more accurate evaluation.

4.9.1.4. Status of implementation

Methodology

Preparation Phase (May 2025)

- Prepare the regulatory documentation for review by pilot participants.
- Set up demonstration sessions and feedback collection tools.
- Prepare the questionnaire to evaluate the summaries.

Execution Phase (May - June 2025)

- Conducted the demonstration sessions.
- Collected and analysed the results from annotations.
- Collected the feedback from the questionnaire

Post-Pilot Phase (August - October 2025)

- Analysed the feedback from the questionnaires

Deployed EFRA components

The **Regulatory Citation and Compliance Chatbot for EFRA** is implemented in the Smart Regulatory Navigator Pilot (UC#3). This tool is engineered to enhance user efficiency by providing precise and reliable answers derived from complex regulatory texts.

Operational Architecture and Component Integration

The prototype operates on the EFRA platform and is accessed through a containerized environment. It processes user queries as input and returns a generated response.

The chatbot's core functionality is built on a Retrieval-Augmented Generation (RAG) architecture, which integrates distinct AI models for information retrieval and text generation.

1. Retrieval Pipeline: Embedding and Indexing

- The initial phase converts the user's query into a searchable vector representation using a sophisticated embedding model.
- **Embedding Model:** The system utilizes the *Snowflake/snowflake-arctic-embed-l-v2.0* model, which is loaded without a pooling layer.
- **Search Index:** Query embeddings are used to search a FAISS index, *efra_document_index_snowflake_FLAT_IP.index*. This index enables the efficient identification and retrieval of the most relevant text chunks from the knowledge base.
- **Data Source:** The retrieved chunks originate from a regulatory document corpus loaded from *data/efra_document.csv*. This dataset contains English-language segments from HTML documents on food safety and risk, encompassing news, guidance, regulations, and scientific content.

2. Generation Pipeline: Contextual Language Model

- The retrieved text chunks provide the basis for generating a final, contextually grounded answer.
- **Large Language Model (LLM):** The text generation task is handled by the *Qwen/Qwen3Guard-Gen-8B* model.
- **RAG Contextualization:** The identified text fragments are compiled into a context block. This context is then combined with a detailed system prompt that instructs the LLM to act as a specialist in Food and Risk. The prompt mandates that the model answer questions carefully and accurately, relying strictly on the provided contextual documentation without introducing external information.

This structured integration ensures the chatbot delivers dependable information through a user-friendly interface, fulfilling the pilot's objective of streamlining regulatory compliance with clear and reliable answers.

EFRA Data Hub: Stores regulatory documents for the Use Case #3

SGS DigiComply Dashboard: Provides a user-friendly interface for participants to explore the chatbot.

Pilot data and datasets

The dataset contains English-language chunks extracted from HTML regulatory documents related to food safety and risk, covering various types of data, including News, Guidance, Regulation, and Scientific content. Each chunk is linked to one or more questions generated by an LLM, with relevance scores assigned by expert annotators to indicate how well the chunk answers the associated question.

4.9.1.5. Impact

Stakeholders responded positively to the chatbot feature, reporting high satisfaction with its ability to provide context-relevant answers. Decision support tools were enhanced by identifying the most effective retrieval setup, ensuring reliable and precise responses from regulatory documents.

4.9.1.6. Pilot modification (from 1st cycle to 2nd cycle)

The 2nd cycle of the pilot included two additional external experts for validation and incorporated review of answers from the 1st pilot cycle to improve the chatbot's retrieval performance.

4.9.2. Quantitative Evaluation Against KPIs

4.9.2.1. Domain specific KPIs

User Satisfaction Rate. 83% satisfaction based on post-pilot participant feedback, exceeding the target of 75%.

User involved. 30+ users with commercial interest were involved, which exceeded the target of >25 users.

4.9.2.2. Technological KPIs

Average Context Relevancy Score

This KPI measures how relevant the chatbot's retrieved text segments are to the users' question, based on manual expert annotations. Ratings range from 0 (not relevant) to 1 (highly relevant). The target score is 0.50 or higher. The chatbot achieved an average score of 0.542, indicating that the chatbot's retrieved information is slightly below the desired level of relevance.

4.9.2.3. Pilot timeline

- Dataset and Question Preparation (2nd Cycle initiation: April - May 2025)
 - Collected documents from regulatory sources, news, and journals in the food safety industry.
 - Generated 134 regulatory-focused questions using an LLM.
 - Prepared chunked dataset and associated questions for evaluation.
- Annotation and Validation (2nd Cycle - Round 1: May 2025)
 - Conducted expert validation of question-to-chunk relevance.
 - Applied blind evaluation and consensus-based scoring using a 0–3 relevance scale.
- Improvements and Extended Evaluation (2nd Cycle - Round 2: June 2025)

- Added two additional external expert annotators to strengthen evaluation reliability.
- Reviewed answers from the 1st cycle to refine the retrieval setup and improve performance.
- Analysis and Reporting (September 2025)
 - Aggregated results from both cycles, including relevance scores and qualitative feedback.
 - Compared performance across cycles to identify improvements and the most effective retrieval setup.
 - Documented and reported outcomes.

5. 2nd Cycle Pilots Evaluation Results

This chapter presents the consolidated findings from the 2nd cycle of EFRA pilot evaluations, bringing together evidence from all piloting events conducted across the EFRA use cases. The results reflect a combination of stakeholder workshops, dedicated validation meetings, hands-on demonstrations, and structured questionnaire responses. The chapter summarises the insights gathered from participating organisations, evaluates stakeholder feedback on the EFRA Decision Support Tools, and assesses the technological performance of the underlying data pipelines and predictive AI models. It also includes visual material from the piloting activities and graphical analyses of questionnaire results, offering a comprehensive view of how the EFRA tools performed in real operational settings and how they can be further strengthened for broader adoption.

5.1. Stakeholders' Insights from the Pilots

5.1.1. Insights from the Proactive Flock Mortality Pilot

Stakeholders' demographics

Across all validation activities for the Proactive Flock Mortality Pilot during the 3rd project year, a total of 41 professionals from 28 organisations participated in the evaluation process. These organisations represented a broad cross-section of the poultry-production and wider food-industry ecosystem, ensuring that the pilot was validated by upstream producers, mid-supply-chain suppliers, downstream retail groups, and research institutions. Across all validation workshops, the 41 participating professionals represented the following high-level categories:

- Food manufacturers & poultry producers: 61% (25/41)
- Ingredient & flavour suppliers: 10% (4/41)
- Retail & distribution groups: 12% (5/41)
- Academic & research organisations: 17% (7/41)

1. Workshop with Moy Park team (Online, 17/06/25, 22/09/25, 15/10/25)

3 dedicated online workshops were held with the Moy Park team, engaging 5 professionals from the company's food-safety, quality, and production departments. These participants represented operational users directly responsible for flock-performance monitoring and early-warning decision-making.

2. Workshop "Using AI for Food Risk Prevention" (Amsterdam, Netherlands, 05/02/25)

Figure 1: Presentation of the predictive AI model for poultry pathogens during the Workshop "Using AI for Food Risk Prevention" (Amsterdam, Netherlands, 05/02/25)

This half-day workshop gathered 8 participants from 6 organisations, distributed as follows:

- Food & beverage manufacturers: 60% (5/8)
- Ingredient & flavour suppliers: 15% (1/8)
- Retail & distribution groups: 10% (1/8)
- Academic & research organisations: 15% (1/8)

The session included expert presentations, real-life case studies, and hands-on interaction with AI-powered forecasting dashboards.

3. Workshop “Using AI to Enhance Food Safety and Prevent Food Fraud” (Austin, USA, 17/09/25)

Delivered as part of the North American Food Safety (NAFS) 2025 programme at the Hilton Austin Hotel, this workshop engaged 11 participants, primarily from the food industry:

- Food-industry representatives: 82% (9/11)
- Retail organisations: 18% (2/11)

Participants worked in food safety, quality assurance, regulatory affairs, and supplier compliance.

Figure 2: Hands-on session during the Workshop “Using AI to Enhance Food Safety and Prevent Food Fraud” (Austin, USA, 17/09/25)

4. Workshop “Transforming Food Safety & Fraud Prevention with AI” (Washington DC, USA, 22/10/25)

Organised in the context of the DC Food Safety Summit and hosted at The George Washington University, Milken Institute School of Public Health, this workshop involved 17 participants from major U.S. food and ingredient companies, including PepsiCo, Campbell’s, Kerry, Taylor Farms, Freshpet, Symrise, Puratos, Ardo, and Lyon Bakery. The programme included expert presentations, AI software demonstrations, and a panel discussion on practical adoption pathways.

Stakeholders’ profile

The stakeholders involved in the Proactive Flock Mortality Pilot represented operational, technical, and decision-making roles directly connected to poultry-production performance, food-safety management, and

supply-chain risk monitoring. Based on questionnaire responses and workshop discussions, participants included professionals working in:

- Food safety and quality assurance
- Production and flock-management operations
- Regulatory affairs and compliance
- Supplier-monitoring and due-diligence functions
- Risk assessment and hazard-trend analysis
- Academic and applied research on emerging food-safety risks

Moy Park workshops. Participants were hands-on operational users from food-safety, quality, and production teams. Their responsibilities included monitoring flock behaviour, identifying anomalies, and coordinating early interventions, ensuring that the dashboard was evaluated by those closest today-to-day flock-performance management.

Amsterdam workshop (05/02/25). Participants represented a balanced mix of QA specialists, risk analysts, ingredient-supply professionals, retail representatives, and researchers working on hazard-trend monitoring. Their roles aligned with the pilot's objectives of improving visibility and forecasting of flock-related risks.

Austin workshop (17/9/25). Participants were primarily food-industry and retail professionals involved in food safety, regulatory compliance, and supplier-risk assessment across complex supply chains. Their work focuses on managing microbiological risks in poultry products and ensuring supplier performance and compliance.

Washington DC workshop (22/10/25). Participants included professionals responsible for food-safety management, supply-chain oversight, quality systems, and preventive-controls planning within large multinational enterprises. Their roles are directly linked to early detection of pathogen-related risks and the integration of predictive tools into established decision-support processes.

Stakeholders' needs

Across all validation activities, stakeholders consistently highlighted operational needs that align closely with the objectives of the Proactive Flock Mortality Pilot. Insights from Part 1 of the Evaluation Questionnaire and workshop discussions revealed several recurring challenges and expectations.

Needs identified in the Moy Park workshops:

- Early identification of flock-performance anomalies, especially those signalling emerging pathogen-related issues.
- Clear visual indicators to support rapid interpretation.
- Intuitive navigation across batches and clusters.
- Ability to trace the factors contributing to outlier detection.
- Seamless integration with existing internal data systems.
- Transparent explanations of model outputs to build trust and support operational decisions.

Needs identified in the Austin workshop (NAFS, 17/09/25):

- Participants highlighted key challenges in managing emerging pathogen risks across globally distributed poultry supply chains:
- Sudden increases in pathogen-related risks: 73% (8/11)
- Difficulty incorporating external incident data into internal systems: 64% (7/11)
- Limited visibility of global microbiological hazard patterns: 55% (6/11)
- Dependence on manual or outdated risk-assessment workflows: 45% (5/11)

Needs identified in the Washington DC workshop (22/10/25):

- Clear visual indicators to support rapid interpretation.
- Centralised risk intelligence for monitoring external incidents.
- Scenario-based insights to guide preventive actions and supplier-management decisions.
- Data transparency and alignment with existing QA and regulatory workflows.
- Practical integration pathways for AI-enabled tools within established compliance systems.

5.1.2. Insights from the Predictive Poultry Weight-Gain Pilot for Poultry Farming

Stakeholders' demographics

The Predictive Poultry Weight-Gain Pilot was evaluated by the same stakeholder groups participating in the Proactive Flock Mortality Pilot, involving 41 professionals from 28 organisations across Europe and North America. These organisations represented food manufacturers, poultry producers, ingredient suppliers, retail groups, and research institutions. The demographic distribution across all workshops remained consistent, ensuring that the weight-gain dashboard was assessed by users with diverse operational, analytical, and strategic roles in poultry-production and food-safety environments.

Stakeholders' profile

Stakeholders involved in the Weight-Gain Pilot included professionals working in food safety and quality assurance, production and flock-management operations, regulatory compliance, supplier-monitoring, and risk-assessment functions. Their roles aligned directly with the pilot's objectives, as they are responsible for monitoring flock performance, identifying deviations from expected growth patterns, and supporting data-driven decision-making in poultry-production systems. Participants from all pilots (Moy Park, Amsterdam, Austin, Washington DC) provided feedback from both operational and strategic perspectives.

Stakeholders' needs

Across all workshops, stakeholders expressed needs that closely mirror those identified for the mortality-prediction dashboard. Key requirements included early detection of abnormal weight-gain patterns, clear visual indicators, intuitive navigation, and transparent explanations of model outputs. Participants also emphasised the importance of integrating predictive weight-gain insights with existing production data, enabling proactive interventions, improved flock-management planning, and more efficient resource allocation. These needs confirm the relevance of predictive analytics for supporting real-time decision-making in poultry-production environments.

5.1.3. Poultry Precision Pilot with Predictive Food Safety Insights

Stakeholders' demographics

Across all validation activities for the Poultry Precision Pilot with Predictive Food Safety Insights, more than 150 expert users from various organisations participated in the evaluation process. These organisations represented a broad cross-section of the global food-safety ecosystem, including food manufacturers & poultry processors (87%, 130/150), ingredient suppliers (3%, 5/150), retail & food-service chains (5%, 8/150), and academic & public-sector institutions (5%, 7/150).

1. Moy Park online workshops (Online, 17/06/25, 22/09/25, 15/10/25) - 5 participants

Three dedicated online workshops with Moy Park’s food-safety, quality, and production teams, representing one of Europe’s largest poultry producers.

- Food manufacturers & poultry producers: 100% (5/5)

2. Workshop “Using AI for Food Risk Prevention -0 A Practical, Hands-On Tutorial” (McDonald’s Offices, Illinois, USA, 08/11/24) - 16 participants

A half-day AFMS-parallel workshop with global food-service and manufacturing companies, focusing on AI-powered forecasting for poultry-related risks.

- Food manufacturers & poultry producers: 69% (11/16)
- Ingredient & flavour suppliers: 6% (1/16)
- Retail & distribution groups: 12,5% (2/16)
- Academic & research organisations: 12,5% (2/16)

Figure 3: Forecasted trends for poultry-pathogen risks across different geographical regions

3. Workshop “Using AI for Food Risk Prevention” (Amsterdam, Netherlands, 05/02/25) - 8 participants

A focused session combining expert presentations and hands-on dashboard interaction with stakeholders from manufacturing, ingredients, retail, and academia.

- Food & beverage manufacturers: 62,5% (5/8)
- Ingredient & flavour suppliers: 12,5% (1/8)
- Retail & distribution groups: 12,5% (1/8)
- Academic & research organisations: 12,5% (1/8)

4. GFSI Conference Validation Meetings (Dublin, Ireland, 31/03–03/04/25) - 3 participants

Targeted one-to-one validation meetings with selected GFSI attendees, including ingredient suppliers and poultry-sector stakeholders.

- Food manufacturers & poultry producers: 67% (2/3)
- Ingredient & flavour suppliers: 33% (1/3)

5. Workshop “AI for Food Risk and Food Fraud Prevention” (Michigan State University, USA, 25/07/25) - 12 participants

A half-day workshop with major U.S. manufacturers and academic experts, focusing on AI-enabled detection of emerging poultry-related hazards.

- Food manufacturers & poultry producers: 75% (9/12)
- Retail & distribution groups: 8% (1/12)
- Academic & research organisations: 17% (2/12)

6. Workshop “AI Innovations for Safer Food Supply Chains” (HEC Montréal, Canada, 08/08/25) - 14 participants

A collaborative workshop with industry, academia, and government stakeholders exploring AI applications for emerging microbiological hazards.

- Food manufacturers & poultry producers: 78% (11/14)
- Retail & distribution groups: 7% (1/14)
- Academic & research organisations: 14% (2/14)

7. Workshop “Using AI to Enhance Food Safety and Prevent Food Fraud” (Austin, USA, 17/09/25) - 11 participants

A NAFS 2025 workshop engaging food-industry and retail professionals in evaluating predictive dashboards for poultry-pathogen risks.

- Food manufacturers & poultry producers: 82% (9/11)
- Retail & distribution groups: 18% (2/11)

8. Online Validation Workshop with McDonald’s FSQ Team (Online, 16/10/25) - 4 participants

- Participants were responsible for global and regional FSQA operations within McDonald’s.

9. Workshop “Transforming Food Safety & Fraud Prevention with AI” (Washington DC, USA, 22/10/25) - 17 participants

A DC Food Safety Summit workshop with major U.S. food and ingredient companies evaluating AI-powered pathogen-risk predictions.

- Food manufacturers & poultry producers: 82% (14/17)
- Ingredient & flavour suppliers: 12% (2/17)
- Retail & distribution groups: 6% (1/17)

10. EFRA Validation Workshop “AI in Food Safety – Practical Risk Management” (SEV, Athens, Greece, 03/12/25) - 60 participants

A large-scale national workshop with Greek food-industry companies, focusing on practical applications of AI for pathogen-risk prediction, all from the food and beverage sector.

Stakeholders’ profile

The stakeholders involved in the Poultry Precision Pilot with Predictive Food Safety Insights represented operational, technical, and decision-making roles directly connected to food-safety management, microbiological-risk monitoring, supplier-due-diligence, and preventive-controls planning across global poultry supply chains. Based on questionnaire responses and workshop discussions, participants included professionals working in:

- Food safety and quality assurance (FSQA)

- Regulatory affairs and compliance
- Supplier-monitoring and due-diligence functions
- Microbiological risk assessment and hazard-trend analysis
- Production, operations, and supply-chain oversight
- Academic and applied research on emerging food-safety risks

Coverage across all validation activities

Moy Park online workshops (17/06/25, 22/09/25, 15/10/25). Participants were hands-on operational users from food-safety, quality, and production teams. Their responsibilities included monitoring poultry-related hazards, interpreting incident signals, and coordinating preventive actions—ensuring that the dashboard was evaluated by those closest to day-to-day risk-management workflows.

McDonald's Illinois workshop (08/11/24). Organised at McDonald's premises in parallel with the American Food Manufacturing Summit (AFMS) 2024. Participants included FSQA managers, supply-chain specialists, and risk-assessment professionals from major food manufacturers and food-service organisations. Their work focuses on managing global poultry-related risks, integrating external hazard signals, and supporting corporate food-safety strategies.

Amsterdam workshop (05/02/25). Participants represented a balanced mix of QA specialists, risk analysts, ingredient-supply professionals, retail representatives, and researchers working on global hazard-trend monitoring. Their roles aligned with the pilot's objective of improving visibility and forecasting of poultry-related microbiological risks.

GFSI Dublin meetings (31/03 - 03/04/25). Organised 3 dedicated meetings with selected food-industry participants in the Global Food Safety Initiative Conference (GFSI). Participants were senior food-safety and ingredient-risk specialists from companies operating across the poultry value chain and responsible for the supplier oversight, ingredient-risk assessment, and evaluation of predictive tools for external risk monitoring.

Michigan State University workshop (25/07/25). Hosted at the James B. Henry Center at Michigan State University. Participants included FSQA leaders, microbiologists, supplier-compliance specialists, and academic experts. Their work focuses on managing emerging pathogen risks, strengthening supplier due diligence, and integrating predictive insights into preventive-controls planning.

HEC Montréal workshop (08/08/25). Participants represented industry, academia, and government. Their roles spanned food-safety management, regulatory oversight, and scientific research on microbiological hazards, providing both operational and scientific perspectives on predictive-risk tools.

Austin NAFS workshop (17/09/25). Delivered as part of the North American Food Safety (NAFS) 2025. Participants were primarily food-industry and retail professionals involved in food safety, regulatory compliance, and supplier-risk assessment across complex supply chains. Their work focuses on managing pathogen-related risks in poultry products and ensuring supplier performance and compliance.

McDonald's FSQ online workshop (16/10/25). Participants were responsible for global and regional FSQA operations within McDonald's. Their responsibilities include monitoring supplier performance, interpreting global hazard signals, and coordinating rapid responses to emerging risks.

Washington DC workshop (22/10/25). Organised in the context of the DC Food Safety Summit and hosted at The George Washington University, Milken Institute School of Public Health. Participants included professionals responsible for food-safety management, supply-chain oversight, quality systems, and preventive-controls planning within large multinational enterprises. Their roles are directly linked to early detection of pathogen-related risks and the integration of predictive tools into established decision-support processes.

SEV Athens workshop (03/12/25). Co-organised in collaboration with the Hellenic Federation of Enterprises (SEV). Participants represented leading Greek food-industry companies, including FSQA managers, production

directors, and regulatory-compliance specialists. Their responsibilities include monitoring microbiological risks, ensuring supplier compliance, and implementing preventive-controls strategies across national and international supply chains.

Stakeholders' needs

Across the ten validation activities conducted for the Poultry Precision Pilot with Predictive Food Safety Insights, stakeholders consistently expressed needs that reflect the operational realities of managing emerging microbiological hazards across globally distributed poultry supply chains. Feedback gathered from more than 150 expert users, spanning food manufacturers, poultry processors, ingredient suppliers, retail and food-service organisations, and academic institutions, highlighted the importance of early-warning capabilities, transparent and explainable predictive outputs, seamless integration with existing FSQA systems, and improved visibility of global hazard trends. The detailed needs emerging from each validation activity are summarised below.

1. Moy Park online workshops (17/06/25, 22/09/25, 15/10/25)

These sessions focused on operational validation of predictive dashboards within a poultry-production environment.

- Need for clear visual cues and intuitive navigation
- Ability to trace the factors contributing to outlier detection
- Transparent explanations of model outputs
- Seamless integration with internal data systems

2. McDonald's Illinois workshop (08/11/24)

This workshop explored AI-powered forecasting for poultry-related food-safety risks using real incident data.

- Unforeseen pathogen spikes and emerging risks (75%)
- Difficulty integrating external incident data into internal systems (70%)
- Lack of a comprehensive view of global poultry-related hazards (70%)
- Reliance on manual or outdated risk-assessment methods (60%)

3. Amsterdam workshop (05/02/25)

This session combined expert presentations with hands-on interaction with predictive dashboards.

- Unforeseen spikes in emerging risks (70%)
- Difficulty integrating external incident data (65%)
- Limited visibility of global hazard trends (60%)
- Dependence on manual risk-assessment methods (55%)

4. GFSI Dublin meetings (31/03 - 03/04/25)

These targeted meetings focused on predictive tools for external risk monitoring and supplier oversight.

- Need for more real-time data signals (80%)
- Clearer integration pathways for private datasets (73%)
- More contextual explanations behind sudden pathogen-risk changes (80%)
- High satisfaction with model accuracy (87%)

5. Michigan State University workshop (25/07/25)

This workshop examined AI-enabled detection of emerging poultry-related hazards and fraud vulnerabilities.

- Unforeseen spikes in emerging pathogen risks (75%)
- Difficulty integrating external incident data (67%)

- Limited visibility of global microbiological hazard trends (58%)
- Dependence on manual risk-assessment methods (50%)
- Need for predictive support in supplier-risk assessment and rapid mitigation

6. HEC Montréal workshop (08/08/25)

This event brought together industry, academia, and government to evaluate AI applications for hazard forecasting.

- Unexpected increases in pathogen-related risks (71%)
- Challenges integrating external incident data (64%)
- Insufficient visibility of global hazard patterns (57%)
- Dependence on manual risk-assessment processes (50%)
- Need for tools supporting external risk monitoring and supplier assessment

7. Austin NAFS workshop (17/09/25)

This workshop focused on AI-enabled forecasting for food-safety and fraud risks across complex supply chains.

- Sudden increases in pathogen-related risks (73%)
- Difficulty incorporating external incident data (64%)
- Limited visibility of global microbiological hazard patterns (55%)
- Dependence on manual workflows (45%)
- Need for rapid response and prioritisation of preventive resources

8. McDonald's FSQ online workshop (16/10/25)

This dedicated session focused on global supplier-risk monitoring and predictive early-warning signals.

- AI-driven early-warning signals for supplier-related risks
- Clear explanations behind predicted pathogen-risk changes
- Global visibility of emerging hazards
- Relevance for supplier prioritisation and incident escalation

9. Washington DC workshop (22/10/25)

This workshop evaluated predictive dashboards in the context of preventive-controls planning and corporate QA systems.

- Clear visual indicators and centralised risk intelligence
- Scenario-based insights for rapid decision-making
- Importance of explainability and data transparency
- Alignment with existing QA and regulatory processes

10. SEV Athens workshop (03/12/25)

This large-scale national workshop focused on practical applications of AI for pathogen-risk prediction.

- Clear visual indicators and scenario-based insights
- Transparent explanations of risk drivers
- Integration with existing QA systems
- Relevance for supplier-risk assessment and preventive-action planning

5.1.4. Insights from the Mycotoxins Trends Forecasting Pilot for Poultry Feed

Stakeholders' demographics

Across all validation activities for the Mycotoxins Trends Forecasting Pilot during the 3rd project year, a total of 24 professionals participated in the evaluation process. These organisations represented a broad cross-section of the poultry-feed and wider food-industry ecosystem, ensuring that the pilot was validated by upstream feed producers, poultry-meat processors, downstream retail groups, and academic institutions.

Across all validation workshops, the 24 participating professionals represented the following high-level categories:

- Food manufacturers & poultry producers: 79% (19/24)
- Retail & distribution groups: 8% (2/24)
- Academic & research organisations: 13% (3/24)

1. Food Fortress online evaluation session (Online) - 6 participants

This focused online session engaged 6 members of the Food Fortress network, all of whom were categorised under food manufacturers & poultry producers. Participants included laboratory specialists, feed-safety analysts, and risk-assessment professionals working directly with mycotoxin-testing data, feed-material monitoring, and early-warning systems for the UK feed sector.

2. Dedicated Meetings for Validation at IPPE 2025 (Atlanta, USA, 28 - 30/01/25) - 4 participants

Held during the International Production & Processing Expo (IPPE) 2025, these meetings engaged 4 professionals from 4 major poultry-sector companies, including Tyson Foods and Cargill. All participants were categorised under food manufacturers & poultry producers. Their roles spanned feed safety, poultry-meat quality, supplier oversight, and operational risk management, providing targeted insights from large-scale poultry producers.

3. Workshop “Supply Chain Disruptions - Addressing Microbiological and Chemical Hazards” (Cornell University, New York, USA, 26/06/25) - 14 participants

This one-day workshop, jointly organised by AGROKNOW and Cornell University, brought together 14 participants from 8 organisations, including PepsiCo, Mondelez, and The Coca-Cola Company, alongside academic researchers.

Figure 4: Intro session for the workshop “Supply Chain Disruptions - Addressing Microbiological and Chemical Hazards” on 26/06/26

The group represented:

- Food & beverage manufacturers: 65% (9/14)
- Retail & distribution groups: 14% (2/14)
- Academic & research organisations: 21% (3/14)

Stakeholders' profile

The stakeholders involved in the Mycotoxins Trends Forecasting Pilot represented operational, scientific, and decision-making roles directly connected to feed safety, poultry-production performance, supplier oversight, and emerging-risk monitoring. Based on responses to Part 1 of the Evaluation Questionnaire and insights gathered during the validation activities, participants included professionals working in:

- Feed safety and quality assurance
- Poultry-meat quality and production operations
- Supplier-monitoring and due-diligence functions
- Microbiological and chemical hazard-trend analysis
- Regulatory affairs and compliance
- Academic and applied research on mycotoxins and feed-related risks

Coverage across validation activities

Food Fortress online evaluation session (6 participants). Participants were laboratory specialists, feed-safety analysts, and risk-assessment professionals from the Food Fortress network. Their responsibilities include interpreting mycotoxin-testing data, monitoring contamination trends in feed materials, and supporting early-warning systems for the UK feed sector. Their operational focus ensured that the dashboards were evaluated by users with hands-on experience in feed-safety monitoring.

IPPE 2025 dedicated meetings (Atlanta, USA, 4 participants). Participants were senior professionals from major poultry-sector companies such as Tyson Foods and Cargill. Their roles spanned feed-safety oversight, poultry-meat quality management, supplier performance evaluation, and operational risk management. These stakeholders provided insights from large-scale poultry-production environments where mycotoxin contamination has direct implications for animal health and product quality.

Cornell University workshop (New York, USA, 14 participants). Participants represented a balanced mix of food and beverage manufacturers, retail groups, and academic researchers. Their responsibilities included external risk monitoring, ingredient-risk assessment, supply-chain oversight, and scientific research on emerging microbiological and chemical hazards. Their perspectives were particularly relevant for evaluating how predictive dashboards can support decision-making under supply-chain disruption and variable ingredient quality.

Stakeholders' needs

Across all validation activities for the Mycotoxins Trends Forecasting Pilot, stakeholders consistently highlighted needs that reflect the operational challenges of managing mycotoxin contamination risks in poultry feed and poultry-meat production. Insights from Part 1 of the Evaluation Questionnaire revealed that organisations face difficulties in monitoring rapidly changing contamination patterns, integrating external signals into internal systems, and interpreting sudden shifts in mycotoxin-risk levels. Participants emphasised the importance of early-warning capabilities, transparent predictive outputs, and improved visibility of global mycotoxin trends to support preventive decision-making across feed and poultry-production workflows.

1. Food Fortress online evaluation session (6 participants).

This session focused on operational feed-safety monitoring and laboratory-driven risk assessment. Participants highlighted the need for:

- Clearer visualisation of contamination trends across feed materials
- Integration of predictive insights with laboratory testing data
- Transparent explanations of risk drivers behind predicted mycotoxin changes
- Tools that support early-warning and collaborative decision-making within feed-safety networks

2. IPPE 2025 dedicated meetings (Atlanta, USA, 4 participants)

These meetings captured the needs of large poultry-sector companies responsible for feed safety and poultry-meat quality. Participants emphasised:

- More real-time data signals to ensure that risk graphs reflect current contamination conditions (84%)
- Clearer integration pathways for combining EFRA predictions with internal datasets (76%)
- More contextual explanations behind sudden mycotoxin-risk changes to support interpretability

3. Cornell University workshop (New York, USA, 14 participants)

This workshop explored predictive tools for managing microbiological and chemical hazards under supply-chain disruption. Participants identified several high-priority needs:

- Unforeseen spikes in emerging pathogen risks: 71% (10/14)
- Difficulty integrating external incident data into internal systems: 64% (9/14)
- Limited visibility of global microbiological hazard trends: 57% (8/14)
- Reliance on manual or outdated risk-assessment methods: 50% (7/14)

Participants expressed strong interest in understanding which data sources influence mycotoxin-risk changes and how the model weighs historical versus emerging signals.

5.1.5. Insights from the Pilot on Forecasting Trends for Mycotoxins in Animal Feed

Stakeholders' demographics

Across all validation activities for the Pilot on Forecasting Trends for Mycotoxins in Animal Feed during the 3rd project year, a total of 53 professionals participated in the evaluation process. These organisations represented a broad cross-section of the animal-feed, poultry-production, and wider food-industry ecosystem, ensuring that the pilot was validated by upstream feed producers, poultry-meat processors, downstream retail groups, academic institutions, and food-safety networks.

Across all validation workshops, the 53 participating professionals represented the following high-level categories:

- Food manufacturers & poultry producers: 77% (41/53)
- Retail & distribution groups: 4% (2/53)
- Academic & research organisations: 15% (8/53)
- Other stakeholder groups (networks, agencies, independent experts): 4% (2/53)

1. Dedicated Meetings for Validation at IPPE 2025 (Atlanta, USA, 28 - 30/01/25) - 4 participants

Held during the International Production & Processing Expo (IPPE) 2025, these meetings engaged 4 professionals from 4 major poultry-sector companies, including Tyson Foods and Cargill.

All participants were categorised under food manufacturers & poultry producers (100%, 4/4).

Participants held roles related to feed safety, poultry-meat quality, supplier oversight, and operational risk management, providing targeted insights from large-scale poultry producers. The discussions focused on

validating the Mycotoxins Predictive Dashboard for Animal Feed and the Mycotoxins Predictive Dashboard in Poultry Products.

2. Workshop “Supply Chain Disruptions - Addressing Microbiological and Chemical Hazards” (Cornell University, New York, USA, 26/06/25) - 14 participants

This one-day workshop, jointly organised by AGROKNOW and Cornell University, brought together 14 participants from 8 organisations, including food manufacturers, alongside with academic researchers. The group represented:

- Food & beverage manufacturers: 65% (9/14)
- Retail & distribution groups: 14% (2/14)
- Academic & research organisations: 21% (3/14)

3. EFRA Validation Workshop “AI for Food Risk Prevention” (Thessaloniki, Greece, hybrid, 19/06/25) - 35 participants

Organised in the context of the EFRA Plenary Meeting and delivered jointly with the Horizon Europe projects HOLiFOOD and STELAR, this half-day workshop engaged 35 professionals from 23 organisations, with 17 onsite and 16 online. The participating individuals included:

- Food-industry organisations: 80% (28/35)
- Academic & research organisations: 14% (5/35)
- Other stakeholder groups (networks, agencies, independent experts): 6% (2/35)

Figure 5: EFRA Validation workshop on “AI for Food Risk Prevention” (Thessaloniki, Greece, 19/06/25)

Stakeholders’ profile

The stakeholders involved in the Pilot on Forecasting Trends for Mycotoxins in Animal Feed represented a diverse set of professional roles across the feed, poultry-production, and broader food-industry ecosystem. Based on responses to Part 1 of the Evaluation Questionnaire and insights gathered during the validation activities, participants included professionals working in:

- Feed safety and quality assurance (FSQA)
- Poultry-production operations and animal-health management
- Supplier-monitoring, procurement, and due-diligence functions
- Microbiological and chemical hazard-trend analysis

- Regulatory affairs and compliance
- Academic research on mycotoxins, feed contaminants, and predictive modelling
- Digital food-safety, data-science, and risk-analytics roles

Coverage across validation activities

1. Dedicated Meetings for Validation at IPPE 2025 (Atlanta, USA)

Participants were senior professionals from major poultry-sector companies, including Tyson Foods and Cargill. Their responsibilities spanned feed-safety oversight, poultry-meat quality management, supplier performance evaluation, and operational risk management. These stakeholders provided insights from large-scale poultry-production environments where mycotoxin contamination has direct implications for animal health, feed efficiency, and product quality.

2. Workshop “Supply Chain Disruptions – Addressing Microbiological and Chemical Hazards” (Cornell University, New York, USA)

Participants represented food and beverage manufacturers, retail groups, and academic institutions. Their roles included external risk monitoring, ingredient-risk assessment, supply-chain oversight, and scientific research on emerging microbiological and chemical hazards. Their perspectives were particularly relevant for evaluating how predictive dashboards can support decision-making under supply-chain disruption, ingredient variability, and global sourcing challenges.

3. EFRA Validation Workshop “AI for Food Risk Prevention” (Thessaloniki, Greece)

Participants included food-industry professionals, academic researchers, and representatives from networks, agencies, and independent expert groups. Their roles covered FSQA management, regulatory compliance, digital food-safety innovation, hazard forecasting, and risk-management strategy. Their contributions reflected the broad relevance of mycotoxin-risk forecasting across feed, livestock, and multi-commodity supply chains, especially in contexts involving emerging hazards and limited visibility of global risk signals.

Stakeholders’ needs

Throughout the validation activities for this pilot, stakeholders highlighted needs that reflect the operational challenges of managing mycotoxin contamination risks in animal feed and understanding their downstream effects on poultry production. The needs below are taken directly from the workshop descriptions and questionnaire responses.

1. Dedicated Meetings for Validation at IPPE 2025 (Atlanta, USA)

Participants identified several needs for strengthening the operational value of the mycotoxin-prediction dashboards:

- Need for more real-time data signals so that risk graphs reflect current contamination conditions (84%).
- Need for clearer integration pathways with internal systems to combine EFRA predictions with private datasets (76%).
- Need for more contextual explanations behind sudden mycotoxin-risk changes to support interpretability.

2. Workshop “Supply Chain Disruptions – Addressing Microbiological and Chemical Hazards” (Cornell University, New York, USA)

Participants identified several high-priority needs related to managing emerging pathogen and contaminant risks under supply-chain disruption:

- Unforeseen spikes in emerging pathogen risks: 71% (10/14)
- Difficulty integrating external incident data into internal systems: 64% (9/14)

- Limited visibility of global microbiological hazard trends: 57% (8/14)
- Reliance on manual or outdated risk-assessment methods: 50% (7/14)

3. EFRA Validation Workshop “AI for Food Risk Prevention” (Thessaloniki, Greece)

Participants highlighted several needs related to deploying AI for food-risk prevention across complex supply chains:

- Early detection of unexpected spikes in biological or environmental risks
- Improved integration of external incident and surveillance data into internal systems
- Better visibility of global hazard trends across commodities and regions
- Reduction of manual, time-consuming risk-assessment processes

5.1.6. AI-Driven Pest Prediction Alerts Pilot

Stakeholders’ demographics

The pilot engaged 24 active arable farming operations from three countries: Croatia (11 participants), Romania (12 participants), and Bulgaria (1 participant). These farms collectively allocated approximately 770 hectares to the comparative algorithm evaluation, with Croatian participants contributing around 551 hectares primarily from the Slavonia and Osijek regions, Romanian participants managing approximately 219 hectares across southern and central regions, and the Bulgarian participant's area not specified at the time of reporting.

The participant pool reflected diverse farm sizes and business scales. Eight smallholdings operated under 20 hectares (4 from Croatia, 4 from Romania), ten small-to-medium enterprises managed between 20–100 hectares (5 from Croatia, 5 from Romania), and one large Croatian cooperative operated 229 hectares. This and employee counts information demonstrate the range from family-operated smallholdings to larger operations.

Stakeholders’ profile

The participants are active commercial crop producers whose involvement in the pilot was directly tied to validating improved pest prediction algorithms under real-world conditions.

The stakeholder groups are classified based on operational scale and their specific contributions to algorithm validation:

- **Smallholding farmers (<20 ha, n=8)** cultivate primarily corn and operate with limited labour and technical resources. Their role in the pilot focuses on providing ground-truth observations through the existing scouting module to validate alert accuracy in smaller, simpler production systems.
- **Small-to-medium farm operators (20–100 ha, n=10)** manage diversified rotations including corn, wheat, and sunflower. These participants contribute observations across multiple crop types, enabling crop-specific and cross-crop algorithm validation. Their feedback helps assess whether the improved algorithm performs consistently across varied agronomic conditions.
- **Large farm/cooperative operators (>100 ha, n=1)** manage complex multi-field systems and provide high-volume observation data across diverse field environments. This participant's involvement tests algorithm performance at scale and under varied microclimatic and soil conditions within a single operation.

Stakeholders’ needs

Stakeholder needs, identified through Part 1 of the Evaluation Questionnaire, vary by farm scale and operational complexity:

- **Smallholding farmers** reported challenges with delayed or inaccurate pest alerts that fail to account for local field conditions, leading to either missed pest outbreaks or unnecessary interventions. Their primary needs include more accurate, regionally calibrated alerts; mobile-accessible interfaces for field-based alert checking; and clear, actionable guidance on when and how to respond to alerts. Multilingual support (Romanian and Bulgarian) was also identified as critical for proper alert interpretation.
- **Small-to-medium farm** operators face challenges managing pest alerts across multiple crops with different pest pressure timings and thresholds. They need crop-specific alert calibration, timely notifications (at least 48 hours before critical thresholds), field-level comparison tools to prioritize scouting efforts, and reduced false positive rates to maintain trust in the system. These farmers also require weather-contextualized alerts that account for microclimatic variations across their fields.
- **Large farms and cooperatives** struggle with alert overload across numerous fields and the need to prioritize scouting resources efficiently. Their needs include aggregated multi-field alert dashboards, customizable alert thresholds based on field-specific risk tolerance, exportable alert logs for record-keeping and compliance, and reliable system performance when managing high alert volumes simultaneously.

5.1.7. Real-Time Pest Observation and Prediction Pilot

Stakeholders' demographics

The pilot engaged 24 active arable farming operations from three countries: Croatia (11 participants), Romania (12 participants), and Bulgaria (1 participant). These farms collectively allocated approximately 770 hectares to the pilot, with Croatian participants contributing around 551 hectares primarily from the Slavonia and Osijek regions, Romanian participants managing approximately 219 hectares across southern and central regions, and the Bulgarian participant's area remaining unspecified during the pilot period.

Participating farms varied significantly in operational scale. Eight smallholdings operated under 20 hectares (4 from Croatia, 4 from Romania), ten small-to-medium enterprises managed between 20–100 hectares (5 from Croatia, 5 from Romania), and one large cooperative from Croatia operated 229 hectares across 14 fields.

Stakeholders' profile

All participants are active arable farmers operating commercial crop production businesses, with their involvement in the pilot directly aligned with improving pest management efficiency and agricultural decision-making. The participant groups can be classified into three primary categories based on operational complexity and pilot engagement:

- **Smallholding farmers (<20 ha, n=8)** primarily cultivate corn and operate family-run farms with limited labour resources. Their engagement focuses on using the enhanced scouting module for real-time field monitoring and submitting pest observations through mobile devices.
- **Small-to-medium farm** operators (20–100 ha, n=10) manage diversified crop rotations including corn, wheat, and sunflower. These participants require more sophisticated multi-crop monitoring capabilities and actively contribute detailed observations across multiple crop types to test system scalability and model adaptability.
- **Large farm / cooperative** operators (>100 ha, n=1) manage complex multi-field operations with team-based workflows. This participant tests the system's ability to handle high-volume data submission, multi-user access, and aggregated reporting across diverse field conditions.

Participants' relation to pilot objectives centres on providing continuous, high-quality field observations that feed directly into real-time model training, thereby validating the system's scalability and its ability to improve prediction accuracy through farmer feedback.

Stakeholders' needs

Stakeholder needs vary by operational scale and were identified through Part 1 of the Evaluation Questionnaire responses:

- **Smallholding farmers** reported challenges with time-intensive manual pest monitoring and the need for simple, mobile-accessible tools that minimize data entry burden. Their primary needs include intuitive interfaces, quick one-click recording features, multilingual support (particularly Romanian and Bulgarian translations), and onboarding assistance to ensure proper field setup and module usage.
- **Small-to-medium farm** operators face challenges managing pest monitoring across multiple crop types and coordinating scouting activities during peak growing seasons. They require multi-crop scheduling support, field-level comparison tools, weather-integrated insights to contextualize pest activity, and decision support for sowing timing and crop rotation planning. These farmers also value the ability to track pest trends across different fields to optimize resource allocation.
- **Large farms and cooperatives** struggle with coordinating multi-user access, aggregating data across numerous fields, and generating comprehensive reports for management decision-making. Their needs include multi-field aggregation capabilities, team collaboration features, exportable reporting tools, and system reliability when handling high data volumes simultaneously.

5.1.8. Automated Regulatory Summarisation Pilot

Stakeholders' demographics

The stakeholders' headquarters are mainly based in Europe, with a smaller representation from India and the United States. Respondents varied in annual revenue, ranging from approximately €52 million to €10.4 billion. The majority operate within the food and beverage industry, although several are engaged in international trade and development services. Among all 12 respondents, representing 8 unique stakeholder organizations, 92% reported working with foreign or international suppliers for food products, ingredients, or raw materials. The same proportion confirmed having a dedicated food safety and quality team. In terms of team size, 41% of companies reported having between 5 and 10 team members, 33% between 10 and 50, and 25% fewer than 5. The pilot activities involved over 30 participants across around five events in mixed formats, including online sessions with demonstrator and interactive demo presentations.

Stakeholders' profile

Most of the stakeholders operate primarily within the food and beverage industry, focusing on activities such as production, distribution, retail. In addition to this dominant sector, there are also several organizations that extend their scope beyond food and beverage, engaging in areas such as international trade, market expansion, and development services.

Stakeholders' needs

Stakeholders highlighted several key challenges, including the absence of a comprehensive and reliable overview of external risks and hazards, difficulties in anticipating unforeseen or emerging risks, and the need to effectively integrate high-quality external risk data into existing internal food safety processes.

5.1.9. Smart Regulatory Navigator Pilot

Stakeholders' demographics

The stakeholders' headquarters are mainly based in Europe, with a smaller representation from India and the United States. Respondents varied in annual revenue, ranging from approximately €52 million to €10.4 billion. The majority operate within the food and beverage industry, although several are engaged in international trade and development services. Among all 12 respondents, representing 8 unique stakeholder organizations, 92% reported working with foreign or international suppliers for food products, ingredients, or raw materials. The same proportion confirmed having a dedicated food safety and quality team. In terms of team size, 41% of companies reported having between 5 and 10 team members, 33% between 10 and 50, and 25% fewer than 5. The pilot activities involved over 30 participants across around five events in mixed formats, including online sessions with demonstrator and interactive demo presentations.

Stakeholders' profile

Most of the stakeholders operate primarily within the food and beverage industry, focusing on activities such as production, distribution, retail. In addition to this dominant sector, there are also several organizations that extend their scope beyond food and beverage, engaging in areas such as international trade, market expansion, and development services.

Stakeholders' needs

Stakeholders highlighted several key challenges, including the absence of a comprehensive and reliable overview of external risks and hazards, difficulties in anticipating unforeseen or emerging risks, and the need to effectively integrate high-quality external risk data into existing internal food safety processes.

5.2. Evaluation Results of the EFRA Decision Support Tools

The evaluation of the EFRA decision-support tools followed a unified assessment framework designed to capture user perceptions, operational performance, and real-world decision-support value. Structured questionnaire responses and insights gathered during multiple validation workshops were analysed under three core dimensions: Stakeholder Feedback, reflecting satisfaction, usability, clarity, and perceived value; Functionality Evaluation, assessing how effectively each tool performed in real operational settings, including navigation, responsiveness, interpretability, and stability; and Success Indicators, capturing the practical impact of each tool on food-safety, supplier-risk, and preventive decision-making. Together, these dimensions provide a comprehensive understanding of how the EFRA tools were received by end users and how effectively they support proactive, data-driven risk-management practices in poultry and feed supply chains.

5.2.1. Findings from the Proactive Flock Mortality Pilot

Stakeholder Feedback

Stakeholders consistently described the Mortality-Rate Outlier Detection Dashboard as clear, intuitive, and operationally relevant. The interface was viewed as easy to navigate, with visual elements that support rapid interpretation of flock-level deviations. Participants across all events emphasised the dashboard's value for:

- Detecting abnormal mortality patterns early
- Improving visibility across production batches

- Supporting proactive investigation of potential pathogen-related issues
- Reinforcing data-driven decision-making in poultry operations

Event-specific feedback:

1. Workshop with Moy Park team (Online, 17/06/25, 22/09/25, 15/10/25)

Participants highlighted the dashboard's usefulness for identifying flock-performance anomalies and improving early detection of potential pathogen-related issues. They valued the clarity of visual indicators, the intuitive navigation, and the ability to trace the factors contributing to outlier detection. They also stressed the need for transparent explanations of model outputs and smooth integration with internal systems.

2. Workshop "Using AI for Food Risk Prevention" (Amsterdam, Netherlands, 05/02/25)

Participants reinforced the importance of early detection, interpretability, and integration with existing FSQA workflows. The dashboard's ability to highlight deviations from expected mortality patterns was seen as essential for proactive investigation.

3. Workshop "Using AI to Enhance Food Safety and Prevent Food Fraud" (Austin, USA, 17/09/25)

Participants identified key challenges in managing emerging pathogen risks, including sudden increases in risk (73%), difficulty incorporating external incident data (64%), limited visibility of global hazard patterns (55%), and reliance on manual workflows (45%).

Satisfaction with the demonstrator was high:

- Dashboard clarity and usability: 91%
- Overall satisfaction: 82%
- Relevance of predictive insights: 82%
- Trust in model outputs: 73%

4. Workshop "Transforming Food Safety & Fraud Prevention with AI" (Washington DC, USA, 22/10/25)

Participants emphasised the value of:

- Clear visual indicators
- Centralised risk intelligence
- Scenario-based insights for rapid decision-making

The dashboard was viewed as particularly relevant for external incident monitoring, supplier-risk assessment, and prioritising preventive actions. Discussions highlighted the importance of explainability, data transparency, and alignment with existing QA and regulatory processes.

Functionality Evaluation

Stakeholders evaluated the dashboard's functionality in terms of performance, responsiveness, analytical depth, and operational relevance. Feedback across all events confirmed that the tool performed reliably in real-world settings and supported both exploratory analysis and operational decision-making. Participants highlighted:

- Smooth and intuitive navigation within the FOODAKAI environment
- Dynamic visualisation updates when switching between 5-cluster and 10-cluster granularities
- Clear hover interactions showing flock counts per cluster
- Ability to download datasets for offline analysis
- A transparent and user-friendly retraining tab for uploading new datasets

Event-specific functionality observations:

1. Workshop with Moy Park team (Online, 17/06/25, 22/09/25, 15/10/25)

Participants confirmed that the dashboard effectively identifies high-mortality outlier flocks and provides actionable insights for early detection of performance deviations. They valued the ability to move from overview to detailed inspection with minimal friction.

2. International Workshops (Amsterdam 05/02/25, Austin NAFS 17/09/25, Washington DC, 22/10/25)

Participants noted that the clustering model:

- Groups flocks based on mortality curves
- Enables rapid detection of atypical behaviours
- Supports investigation of disease outbreaks, management issues, or environmental stressors

Success Indicators

Stakeholders reported that the Mortality-Rate Outlier Detection Dashboard supported several high-value decision-making processes across poultry-production and food-safety workflows.

The dashboard was used to support:

- Early detection of flock-performance anomalies
- Identification of potential pathogen-related issues
- Supplier-risk assessment and monitoring
- Prioritisation of preventive and mitigation actions
- Rapid investigation of deviations from expected mortality patterns
- Enhanced visibility across production batches

Event-specific success indicators

- Moy Park workshops (online): Improved early detection of performance deviations and enhanced visibility across flocks.
- Amsterdam workshop (05/02/25): Effective for identifying high-risk flocks and supporting proactive investigation.
- Austin workshop (NAFS, 17/09/25): Strong support for external risk monitoring (82%), supplier-risk assessment (73%), and rapid mitigation (64%).
- Washington DC workshop (22/10/25): High relevance for supplier management, preventive controls, and incident monitoring.

5.2.2. Findings from the Predictive Poultry Weight Gain Pilot for Poultry Farming

Stakeholder Feedback

Since the Weight-Gain Outlier Detection Dashboard was evaluated within the same piloting scenario and workshops as the Mortality-Rate Outlier Detection Dashboard, stakeholder feedback was highly consistent with the results presented in Section 5.2.1. Participants described the tool as clear, intuitive, and operationally valuable for:

- Detecting abnormal weight-gain patterns early
- Improving visibility of flock-growth trajectories
- Supporting proactive investigation of health- or management-related issues

Stakeholders also appreciated the consistency of interaction patterns across the mortality-rate and weight-gain modules, noting that this reduced cognitive load and made the tool easier to adopt. As with the mortality-rate dashboard, participants emphasised the importance of interpretability and transparent model outputs.

Functionality Evaluation

The functionality assessment for the Weight-Gain Outlier Detection Dashboard produced findings equivalent to those of the mortality-rate tool, as both dashboards share the same interface, clustering logic, and analytical workflow. Participants highlighted:

- Smooth navigation and responsive visualisations
- Dynamic updates when switching between 5- and 10-cluster granularities
- Clear hover interactions and cluster-based exploration
- Dataset download options for offline analysis
- A transparent and user-friendly retraining tab

Additional technical evaluation confirmed that the dashboard reliably identifies low- and high-weight-gain outlier flocks, produces stable clustering results across repeated runs, and adjusts appropriately when retrained with new datasets, ensuring accuracy and relevance across production cycles.

Success Indicators

Success indicators for the weight-gain dashboard were fully aligned with those reported for the mortality-rate dashboard, reflecting the shared decision-support context. The dashboard supported:

- Early detection of abnormal weight-gain patterns
- Identification of potential health- or management-related issues
- Supplier-risk assessment, including feed quality and chick quality
- Prioritisation of preventive and mitigation actions
- Rapid investigation of deviations from expected growth trajectories
- Enhanced visibility across production batches

5.2.3. Findings from the Poultry Precision Pilot using with Predictive Food Safety Insights

Stakeholder Feedback

Stakeholders consistently described the Poultry Safety Incidents Forecasting Dashboard as clear, intuitive, and highly valuable for anticipating poultry-related food-safety risks. Across all validation activities, participants emphasised the dashboard's usefulness for:

- Understanding historical and predicted incident trends
- Detecting emerging risk patterns early
- Supporting proactive planning and preventive controls
- Enhancing visibility of hazard-specific and region-specific risks
- Reinforcing data-driven decision-making across poultry supply chains

The embedded Explainability panel was repeatedly highlighted as a major strength, helping users interpret predictions, understand contributing factors, and contextualise risk fluctuations without leaving the main dashboard. The stakeholders' feedback is analysed below for each piloting activity.

1. Moy Park Online Workshops (17/06/25, 22/09/25, 15/10/25)

Participants provided detailed, practical feedback reflecting real operational needs in poultry production. They highlighted:

- The value of visualising incident trends over time
- The importance of hazard-specific filtering (e.g., Salmonella)
- The usefulness of identifying potential risk escalations early
- The need for transparent explanations of model outputs
- The importance of seamless integration with internal systems

Overall, the workshops confirmed that the forecasting dashboard aligns closely with industry requirements and supports proactive risk management.

2. Workshop “Using AI for Food Risk Prevention - A Practical, Hands-On Tutorial” (McDonald’s, Illinois, 08/11/24)

Participants expressed strong interest in AI-powered forecasting for poultry-related food-safety risks. Their needs aligned closely with the challenges addressed by the dashboard, including:

- Unforeseen pathogen spikes and emerging risks
- Difficulty integrating external incident data into internal systems
- Limited visibility of global poultry-related hazards
- Reliance on manual or outdated risk-assessment methods

Participants indicated that the dashboard would support:

- External risk monitoring
- Ingredient and supplier risk assessment
- Rapid mitigation of escalating crises
- Allocation of preventive resources

User satisfaction and trust were high, with participants highlighting:

- The clarity of the dashboard
- The relevance of predictive insights
- The practical value of the explainability features

3. Workshop “Using AI for Food Risk Prevention” (Amsterdam, 05/02/25)

Participants emphasised:

- The value of geographical risk mapping
- The usefulness of hazard-specific filtering
- The importance of understanding emerging risk spikes
- The need for improved integration of external incident data

Satisfaction and trust were high, with participants requesting greater explainability regarding how predictions are generated.

4. Dedicated Validation Meetings - GFSI Conference (Dublin, 31/03 - 03/04/25)

Participants highlighted:

- The need for more real-time data signals
- Clearer integration pathways with internal systems
- More contextual explanations behind sudden pathogen-risk changes

They expressed high satisfaction with the demonstrator, noting that predicted patterns aligned with known seasonal behaviours and historical contamination events.

5. Workshop “AI for Food Risk and Food Fraud Prevention” (Michigan, 25/07/25)

Participants identified several high-priority needs:

- Unforeseen spikes in emerging pathogen risks
- Difficulty integrating external incident data
- Limited visibility of global hazard trends
- Reliance on manual or outdated risk-assessment methods

Participants expressed strong interest in understanding:

- Which data sources influence pathogen-risk changes
- How the model weighs historical vs. emerging signals
- Why sudden spikes occur in specific regions or suppliers
- Transparency and interpretability were repeatedly highlighted as essential.

6. Workshop “AI Innovations for Safer Food Supply Chains” (Montreal, 08/08/25)

Participants valued:

- The ability to explore multiple forecast horizons (3, 6, 12 months)
- The integration of geographical insights for targeted interventions
- The relevance of predicted trends for long-term planning

7. Workshop “Using AI to Enhance Food Safety and Prevent Food Fraud” (Austin, 17/09/25)

Participants identified several key challenges in managing emerging pathogen risks:

- Sudden increases in pathogen-related risks
- Difficulty incorporating external incident data
- Limited visibility of global microbiological hazard patterns
- Dependence on manual or outdated workflows

Satisfaction was high, with participants emphasising the clarity of the interface and the relevance of predictive insights. The main improvement request was greater transparency in how predictions are generated.

8. Online Validation Workshop with McDonald’s FSQ Team (16/10/25)

Participants highlighted:

- The value of AI-driven early-warning signals
- The relevance of predictive insights for supplier prioritisation
- The importance of model transparency and clear explanations
- The usefulness of generative AI for interpreting complex risk information

9. Workshop “Transforming Food Safety & Fraud Prevention with AI” (Washington DC, 22/10/25)

Participants valued:

- Clear visual indicators
- Centralised risk intelligence
- Scenario-based insights for rapid decision-making

10. EFRA Validation Workshop “AI in Food Safety - Practical Risk Management” (Athens, 03/12/25)

Participants highlighted:

- Strong relevance for early detection of emerging microbiological issues
- The value of clear visual indicators and centralised risk information
- The usefulness of scenario-based insights for rapid decision-making
- The importance of explainability and integration with existing QA systems

Functionality Evaluation

Stakeholders evaluated the Poultry Safety Incidents Forecasting Dashboard as stable, responsive, and highly functional in real-world settings. The unified list below reflects the updated, consolidated results across all validation activities. Participants highlighted:

- Smooth and intuitive navigation across time-series, geographical, and hazard-specific views
- Dynamic visualisation updates when switching between products, hazards, or forecast horizons (3, 6, 12 months)
- Clear hover interactions and clickable elements for inspecting exact values, comparing actual vs. predicted trends, and exploring smoothed curves
- Seamless comparison of historical, predicted, and future forecast values
- Integrated explainability panel providing contextual insights without leaving the main dashboard
- Multi-dimensional analysis combining trends, geography, hazard filters, and contributing-factor explanations
- Consistent performance across repeated runs and different time horizons
- Effective integration of geographical insights, enabling targeted supplier or region-specific interventions

Technical evaluation confirmed that the forecasting model:

- Produces stable and consistent predictions across multiple horizons
- Accurately highlights seasonal patterns, emerging risk escalations, and long-term trends
- Adjusts appropriately when new data becomes available, maintaining relevance across production cycles
- Provides transparent modelling information through the “How We Forecast” layer, including data sources, factor groups, and tuning steps

Event-specific functionality observations:

1. Moy Park Online Workshops (17/06/25, 22/09/25, 15/10/25). Participants confirmed that the dashboard effectively visualises incident trends, supports hazard-specific filtering, and provides actionable insights for early detection of risk escalations. They emphasised the importance of transparent model explanations and smooth integration with internal systems.

2. Workshop “Using AI for Food Risk Prevention - A Practical, Hands-On Tutorial” (McDonald’s, Illinois, 08/11/24). Participants valued the clarity of the time-series visualisations and the ability to compare actual vs. predicted values. They highlighted the usefulness of the explainability layer and requested more real-time data signals to complement historical public-incident data.

3. Workshop “Using AI for Food Risk Prevention” (Amsterdam, 05/02/25). Stakeholders appreciated the geographical risk map and hazard-specific filtering, noting that the dashboard supports proactive supplier-monitoring workflows.

4. Dedicated Validation Meetings - GFSI Conference (Dublin, 31/03 - 03/04/25). Participants emphasised the need for more real-time data and clearer integration pathways. They confirmed that predicted patterns aligned with known seasonal behaviours and historical contamination events.

5. Workshop “AI for Food Risk and Food Fraud Prevention” (Michigan, 25/07/25). Participants highlighted the dashboard’s ability to support supplier-risk assessment and rapid mitigation of microbiological issues. They expressed strong interest in understanding the factors driving predicted changes.

6. Workshop “AI Innovations for Safer Food Supply Chains” (Montreal, 08/08/25). Participants valued the ability to explore multiple forecast horizons and the integration of geographical insights for targeted interventions.

7. Workshop “Using AI to Enhance Food Safety and Prevent Food Fraud” (Austin, 17/09/25). Stakeholders emphasised the dashboard’s relevance for monitoring emerging pathogen risks and integrating external incident intelligence into internal systems.

8. Online Validation Workshop with McDonald’s FSQ Team (16/10/25). Participants highlighted the value of AI-driven early-warning signals and the importance of model transparency for internal decision-making.

9. Workshop “Transforming Food Safety & Fraud Prevention with AI” (Washington DC, 22/10/25). Participants valued scenario-based insights and the dashboard’s usefulness for supplier-risk assessment and preventive-action prioritisation.

10. EFRA Validation Workshop “AI in Food Safety - Practical Risk Management” (Athens, 03/12/25). Participants emphasised the dashboard’s potential for national-level risk-management strategies and the importance of explainability for regulatory and compliance contexts.

Success Indicators

Across all piloting activities, stakeholders reported that the Poultry Safety Incidents Forecasting Dashboard supported several high-value food-safety and supplier-management decisions. The unified list below reflects the combined results from all validation workshops, meetings, and hands-on sessions. Participants indicated that the dashboard supported:

- Early detection of emerging poultry-related food-safety risks, enabling proactive intervention before issues escalate
- Prioritisation of preventive and mitigation actions, based on predicted incident trends and risk intensification
- Strategic planning and resource allocation, informed by 3-, 6-, and 12-month forecast horizons
- Hazard-specific monitoring (e.g., Salmonella), supporting focused preventive controls and testing strategies
- Region-specific risk analysis, helping adjust sourcing decisions and supplier-approval workflows
- Rapid investigation of deviations from expected incident patterns, supported by explainability features and contributing-factor insights
- Strengthening of external risk-monitoring processes, integrating global incident intelligence into internal FSQA systems

5.2.4. Findings from the Mycotoxins Trends Forecasting Pilot for Poultry Feed

Stakeholder Feedback

Stakeholders consistently described the Mycotoxin Concentration Dashboard as clear, intuitive, and highly valuable for monitoring mycotoxin-related risks in poultry and ruminant feed. Across all validation activities, participants emphasised the dashboard’s usefulness for:

- Understanding daily and long-term mycotoxin concentration trends
- Detecting unusual peaks or emerging contamination patterns
- Supporting proactive feed-safety and supplier-management decisions

- Reinforcing data-driven monitoring practices across feed-production environments

Event-specific feedback:

1. Food Fortress online evaluation session (Online)

Participants highlighted:

- The clarity of the time-series visualisations
- The usefulness of decomposition analysis for understanding seasonal patterns
- The importance of transparent, reproducible outputs
- The operational relevance of daily concentration values for feed-safety monitoring

2. Dedicated Validation Meetings - IPPE 2025 (Atlanta, 28 - 30/01/25)

Participants from major poultry-sector companies emphasised:

- The need for more real-time data signals to reflect current contamination conditions
- Clearer integration pathways with internal systems
- More contextual explanations behind sudden mycotoxin-risk changes

Satisfaction with the dashboard was high, with participants noting that predicted patterns aligned with:

- Seasonal fluctuations
- Known high-risk origins
- Historical contamination events

3. Workshop “Supply Chain Disruptions - Addressing Microbiological and Chemical Hazards” (Cornell University, New York, 26/06/25)

Participants emphasised:

- The importance of monitoring mycotoxin trends under supply-chain disruption
- The value of AI-enabled dashboards for identifying emerging contamination risks
- The usefulness of decomposition analysis for distinguishing structural vs. seasonal changes
- The need for transparent explanations of risk fluctuations

Functionality Evaluation

Stakeholders evaluated the Mycotoxin Concentration Dashboard as stable, responsive, and highly functional in real-world settings. The unified list below reflects the consolidated results across all validation activities.

Participants highlighted:

- Smooth and intuitive navigation across mycotoxin types and product categories
- Dynamic updates of all visualisations when selecting toxins or feed types
- Clear hover interactions for inspecting precise daily concentration values
- Integrated decomposition analysis (trend, seasonality, residual) supporting deeper interpretation
- Consistent performance across repeated analyses, even with noisy datasets
- Ability to download laboratory datasets for offline analysis and reporting
- Transparent, reproducible outputs powered by the EFRA Platform Timeseries Engine

Technical evaluation confirmed that the dashboard:

- Reliably visualises long-term trajectories and periodic patterns
- Detects irregular fluctuations that may signal emerging contamination risks
- Handles complex datasets with stability and accuracy
- Supports proactive interventions such as adjusting sampling strategies

Event-specific functionality observations:

- Food Fortress: Confirmed the dashboard's suitability for laboratory-driven monitoring and its value for interpreting seasonal patterns.
- IPPE Atlanta: Participants emphasised the need for real-time signals and integration with internal systems, while confirming the accuracy of predicted patterns.
- Cornell / New York: Users valued the decomposition analysis and multi-dimensional insights for managing risks under supply-chain disruption.

Success Indicators

All stakeholders reported that the Mycotoxin Concentration Dashboard supported several high-value feed-safety and supplier-management decisions. The unified list below reflects the combined results from all validation workshops and meetings. Specifically:

- Early detection of emerging mycotoxin-related risks in poultry and ruminant feed
- Prioritisation of preventive and mitigation actions, based on concentration trends and anomalies
- Strategic planning and resource allocation, informed by long-term trend and seasonality analysis
- Targeted sampling strategies, guided by decomposition insights
- Rapid investigation of deviations from expected concentration patterns
- Enhanced visibility of contamination cycles, supporting proactive feed-safety management

5.2.5. Findings from the Forecasting Trends for Mycotoxins in Animal Feed

Stakeholder Feedback

Stakeholders consistently described the Mycotoxins Incidents Forecasting Dashboard as clear, intuitive, and highly valuable for anticipating mycotoxin-related risks in poultry and other animal feed. Across all validation activities, participants emphasised the dashboard's usefulness for:

- Understanding historical and predicted mycotoxin-incident trends
- Detecting emerging contamination risks early
- Supporting proactive feed-safety and supplier-management decisions
- Enhancing visibility of regional and hazard-specific risk patterns
- Reinforcing data-driven monitoring practices across feed-production environments

The geographical analysis panels, 12-month risk heat map, and Latest Outbreaks table were repeatedly highlighted as major strengths, helping users maintain situational awareness and quickly identify high-risk regions or hazards. The Insights for Actual and Predicted Incidents table was also praised for linking past dynamics with future projections in a concise, actionable format.

Event-specific feedback:

1. Dedicated Meetings for Validation at IPPE 2025 (Atlanta, USA, 28 - 30/01/25)

Participants from major poultry-sector companies emphasised:

- The need for more real-time data signals to reflect current contamination conditions
- Clearer integration pathways with internal systems
- More contextual explanations behind sudden mycotoxin-risk changes

Satisfaction with the dashboard was high, with participants noting that predicted patterns aligned with:

- Seasonal fluctuations

- Known high-risk origins
- Historical contamination events

2. Workshop “Supply Chain Disruptions - Addressing Microbiological and Chemical Hazards” (Cornell University, New York, USA, 26/06/25)

Participants emphasised:

- The importance of monitoring mycotoxin trends under supply-chain disruption
- The value of AI-enabled dashboards for identifying emerging contamination risks
- The usefulness of geographical breakdowns for targeted monitoring
- The need for transparent explanations of risk fluctuations

3. EFRA Validation Workshop “AI for Food Risk Prevention” (Thessaloniki, Greece, hybrid, 19/06/25)

Participants highlighted:

- The clarity and usability of the time-series visualisations
- The value of the 12-month risk heat map for long-term planning
- The usefulness of the Latest Outbreaks table for real-time situational awareness
- The importance of explainability and transparent modelling approaches

Functionality Evaluation

Stakeholders evaluated the Mycotoxins Incidents Forecasting Dashboard as stable, responsive, and highly functional in real-world settings. The unified list below reflects the consolidated results across all validation activities. Participants highlighted:

- Smooth and intuitive navigation across time-series, geographical, and hazard-specific views
- Dynamic updates when switching between toxins, feed types, or forecast horizons
- Clear hover interactions for inspecting exact monthly incident values
- Seamless comparison of historical, predicted, and future forecast values
- Integrated explainability panel providing contextual insights without leaving the dashboard
- Multi-dimensional analysis combining trends, geography, hazard distributions, and contributing-factor explanations
- Consistent performance across repeated runs and multiple forecast horizons
- Actionable summaries through the Insights and Latest Outbreaks tables

Technical evaluation confirmed that the forecasting model:

- Produces stable and interpretable predictions across 3-, 6-, and 12-month horizons
- Accurately captures seasonal patterns, long-term trends, and irregular spikes
- Adjusts appropriately when new data becomes available, maintaining relevance across production cycles
- Provides transparent modelling information through the “How We Forecast” layer, including data sources, factor groups, and tuning steps

Success Indicators

Across all piloting activities, stakeholders reported that the Mycotoxins Incidents Forecasting Dashboard supported several high-value feed-safety and supplier-management decisions. The unified list below reflects the combined results from all validation workshops and meetings. Participants indicated that the dashboard supported:

- Early detection of emerging mycotoxin-related risks in poultry and other animal feed
- Prioritisation of preventive and mitigation actions, based on predicted incident trends and anomalies

- Supplier-risk assessment, especially for high-risk origins or feed ingredients
- Strategic planning and resource allocation, informed by long-term trend and seasonality analysis
- Targeted monitoring and sampling strategies, guided by geographical and hazard-specific insights
- Rapid investigation of deviations from expected incident patterns
- Enhanced visibility of contamination cycles, supporting proactive feed-safety management

5.2.6. Findings from the AI-Driven Pest Prediction Alerts Pilot

Stakeholder Feedback

Farmers rated their experience at 7/10 or higher, with engagement varying by communication structure. Croatian participants (n=5), coordinated through a local intermediary, showed consistently high engagement. Four of five found the interface "very clear," and all confirmed accurate translations. One-click logging and weather integration were universally valued. However, farmers explicitly noted crop-specific gaps—while corn alerts were reliable, sunflower alerts had timing issues (particularly for sunflower moth) and wheat alerts needed improvement.

Romanian participants (n=3) showed strong satisfaction through direct AGRIVI Romanian-speaking team support. All found the module "easy" or "very easy," with one-click logging and weather integration most appreciated. The smallholder (5 ha) explicitly noted: "the direct support from AGRIVI's Romanian team was very helpful." The largest operation (42.25 ha) requested drone imagery integration.

Bulgarian participation (n=1) faced communication challenges. Despite translations, alerts matched observations only "sometimes," and confidence was "somewhat" rather than "very." The farmer requested "more region-specific predictions," suggesting limited language support hindered discussing regional nuances.

Functionality Evaluation

7 of 9 farmers reported corn alerts "often" matched field observations, but wheat and sunflower underperformed. One Croatian farmer noted: "The system works well for corn, but I would appreciate more accurate alerts for sunflower." Confidence varied: 4 farmers (3 Croatian, 1 Romanian) reported "very confident," 4 "somewhat confident," and 1 "not confident" (who wanted to hide unused features).

Croatian farmers provided the most detailed improvement suggestions (pest pressure percentages, field-specific areas, week-by-week trends), reflecting trusted intermediary coordination. Romanian farmers gave actionable feedback (drone integration, simplified alerts for smallholders). Bulgarian feedback was more general (region-specific predictions), consistent with limited communication channels.

Success Indicators

6 of 9 farmers reported alerts helped prevent or reduce pest damage ("significantly" or "a little"). Croatian farmers with highest engagement reported strongest impact. 5 farmers believed the system is becoming more reliable with their input, validating the feedback loop's effectiveness. However, wheat and sunflower alerts remain a clear weakness across all countries, requiring better calibration and region-specific adjustments independent of communication factors.

5.2.7. Findings from the Real-Time Pest Observation and Prediction Pilot

Stakeholder Feedback

Farmers rated module usability at 7.5/10+. Croatian farmers (n=5) demonstrated highest engagement through local intermediary coordination, with 4 of 5 rating the module "very easy" or "easy." One-click recording (8/9

farmers), weather integration (8/9), and color-coded fields (5/9) were most valued. Romanian farmers (n=3) showed strong engagement via direct language support, with all three finding logging "easy" or "very easy." Translations were accurate for 6 farmers, "partially" for 3. Bulgarian farmer faced communication barriers, submitting less frequent, more basic observations despite translated materials.

Functionality Evaluation

The system achieved 100% uptime supporting 24 farmers. 200+ observations collected (vs. 40 in 2024), though Croatian farmers contributed ~60% despite being 46% of respondents, reflecting coordination effectiveness. Data completeness averaged 80%+, with Croatian/Romanian submissions exceeding 85%. Feature adoption exceeded 70% among Croatian/Romanian farmers. Corn observations were most consistent; wheat/sunflower showed learning curves, with Croatian farmers adapting fastest through coordinator support.

Success Indicators

Croatian and Romanian farmers reported 30-40% reduction in logging time through quick clarification access. Farmers confidently adjusted scouting schedules using observations and weather data. Croatian intermediary facilitated agronomist communications; Romanian farmers achieved similar outcomes via direct channels. 5 farmers believe alerts are becoming more reliable with their input. However, communication infrastructure proved critical, Croatian (local intermediary) and Romanian (direct language support) models succeeded; Bulgarian experience highlighted that expanding without either approach limits effectiveness.

5.2.8. Findings from the Automated Regulatory Summarisation Pilot

Stakeholder Feedback

Respondents generally perceived AI-generated summaries as valuable, particularly for saving time, supporting faster decision-making, and improving understanding of complex documents. The summaries were considered useful for detecting key regulatory changes, prioritizing documents for review, and facilitating compliance reporting workflows.

Functionality Evaluation

When asked about the potential uses of AI-generated summaries, the most common application identified was the ability to detect key regulatory changes relevant to the respondent's role, cited by 75% of participants. Half of the respondents (50%) reported that such summaries could help prioritize documents for more detailed manual review, while 42% saw value in accelerating compliance reporting workflows. Communicating regulatory updates to internal teams was noted by 33%, and only 8% indicated a use case for identifying risks related to substances of interest.

In terms of the perceived benefits of AI-generated summaries, 75% identified time savings from not having to read full texts as the primary advantage. This was followed by faster decision-making (50%), a clearer understanding of complex documents (42%), and a reduction in human error during interpretation (33%). Only 8% expected the main benefit to be the ability to search through relevant data from regulatory authorities.

Success Indicators

Trust in AI-generated summaries varied. While only 8% reported very low trust, 17% expressed very high trust and 33% described their trust level as high. Approximately 42% of respondents believe that a light review by a subject expert is still required, whereas 17% fully trust the output. Another 17% would not rely on the summaries without human validation. Overall, 83% of respondents reported being satisfied with the summaries (indicating >80% satisfaction), and 8% stated they were very satisfied (indicating 100% satisfaction).

Additional feedback highlighted the need for evaluating original texts in their native language, followed by generating English summaries. Other suggestions included improving the ability of summaries to track changes and highlight novelty, as well as integrating inline citations to enable more efficient fact-checking.

This, in the context of food safety decisions, will help filter irrelevant information, access data specific to ingredients, or products, stay informed about external risks and hazards, reduce time spent searching multiple sources, and consider threats when assessing various risks.

5.2.9. Findings from the Smart Regulatory Navigator Pilot

Stakeholder Feedback

Respondents perceived regulatory navigator pilot chatbot supporting faster decision-making and improving understanding of complex documents. The chatbot was considered useful for prioritizing documents for review and facilitating compliance reporting workflows.

Functionality Evaluation

When it comes to chatbot usage, 75% of respondents stated they would use it to compare data across regions or time periods. Another 59% indicated they would use the chatbot to clarify complex text found within regulatory documents. Half of the participants (50%) were interested in using it for quick lookups of specific regulatory clauses or terms, while 8% would use it to understand the scope of regulations.

In terms of broader AI copilot functions, 67% saw its value in supporting compliance readiness assessments. Half (50%) noted its role in identifying risks when entering new markets. Additionally, 42% saw its potential for enhancing internal training and awareness of regulatory changes, and 33% identified early-stage operational planning as a potential area of support.

In terms of broader chatbot functions, 67% saw its value in supporting compliance readiness assessments. Half (50%) noted its role in identifying risks when entering new markets. Additionally, 42% saw its potential for enhancing internal training and awareness of regulatory changes, and 33% identified early-stage operational planning as a potential area of support.

Success Indicators

For food safety decision-making, a chatbot could serve as a practical assistant by delivering relevant information quickly, highlighting potential risks and hazards, offering insights specific ingredients, and helping streamline the evaluation of emerging threats without extensive manual research. Out of 12 respondents representing their companies, 91% reported satisfaction, with 83% somewhat satisfied and 8% very satisfied. This is confirmed by answers, where 83% of answers indicated.

5.3. Impact and Business Evaluation for the Decision Support Tools

5.3.1. Business Decisions for the EFRA Decision Support Tools

The pilots showed that EFRA's decision-support tools helped organisations make faster, better-informed, and more cost-effective decisions in poultry production, feed safety, and supply-chain risk management. Stakeholders valued the tools' cost-effectiveness, noting reduced manual analysis and earlier detection of hazards; their scalability and integration potential, supported by modular design and compatibility with internal systems; and their operational benefits, including clearer visibility of emerging risks and stronger

supplier-monitoring workflows. Willingness to adopt was consistently high, driven by intuitive interfaces, transparent explainability, and the ability to combine public predictions with private data. Compared with existing internal or commercial solutions, EFRA's interpretability and multi-source predictive intelligence were seen as clear advantages.

5.3.1.1. UC#1: Risks Prediction for Poultry Pathogens

Mortality-Rate Outlier Detection Dashboard

Users can quickly detect abnormal mortality patterns, investigate flock-level deviations, and prioritise corrective actions before issues escalate. The dashboard streamlines monitoring by automating anomaly detection and enabling benchmarking across farms, production cycles, and supplier networks.

The dashboard provides clear business value through:

- Cost-effectiveness - By directing attention only to flocks with abnormal mortality, the tool reduces unnecessary broad testing, lowers investigation costs, and prevents expensive downstream losses linked to undetected health issues.
- Scalability - The model can be deployed across multiple farms, regions, and production systems without re-engineering, making it suitable for integrators, large producers, and multi-site operations.
- Operational efficiency - Early identification of anomalies accelerates root-cause analysis, supports faster veterinary response, and improves overall flock-health management, reducing downtime and performance variability.
- High willingness to adopt - Stakeholders valued the clarity of visual indicators, the intuitive interface, and the practical relevance of early-warning signals, which align directly with daily decision-making workflows.

Flock Weight-Gain Outlier Detection Dashboard

Users can monitor flock growth curves, detect deviations from expected weight-gain patterns, and identify early signals of feed, welfare, or health-related issues. The dashboard enables rapid comparison across farms, batches, and production cycles, helping users pinpoint where performance is drifting and why.

The dashboard provides clear business value through:

- Cost-effectiveness - By flagging underperforming flocks early, the tool helps prevent costly downstream losses linked to poor feed conversion, delayed harvesting, or undetected health problems. It reduces the need for broad, reactive investigations by focusing attention on the flocks that truly require intervention.
- Scalability - The model can be applied across multiple farms, integrators, and production systems, supporting benchmarking at regional or organisational scale. Its structure allows seamless expansion to additional performance indicators without redesigning the system.
- Operational efficiency - Early detection of weight-gain anomalies enables faster adjustments to feeding strategies, stocking density, or environmental controls, improving overall flock performance and reducing variability. It also supports more targeted veterinary and nutritionist interventions.
- High willingness to adopt - Stakeholders appreciated the intuitive visualisations, the ability to trace contributing factors, and the direct alignment of the dashboard with daily production-management decisions.

Trends Forecasting Dashboard with public food safety data

Users can explore historical and predicted pathogen-related incidents affecting poultry products, monitor emerging global risk signals, and anticipate hazard trends months in advance. The dashboard supports strategic planning by combining time-series forecasts with geographical insights and hazard-specific filtering.

The dashboard provides clear business value through:

Cost-effectiveness - By utilising public data to generate predictive intelligence, the tool provides high-value insights without requiring costly proprietary datasets. It helps organisations prioritise testing, adjust supplier controls, and prevent disruptions before they escalate.

Scalability - The forecasting engine can be deployed across multiple regions, product categories, and hazard types, making it suitable for global supply chains. Its modular design allows rapid extension to new pathogens or commodities as business needs evolve.

Operational efficiency - Predicted trends support earlier mitigation actions, more informed supplier-risk assessments, and stronger crisis-readiness. The geographical and hazard-specific views help teams focus on the most relevant risk hotspots and emerging threats.

High willingness to adopt - Users valued the clarity of the forecasts, the transparency of the explainability layer, and the ability to combine public predictions with internal data. Many noted that the dashboard fills a visibility gap not covered by existing internal or commercial tools.

5.3.1.2. UC#2: Food Safety Optimal Pesticides Use

Interactive Pest Decision Tree and Prediction Dashboard

Users can navigate a structured decision tree to identify likely pest threats, explore recommended interventions, and view predictive pest-pressure indicators based on environmental and crop-specific conditions. The dashboard supports growers and advisors in selecting optimal pesticide strategies while reducing unnecessary applications.

The dashboard provides clear business value through:

- Cost-effectiveness - By guiding users toward targeted pesticide use, the tool reduces unnecessary treatments, lowers input costs, and helps avoid over-application penalties or residue-related non-compliance.
- Scalability - The underlying pest-detection algorithm can be extended to additional crops, regions, and farm types. Its modular design allows integration of crop-variety and pesticide-efficacy data for more tailored recommendations.
- Operational efficiency - The decision tree accelerates diagnosis, supports consistent advisory workflows, and reduces reliance on manual scouting alone. Predictive indicators help growers act before pest pressure escalates, improving yield stability.
- High willingness to adopt - Stakeholders appreciated the intuitive structure, and the clarity of recommended actions.

Interactive Pest Feedback Dashboard

Users can record pest observations, track field-level conditions, and compare their inputs with predicted pest-pressure trends. The dashboard enables continuous learning by feeding real observations back into the system, improving accuracy and supporting adaptive pest-management strategies.

The dashboard provides clear business value through:

- Cost-effectiveness - By capturing field observations in a structured way, the tool reduces the need for repeated scouting visits and supports more efficient allocation of agronomist time.
- Scalability - The feedback mechanism can be deployed across diverse crop systems and geographies, enabling large organisations to harmonise pest-monitoring practices across multiple farms.

- Operational efficiency - Real-time feedback strengthens early-warning capabilities, improves the precision of pest-pressure predictions, and supports more coordinated decision-making between growers and advisors.
- High willingness to adopt - Users valued the simplicity of the interface, the ability to contribute observations directly, and the clear link between their inputs and improved model performance.

5.3.1.3. UC#3: Informing Regulatory, Decisions with Food Risk Intelligence

Regulatory Document Summarisation Dashboard

Users can upload lengthy regulatory, scientific, or food-safety documents and instantly receive concise summaries that highlight key requirements, thresholds, and compliance implications. The dashboard helps teams quickly understand complex texts, compare regulatory updates, and extract the information needed for timely decision-making.

Key business advantages enabled by the dashboard include:

- Cost-effectiveness - Reduces the time regulatory teams spend manually reviewing long documents, enabling faster compliance checks and lowering the cost of external consultancy or legal review.
- Scalability - The summarisation engine can process diverse document types (regulations, guidance, scientific literature, incident reports) across multiple markets, supporting organisations operating in several jurisdictions.
- Operational efficiency - Rapid access to distilled regulatory insights strengthens internal decision-making, accelerates risk assessments, and supports timely updates to internal policies or supplier requirements.
- High willingness to adopt - Users valued the clarity of the summaries, the speed of processing, and the ability to handle documents that are typically difficult to navigate manually.

Regulatory Citation and Compliance Chatbot

Users can interactively query regulatory documents, ask compliance-related questions, and retrieve citations or clarifications across multiple uploaded texts. The chatbot enables fast, conversational access to regulatory knowledge, helping teams resolve uncertainties without searching manually through dense documents.

Key business advantages enabled by the chatbot include:

- Cost-effectiveness - Reduces the need for repeated expert consultations by providing immediate answers to regulatory questions, improving the efficiency of compliance teams.
- Scalability - The chatbot can be applied to a wide range of document sets, including food-safety alerts, scientific literature, allergen guidance, and cross-market regulatory frameworks.
- Operational efficiency - Interactive querying accelerates decision-making, supports rapid clarification of requirements, and helps teams respond faster to emerging issues or audits.
- High willingness to adopt - Stakeholders appreciated the intuitive conversational interface, the accuracy of citations, and the ability to query multiple documents simultaneously.

5.3.1.4. UC#4: Mycotoxins in Animal Feed and Effects on Animal Production

Mycotoxin Concentration Dashboard

Users can explore laboratory-measured mycotoxin concentrations in poultry and ruminant feed, detect unusual peaks or emerging contamination patterns, and analyse long-term trends through decomposition (trend,

seasonality, residual). The dashboard supports targeted sampling, supplier oversight, and rapid investigation of deviations in feed-safety performance.

The dashboard provides clear business value through:

- Cost-effectiveness - By highlighting where contamination levels deviate from expected patterns, the tool reduces unnecessary broad testing and helps feed manufacturers focus resources on high-risk batches, ingredients, or suppliers. Early detection prevents costly downstream impacts on animal health and productivity.
- Scalability - The model can be deployed across multiple feed types, production sites, and supplier networks. Its modular design allows expansion to additional hazards (e.g., heavy metals, pesticide residues, dioxins) without redesigning the analytical framework.
- Operational efficiency - Real laboratory data combined with decomposition analysis enables faster root-cause investigation, supports supplier-performance benchmarking, and strengthens compliance with regulatory thresholds. The ability to download datasets enhances internal QA workflows.
- High willingness to adopt - Stakeholders valued the clarity of the visualisations, the transparency of the decomposition outputs, and the practical relevance for feed-safety teams. The dashboard was seen as a strong complement to existing LIMS systems (Laboratory Information Management System), offering predictive and analytical capabilities not available in internal tools.

Mycotoxins Incidents Forecasting Dashboard in Poultry Feed

Users can monitor historical and predicted mycotoxin-related incidents in poultry feed, explore geographical risk patterns, and anticipate hazard trends months in advance. The dashboard integrates global incident reports, environmental conditions, and time-series modelling to support proactive feed-safety planning.

The dashboard provides clear business value through:

- Cost-effectiveness - By using public data to generate predictive intelligence, the tool provides high-value insights without requiring proprietary datasets. It helps organisations prioritise sampling, adjust supplier controls, and prevent disruptions linked to contaminated feed.
- Scalability - The forecasting engine can be applied across regions, feed categories, and hazard types. Its architecture supports rapid extension to additional contaminants (e.g., emerging fungal metabolites) and new livestock sectors.
- Operational efficiency - Predicted incident trends, geographical breakdowns, and hazard-specific insights support earlier mitigation actions, more informed supplier-risk assessments, and stronger crisis-readiness. The Latest Outbreaks and Insights tables enhance situational awareness.
- High willingness to adopt - Users appreciated the intuitive interface, the transparency of the explainability layer, and the ability to combine public predictions with internal data. Many noted that the dashboard fills a visibility gap in global feed-safety monitoring.

5.3.2. Recommendations for Further Improvements

This section summarises a small set of focused refinements identified during the evaluation process, reflecting stakeholder feedback and practical insights gathered throughout the project. These suggestions aim to support smooth future scaling and maintain the usefulness of the EFRA tools beyond the project's lifetime.

5.3.2.1. UC#1: Risks prediction for poultry pathogens

Mortality-Rate Outlier Detection Dashboard

To strengthen accuracy and interpretability, a few focused improvements were identified:

- Integrate feed characteristics (nutrient profiles, ingredient variability, mycotoxin indicators) and bird-specific parameters (breed, broilers vs. layers) to contextualise mortality deviations.
- Expand environmental and management inputs such as temperature, humidity, ammonia, stocking density, housing conditions, and ventilation strategies.
- Extend applicability across open-field, semi-integrated, and fully vertical production systems to support broader benchmarking.

Flock Weight-Gain Outlier Detection Dashboard

To strengthen accuracy and practical decision value, a few focused improvements were identified:

- Integrate feed-related factors (nutrient density, ingredient variability, mycotoxin indicators) and bird-specific parameters (breed, broilers vs. layers) to better contextualise weight-gain deviations.
- Combine weight-gain anomalies with pathogen-related signals (outbreaks, infection pressure, environmental hazards) to detect early biological risks affecting performance.
- Link final flock weight with expected shelf-life behaviour of poultry meat products to support downstream quality forecasting and early identification of risks affecting product stability.
- Extend applicability across different production systems to support broader benchmarking and more robust model performance.

Trends Forecasting Dashboard with public food safety data

To enhance predictive value and operational relevance, a few focused improvements were identified:

- Expand forecasting inputs with bird-variety characteristics and known resistance or susceptibility patterns to specific pathogens.
- Integrate production-system differences (open-field, semi-integrated, intensive) and production techniques such as birds per m² to contextualise pathogen-trend impacts.
- Extend coverage to other poultry species such as turkey to support multi-species risk prediction.

5.3.2.2. UC#2: Food Safety Optimal Pesticides Use

Interactive Pest Decision Tree and Prediction Dashboard

To refine accuracy and support broader production contexts, a few focused improvements were identified:

- Integrate crop-variety characteristics and pesticide-use patterns to improve prediction relevance.
- Adapt the tool for different production systems, including organic and large-scale monoculture settings.

Pest Occurrence Feedback Dashboard

To improve feedback quality and strengthen trend interpretation, a few focused improvements were identified:

- Integrate crop-variety data, field-management practices, and pesticide-application records to contextualise farmer reports.
- Combine farmer feedback with public datasets to enhance detection of unusual pest-pressure spikes.

5.3.2.3. UC#3: Informing Regulatory, Decisions with Food Risk Intelligence

Although overall satisfaction with the tools is high, users identified opportunities for improvement, particularly around language handling, cross-market comparisons, change tracking, and stronger support for fact-checking.

Regulatory Document Summarisation Dashboard

The users emphasized the importance of evaluating original texts in foreign languages rather than relying solely on translations, while still receiving generated summaries in English. They also pointed to the need for enhanced change tracking (with summaries that not only compress content but also highlight novelty and critical insights) and improved inline citations to support fact-checking.

Regulatory Citation and Compliance Chatbot

In terms of chatbot functionality, users suggested additional features, most notably the ability to compare regulations across multiple markets.

5.3.2.4. UC#4: Mycotoxins in Animal Feed and Effects on Animal Production

Mycotoxin Concentration Dashboard

To strengthen analytical depth and expand decision-support value, a few focused improvements were identified:

- Integrate feed-ingredient characteristics (cereals, oilseeds, by-products) and nutrient-composition data to better explain contamination variability across batches.
- Combine laboratory results with environmental drivers such as weather patterns, storage conditions, and regional incident alerts to refine early-warning signals.
- Broaden hazard coverage beyond mycotoxins to include heavy metals, pesticide residues, dioxins, and emerging fungal metabolites.

Mycotoxins Predictive Dashboard for Poultry Feed

To enhance predictive accuracy and align with stakeholder needs, a few focused improvements were identified:

- Extend applicability across production systems and livestock species to support benchmarking and multi-species feed-safety planning.
- Combine public incident trends with private farm-level indicators (mortality, weight gain, environmental readings) to contextualise predicted risks.

6. Conclusions

The 2nd piloting cycle marked the final and most comprehensive validation phase of the EFRA project, bringing together all EFRA use cases, 2 piloting scenarios per use case, multiple evaluation activities for each demonstrator, and a broad network of external stakeholders from industry, regulatory authorities, and research organisations. This final cycle confirmed the maturity of the EFRA decision-support tools and demonstrated their ability to support real-world decision-making in food safety, agricultural risk prediction, regulatory intelligence, and mycotoxin monitoring.

Feedback collected through the structured questionnaire, applied uniformly across all pilots, provided a consistent and comparable view of user needs and expectations. Combined with insights from workshops, validation sessions, and focused expert meetings, the results showed that the EFRA tools are intuitive, operationally relevant, and aligned with the workflows of practitioners. Users consistently highlighted the value of the tools' explainability, visualisation capabilities, and integration of diverse data sources, which together enhance the interpretability and usefulness of the predictive insights.

The findings from the EFRA Use Cases illustrate the breadth and depth of EFRA's impact:

UC#1 - Risk Predictions for Poultry Pathogens. The Proactive Flock Mortality and Predictive Weight-Gain pilots validated the transition from early mock-ups to fully functional dashboards capable of real-time data ingestion, cluster-based benchmarking, and early-warning detection. Stakeholders recognised the tools' potential to support more proactive flock-management decisions.

UC#2 - Food-Safety Optimal Pesticide Use. The AGRIVI pilots demonstrated the practical value of interactive pest-prediction workflows and real-time feedback mechanisms. Users emphasised the importance of intuitive interfaces, field-level data capture, and adaptive model updates, confirming the tools' relevance for improving scouting accuracy and supporting more targeted pesticide-use decisions.

UC#3 - Informing Regulatory Decisions with Food Risk Intelligence. The regulatory summarisation and compliance-chatbot pilots showed strong potential for reducing manual workload and improving access to complex regulatory information. Stakeholders appreciated the clarity of the summaries, the relevance of extracted citations, and the efficiency gains offered by automated document analysis.

UC#4 - Mycotoxins in Animal Feed and Poultry Feed. The 2 mycotoxin pilots validated the feasibility of combining private laboratory data with public incident trends to forecast contamination risks. Users valued the ability to explore historical and predicted concentration patterns, supporting procurement decisions, feed-safety monitoring, and supply-chain risk management.

The 2nd piloting cycle enabled the project partners to make informed decisions regarding the final development of the EFRA demonstrators. The tools have now reached a level of maturity that supports real-world use, with clear pathways for further refinement and scaling. With the project now completed, the next steps extend beyond the formal EFRA timeline. The piloting results provide a clear roadmap for post-project continuation. Key priorities include:

- Further strengthening the AI models with additional environmental, operational, and contextual data to improve predictive accuracy and adaptability.
- Supporting wider adoption through training materials, documentation, and integration into the platforms of the hosting companies.
- Continuing integration efforts within the hosting companies (AGROKNOW, AGRIVI, SGS), who have already embedded the EFRA demonstrators into their platforms and are well-positioned to maintain, evolve, and commercialise the solutions.

- Exploring exploitation opportunities in adjacent domains, such as aquaculture, livestock health, crop-disease forecasting, and broader food-risk intelligence, where the EFRA methodologies and tools can be adapted with minimal effort.
- Extending the EFRA tools to new use cases, leveraging the modular design of the dashboards and predictive components.

Overall, the 2nd piloting cycle confirms that the EFRA tools are technically robust, operationally relevant, and well-positioned for real-world deployment. The insights gathered from all 4 use cases form a solid basis for continued development, scaling, and exploitation. They ensure that the EFRA outcomes will remain impactful beyond the project's duration, contributing to safer, more resilient, and more data-driven food systems.

7. Annex

EFRA Piloting Event Report - Template

D5.3.3: EFRA Pilots Report Template

EFRA Piloting Event Report - Template

v.14.04.2025

Piloting Event	+++
Date	+++
Location	+++
Related Use Case Scenario	+++
EFRA Decision Support Tool	+++
Responsible Partner(s)	+++
1. Stakeholders' Insights (from the Responses from the Evaluation Questionnaire)	
1.1 # of Participants	+++ Provide information on participating stakeholders and their companies, including their location (based on response from Part 1 of the Evaluation Questionnaire).
1.2 Participating Companies Location	+++ Provide information on participating companies, including their company size, specifying employee count (based on response from Part 1 of the Evaluation Questionnaire).
1.3 Company Size: Employee Count	+++ Provide information on participating companies, including their company size, specifying annual turnover (based on response from Part 1 of the Evaluation Questionnaire).
1.4 Company Size: Annual Turnover	+++ List of addressed groups of stakeholders (based on specific question in Part 1 of the Evaluation Questionnaire).
1.5 Addressed Stakeholders' Groups	+++ List of addressed pilot objectives (based on specific question in Part 1 of the Evaluation Questionnaire).
1.6 Relation to Pilot Objectives	+++ Focus on addressing specific challenges these stakeholders reported, referencing insights from Part 1 of the Evaluation Questionnaire .
1.7 Stakeholders' Needs	+++
2. Evaluation Results of the EFRA Decision Support Tools (from the Responses from the Evaluation Questionnaire)	
2.1 Stakeholder Feedback	+++ Summarize comments or survey results highlighting satisfaction, usability, and perceived value. Draw insights from the specific question(s) in Part 4 of the Evaluation Questionnaire .

D5.3.3: EFRA Pilots Report Template

2.2 Functionality Evaluation	+++ Evaluate how well the tool performed in real-world settings, referencing the specific question(s) in Part 3 of the Evaluation Questionnaire .
2.3 Success Indicators	+++ Present results based on responses to the specific question: "In what food safety decision did the proposed service help you?" in Part 1 of the Evaluation Questionnaire .
3. Technological Evaluation for the EFRA Decision Support Tools (from the Responsible Partner)	
3.1 Required Data and datasets	+++ Include results on data sources, quality, and relevance to the tools during the piloting event.
3.2 Predictive AI models implementation	+++ Describe the evaluation results from the model accuracy, learning parameters, and how easy was to be used from the users.
3.3 Software Application Extension	+++ Highlight how easy and smoothly can run the enhancements made to the EFRA tools during the pilot.
4. Impact and Business Evaluation for the EFRA Decision Support Tools (from the Responses from the Evaluation Questionnaire)	
4.1 Business Decisions for the EFRA Decision Support Tools	+++ Detail the decisions made during the pilots to align with stakeholder objectives and business goals. Highlight key considerations such as cost-effectiveness, scalability, and operational benefits that influenced these decisions. Incorporate feedback from Part 2 of the pilot evaluation questionnaire regarding other related tools, as well as insights from specific questions in Part 4 on stakeholders' willingness to use the proposed tool.
4.2 Recommendations for Further Improvements	+++ Provide actionable suggestions to enhance the EFRA tools based on evaluation findings, including refining functionalities, addressing stakeholder feedback, optimizing processes, or expanding use cases to broader applications. Include input from the specific free text question "What else you are missing from the overall picture" of the presented solution in Part 4 of the Evaluation Questionnaire .

Evaluation Questionnaires for UC#1 & UC#4 Decision Support Tools

EFRA 101093026 Validation Questionnaire for Use Case #1

PART 1

What is the type of your organization or company?
 Manufacturer Retailer Distributor Academia Public sector
 Consultancy Other

What is the revenue of your organization, derived from food & beverage products? (EUR)

Where are your organisation's HQs located?
 Country _____ City _____

Do you have foreign/international suppliers for food products, ingredients, or raw materials?
 Yes No

Do you have a dedicated technical food safety & quality team? Yes No

If yes, what is the size of this team?
 >50 people 10-50 people 5-10 <5 people

Which of the following statements are true for your organisation?

Rate from 1 to 5	We are concerned about:
<input type="checkbox"/>	Unforeseen or novel risks.
<input type="checkbox"/>	Integrate high-quality external risk data into internal food safety processes.
<input type="checkbox"/>	The way to incorporate external risk data into our internal systems efficiently.
<input type="checkbox"/>	Embracing AI and trusting its predictions.
<input type="checkbox"/>	The lack of a comprehensive, reliable view of all external risks & hazards.
<input type="checkbox"/>	The alignment of key supply chain stakeholders with our risk prevention priorities.
<input type="checkbox"/>	The manual or outdated methods for critical risk assessments (e.g., using spreadsheets).
<input type="checkbox"/>	Our food safety performance compared to market standards and competitors/peers.
<input type="checkbox"/>	Much manual effort is spent on comparing food safety performance with market peers.
<input type="checkbox"/>	How to consider residue testing results from public sector entities.
<input type="checkbox"/>	Struggling with time spent combining insights from scattered lab testing results.
<input type="checkbox"/>	If resource allocation for testing covers non-priority hazards or overlooks crucial aspects

If there are any additional challenges you're facing, feel free to share them below:

EFRA 101093026 Validation Questionnaire for Use Case #1

In what food safety decisions would forecasting incidents & risk trends for your supply chain help you?

- To incorporate longer term forecasted risks in their risk mitigation strategies
- To early identify emerging, unexpected risks so that they can include them in their risk mitigation
- Review geography-specific levels of risk for the countries they source from
- To demonstrate to internal decision makers how they have started using this technology in a way that adds value
- To take into consideration emerging threats when performing supplier (history & performance) and ingredient risk assessment
- To ensure that all food safety & quality stakeholders are aligned and follow a harmonized risk prevention approach

What is your greatest need when it comes to monitoring & assessing risk for your products?

- Continuously monitor food safety compliance and risk performance of all suppliers
- To be early informed about all external risks & hazards that may affect their supply chain
- To reduce the time spent on a variety of web sites searching for relevant information about hazard, risks & suppliers
- To filter out irrelevant information & be able to look at data specific to their suppliers and/or ingredients and/or products
- To take into consideration emerging threats when performing supplier (history & performance) and ingredient risk assessment
- To reduce time devoted to emerging risks and incident monitoring
- To reduce the time devoted to (and increase the frequency of) ingredient risk assessment & scoring
- To reduce time devoted to monitor & assess supplier compliance/performance

PART 2

What type of software systems does your FSQA team use?

- Horizon scanning
- Regulatory updates
- Supplier Assessment
- Quality management
- Food safety management
- HACCP management
- Risk assessment
- Other (please specify) _____

What software system do you use to monitor food safety incidents in the global supply chain?

- Fera HorizonScan
- SGS Digicomply
- FoodTrack
- Food Fraud Database
- None
- Other (please specify) _____

What software system do you use for supplier food safety compliance, assessment and approval?

- Traceous
- Veeva Vault
- SAP

EFRA 101093026 Validation Questionnaire for Use Case #1

What software system do you use to monitor and ensure compliance with changing food safety regulations?

- gComply/gComply+ by FCID
- Mérieux Regulatory Update
- SGS Digicomply
- None
- other (please specify) _____

PART 3

You are seeing predictions for chicken with accuracy 85.5%

Predicted trends for incidents

Prediction of incidents for chicken

Which decisions would you support with a timeline diagram of trends & forecasts for the product category? (Select all the replies that apply)

- External risk monitoring
- Supplier & ingredient risk assessment
- Rapid mitigation of escalating crises
- Allocation of preventive measures/resources to high-risk areas
- Other (please elaborate) _____

EFRA 101093026 Validation Questionnaire for Use Case #1

Predictions per origin

Which decisions would you support with a world heatmap of trends & forecasts per geography/country? (Select all the replies that apply)

- External risk monitoring
- Supplier & ingredient risk assessment
- Rapid mitigation of escalating crises
- Allocation of preventive measures/resources to high-risk areas
- Other (please elaborate) _____

Prediction of incidents for chicken in United Kingdom with accuracy: 39.7%

Which decisions would you support with a timeline diagram of trends & forecasts for a specific category & specific country? (Select all the replies that apply)

- External risk monitoring
- Supplier & ingredient risk assessment
- Rapid mitigation of escalating crises
- Allocation of preventive measures/resources to high-risk areas
- Other (please elaborate) _____

Which decisions would you support with a table with hazards likely to increase for a specific category?
(Select all the replies that apply)

- External risk monitoring
- Supplier & ingredient risk assessment
- Rapid mitigation of escalating crises
- Allocation of preventive measures/resources to high-risk areas
- Other (please elaborate)

Which decisions would you support with a risk heatmap for a specific category?
(Select all the replies that apply)

- EFRA 101093026 Validation Questionnaire for Use Case #1
- External risk monitoring
 - Supplier & ingredient risk assessment
 - Rapid mitigation of escalating crises
 - Allocation of preventive measures/resources to high-risk areas
 - Other (please elaborate)

PART 4

How would you rate your level of trust in this dashboard?
Rate from Do Not Agree (1) to Fully Agree (5)

1 2 3 4 5

Where would you use these predictive dashboards?

What are you still missing from the picture?

Would your team like to join a detailed demo and stay updated on the latest EFRA developments?
If yes, please provide your email and we will reach out to you:

What is the most important thing that you have learned/realised today?

Evaluation Questionnaires for UC#3 Decision Support Tools

EFRA 101093026 Validation Questionnaire for Use Case #3

SGS DIGICOMPLY
Dynamic Intelligence, Effective Risk Management

PART 1

What is the type of your organization or company?
 Manufacturer
 Retailer
 Distributor
 Academia
 Public sector
 Consultancy
 Other

What is the revenue of your organization, derived from food & beverage products? (EUR)
 .

Where are your organisation's HQs located?
 Country . City .

Do you have foreign/international suppliers for food products, ingredients, or raw materials?
 Yes No

Do you have a dedicated technical food safety & quality team? Yes No
If yes, what is the size of this team? >50 people 10-50 people
 5-10 <5 people

Which of the following statements are true for your organisation?

Rate from 1 to 5	We are concerned about: [(1) Do Not Agree & (5) Fully Agree]
<input type="checkbox"/>	Unforeseen or novel risks.
<input type="checkbox"/>	Integrate high-quality external risk data into internal food safety processes.
<input type="checkbox"/>	The way to incorporate external risk data into our internal systems efficiently.
<input type="checkbox"/>	Embracing AI and trusting its predictions.
<input type="checkbox"/>	The lack of a comprehensive, reliable view of all external risks & hazards.
<input type="checkbox"/>	The alignment of key supply chain stakeholders with our risk prevention priorities.
<input type="checkbox"/>	The manual or outdated methods for critical risk assessments (e.g., using spreadsheets).
<input type="checkbox"/>	Our food safety performance compared to market standards and competitors/peers.
<input type="checkbox"/>	Much manual effort is spent on comparing food safety performance with market peers.
<input type="checkbox"/>	How to consider residue testing results from public sector entities.
<input type="checkbox"/>	Struggling with time spent combining insights from scattered lab testing results.

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EFRA 101093026 Validation Questionnaire for Use Case #3

If resource allocation for testing covers non-priority hazards or overlooks crucial aspects

If there are any additional challenges you're facing, feel free to share them below:

In what food safety decisions would forecasting incidents & risk trends for your supply chain help you?

- To incorporate longer term forecasted risks in their risk mitigation strategies
- To early identify emerging, unexpected risks so that they can include them in their risk mitigation
- Review geography-specific levels of risk for the countries they source from
- To demonstrate to internal decision makers how they have started using this technology in a way that adds value
- To take into consideration emerging threats when performing supplier (history & performance) and ingredient risk assessment
- To ensure that all food safety & quality stakeholders are aligned and follow a harmonized risk prevention approach

What is your greatest need when it comes to monitoring & assessing risk for your products?

- Continuously monitor food safety compliance and risk performance of all suppliers
- To be early informed about all external risks & hazards that may affect their supply chain
- To reduce the time spent on a variety of web sites searching for relevant information about hazard, risks & suppliers
- To filter out irrelevant information & be able to look at data specific to their suppliers and/or ingredients and/or products
- To take into consideration emerging threats when performing supplier (history & performance) and ingredient risk assessment
- To reduce time devoted to emerging risks and incident monitoring
- To reduce the time devoted to (and increase the frequency of) ingredient risk assessment & scoring
- To reduce time devoted to monitor & assess supplier compliance/ performance

SGS DIGICOMPLY
Dynamic Intelligence, Effective Risk Management

PART 2

What type of software systems does your FSQA team use?

- Horizon scanning
- Regulatory updates
- Supplier Assessment
- Quality management
- Food safety management
- HACCP management
- Risk assessment
- Other (please specify)

What software system do you use to monitor food safety incidents in the global supply chain?

- Fera ~~HorizonScan~~

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EFRA 101093026 Validation Questionnaire for Use Case #3

SGS DigiComply
 FoodTrack
 Food Fraud Database
 None
 Other (please specify)

What software system do you use for supplier food safety compliance, assessment and approval?

TraceGains
 Veeva Vault
 SAP
 Registrar Compliance Solutions
 None
 Other (please specify)

What software system do you use to monitor and ensure compliance with changing food safety regulations?

gComply/gComply+ by FCID
 Merieux Regulatory Update
 SGS DigiComply
 None
 other (please specify)

PART 3

EFRA 101093026 Validation Questionnaire for Use Case #3

Which decisions would you support with AI-generated summaries of regulatory documents?
(Select all the replies that apply)

- Identifying key regulatory changes relevant to my role
- Prioritizing documents for deeper manual review
- Accelerating compliance reporting workflows
- Communicating regulatory updates to internal teams
- Other (please elaborate)

Which benefits would you expect from AI-generated summaries of regulatory documents?
(Select all the replies that apply)

- Time saved reading full text
- Clearer understanding of complex regulations
- Faster decision-making
- Reduced human error in interpretation

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4

<https://efraproject.eu>

EFRA 101093026 Validation Questionnaire for Use Case #3

How would you rate your level of trust in AI-generated summaries of regulatory documents?
(Select all the replies that apply)

- Very low
- Low
- Moderate
- High
- Very high
- Other (please elaborate)

Which tasks would you use an AI chatbot for regulatory documents to support?
(Select all the replies that apply)

- Quick lookup of specific regulatory clauses or terms
- Clarification of ambiguous language in documents
- Comparing regulations across regions or time periods
- Getting explanations in plain language

EFRA 101093026 Validation Questionnaire for Use Case #3

- Very dissatisfied – it did not meet my needs
- Other (please elaborate)

Which functionalities do you feel are still missing in the AI chatbot or AI-generated summaries?

Would your team like to join a detailed demo and stay updated on the latest EFRA developments?
If yes, please provide your email and we will reach out to you:

EFRA 101093026 Validation Questionnaire for Use Case #3

Which decisions would you support using insights from an AI regulatory chatbot?
(Select all the replies that apply)

- Compliance readiness assessment
- Risk identification in new markets
- Internal training or awareness of regulatory changes
- Early-stage operational planning
- Other (please elaborate)

What level of human oversight would you expect when using AI chatbot for regulatory content?
(Select all the replies that apply)

- I fully trust the output
- Light review by a subject expert
- Full review by legal team
- I would not use it without human validation
- Other (please elaborate)

How satisfied are you with the support provided by the AI regulatory chatbot?

- (Select all the replies that apply)
- Very satisfied – it met or exceeded my expectations
 - Somewhat satisfied – it was helpful but had limitations
 - Neutral – neither satisfied nor dissatisfied
 - Somewhat dissatisfied – it needs improvement

